

**TRIANGULATING DIGITAL MATURITY, ORGANIZATIONAL
EFFICIENCY, AND EMPLOYEES' PERFORMANCE: PIONEERING A
PROGRESSIVE BUSINESS TRANSFORMATION MODEL**

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This study examines the interconnectedness of organizational efficiency, employee performance, and maturity level within digital transformation initiatives in business technology companies. It further explores how insights into these factors can guide top management in evaluating organizational maturity and addressing performance gaps through the Progressive Business Transformation Model (PBTM).

Employing a mixed-methods approach, the study collected data via self-assessment surveys, interviews with 18 participants, and responses from 328 employees across three technology firms in Makati City. Most respondents were younger millennials, a trend likely driven by the industry's demand for adaptability to new technologies, revealing a need to bridge generational skill gaps. Results indicate that educational attainment correlates with higher performance and efficiency but has a limited impact on maturity. High digital maturity aligns closely with improved performance and organizational efficiency, suggesting a pathway to enhanced competitiveness.

The PBTM offers a structured guide for business technology companies to assess, plan, and measure digital transformation efforts. This study contributes to continuous improvement by validating the PBTM's role in enhancing both organizational efficiency and employee outcomes.

Keywords: *Business Technology, Human Resources, Maturity level, Digital transformation*

Chapter 1

INTRODUCTION

This section lays the essential groundwork for the research by including several critical components. It encompasses the background to provide context, a literature review to support the study, and the theoretical and conceptual frameworks based on the analysis. Additionally, it outlines the problem statement, delineates the scope and its limitations, highlights the significance, and clarifies vital conditions. Together, these elements present a clear direction and comprehensive framework for the research endeavor.

Background of the Study

An unyielding pursuit of enhanced employee performance marks the contemporary business landscape. As businesses strive to remain competitive in the face of technological advancements, the imperative to refine workforce skills and align them with evolving digital contexts becomes paramount (International Labour Organization, 2023). This research explores the potential relationship between an organization's level of maturity, its efficiency, and these critical employee factors.

Maturity, in this context, denotes an organization's capability to effectively leverage business digital technologies in pursuit of strategic objectives (Cao, Wang,

& Zhu, 2021). A digitally mature organization seamlessly integrates technology across its operations, cultivating a culture of innovation and flexibility.

The current study seeks to establish a pioneering business transformation model premised on heightened maturity, fostering a more productive, high-performing, and engaged workforce. Employee productivity, defined as the quantity and quality of work output per unit of invested time, is a crucial facet under examination (International Labour Organization, 2023). Meanwhile, employee performance encompasses the successful completion of tasks and objectives aligned with organizational goals (Society for Human Resource Management, n.d.), while engagement of employees reflects the degree of enthusiasm, dedication, and commitment employees demonstrate.

This research unravels the intricate connections between these dimensions to give business leaders valuable insights for navigating the complexities of digital transformation. The resulting findings hold the potential to inform the development of strategies for leveraging technology to nurture a thriving workforce and achieve sustainable organizational success.

The swift progression of emerging technologies within the work environment is unavoidable and poised to bring significant changes across various organizations. The impact of digitalization is already being felt across different industries, necessitating the integration of emerging technologies and the

transformation of business models to sustain competitiveness (Trenerry et al., 2021).

Despite the extensive academic attention on the impact of digital technology in reshaping job tasks and professions, there is limited insight into how employees and businesses can successfully adapt to disruptive technological advancements (Trenerry et al., 2021). A key concern is identifying ways to empower organizations and employees, which are crucial in driving digital transformation. Given this context, the noticeable gap in empirical research linking various phases of digital transformation to organizational performance raises an important question: To what extent should firms undergo digital transformation? This inquiry, as noted by (Verhoef et al., 2021), remains a significant puzzle.

On the other hand, the attrition rate in the Philippines is believed to be between 30% and 40%, which is more significant compared to the national average across all sectors and industries, despite several attempts to improve staff efficiency (MagellanSolutions, 2022). This high attrition rate exacerbates the industry's talent shortage, creating business challenges in sustaining skilled personnel.

Employees are considered to be an organization's highest-valued asset. Employee performance, engagement, and productivity directly impact an organization's productivity. Hence, bridging the gap with its workforce is vital for any organization to develop and progress.

The study seeks to uncover the interconnectedness of organizational efficiency, employees' performance, and maturity level within business digital transformation. It also seeks to explore how understanding these factors can inform top management and its leadership about the organization's maturity level and its implications to initiate a discourse on bridging existing gaps through the lens of the Progressive Business Transformation Model.

Review of Related Literature and Studies

This part comprehensively consolidates relevant research and related insights on the organizational level of maturity and efficiency vis-a-vis employees' performance, engagement, and productivity in the business technology sector to pioneer a progressive business transformation model. It draws upon diverse sources, including electronic resources, books, periodicals, and relevant publications, to equip the researcher with the needed context and information to conduct this research.

The topics covered include (1) The Philippine IT-BPO: Past Growth and Current Trends Update; (2) Workplace Transformation: Igniting Business Revolution (3) Business Digitalization: A Catalyst for Organizational Efficiency (4) Assessing Maturity: Performance, Engagement, and Productivity (5) Progressive Business Transformation: Embracing Change for Sustainability and Growth.

The Philippine IT-BPO: Past Growth and Current Trends

According to Jones Lang LaSalle Incorporated (2023), the Business Process Outsourcing (BPO) industry in the Philippines has experienced substantial growth in recent years, contributing 7.5% to the country's total GDP in 2021. Data from the IT and Business Process Association of the Philippines (IBPAP) indicates that the industry's revenue and workforce have steadily increased, with a compounded annual growth rate of 5.1% and 4.6%, respectively, from 2016 to 2022. This growth has persisted despite the economic challenges posed by the pandemic and global macroeconomic pressures.

According to the latest report from the Philippine Statistics Authority, there are 851 listed BPOs and 429 call centers in the country (Tality, 2023). Based on these figures, the Central Bank of the Philippines projects a 10% raise in industry revenue of about US\$24.5 billion. Since establishing the BPO sector in 1992, it has grown significantly and earned a strong reputation as a global leader. Over nearly three decades, the country has held the title of "The BPO Capital of the World" since 2010 (MagellanSolutions, 2022).

The year 2020 posed significant challenges for businesses across industries globally. However, the IT-BPO sector has demonstrated resilience in the face of the global health crisis. The trajectory of the Philippines' IT-BPO industry is nothing short of remarkable. From its modest beginnings two decades ago to becoming the second most popular outsourcing destination globally, it has

consistently defied expectations. With a significant contribution to the country's GDP, employment to millions, and boasting a reputation as the BPO Capital of the World, the industry stands as a beacon of success.

However, the high attrition rate in the Philippines, believed to be between 30% and 40%, remains a significant challenge. Despite several attempts to improve staff efficiency, it exceeds the national average across all industries and sectors (MagellanSolutions, 2022). This high attrition rate exacerbates the talent shortage in the industry, making it challenging for companies to sustain a skilled workforce. Addressing this issue is crucial for sustaining the industry's growth and success.

Workplace Transformation: Igniting the Business Revolution

The business digital revolution is fundamentally transforming the modern workplace. This section explores Workplace Digital Transformation (WDT), its impact on organizations and employees, and the key drivers and challenges associated with this transition. WDT extends beyond merely adopting new software. It signifies a comprehensive shift in how work is conducted, how employees collaborate, and how organizations interact with stakeholders and customers (Trenerry et al., 2021).

Several factors are propelling organizations toward WDT. Evolving customer expectations demand seamless and personalized experiences, which digital tools and automation can deliver. Fierce competition in the digital age

necessitates leveraging technology to enhance efficiency, agility, and innovation. Additionally, advancements in cloud computing, data analytics, and artificial intelligence open new opportunities for optimizing workflows and gaining valuable insights.

According to Trenerry et al. (2021), age, education, job level, and other personal characteristics might influence how individuals experience and adapt to digital change. However, it does not directly measure these characteristics or their impact on maturity. While providing a helpful framework, additional study is required, focusing on collecting demographic data and measuring maturity to understand their connection fully.

A successful WDT can yield significant benefits for organizations. Digital tools can streamline routine processes, optimize workflows, and enhance collaboration, resulting in a more productive workforce. Data analytics empowers organizations to make data-driven decisions, achieving a more effective resource allocation and better overall results. WDT fosters a culture of experimentation and exploration, paving the way for innovation. Additionally, modern digital tools create a more engaging work environment, encouraging employee participation and knowledge sharing.

Integrating workplace transformation requires a comprehensive understanding of maturity, which can be assessed across several critical dimensions. According to the South Australian Government's Digital

Transformation Toolkit (2022), these dimensions include Leadership and Governance, Culture and People, Capability and Capacity, and Technology and Innovation. **Leadership** involves evaluating an organization's leaders' strategic vision and commitment toward digital transformation. **People** refer to the workforce and talent within the organization, focusing on the skills, roles, and engagement that drive performance. **Culture** encompasses the beliefs, shared values, and behaviors that build organizational environments that influence employee interactions. It focuses on the workforce's readiness, adaptability, and overall cultural support for digital initiatives. **Capacity** pertains to the resources and infrastructure available to the organization, including staffing, budget, and physical assets that support operations. **Capability** assesses the skills and competencies required to execute strategies and achieve objectives, driving digital change. Finally, **Technology** evaluates the current technological infrastructure and its capacity to support and enhance digital initiatives. By systematically assessing these dimensions, organizations can identify strengths and areas for improvement, facilitating a more effective and seamless digital transformation process.

However, WDT also presents challenges. Employees may be apprehensive about adopting new technologies and adapting to changed work processes. The growing dependence on technology requires strong data security practices to safeguard sensitive information. Furthermore, organizations may face skill gaps within their workforce, requiring investment in upskilling and reskilling programs.

Business Digitalization: A Catalyst for Organizational Efficiency

Research by Guo and Xu (2021) delves into the effects of business digitalization on organizational performance, focusing mainly on financial, operational, and marketing aspects. Their study scrutinizes the connection between digital transformation and business operations and financial outcomes, revealing that the impact of digitalization on business efficiency tends to be more enduring than its effect on financial performance.

Digitalization offers a broad spectrum of benefits that significantly contribute to organizational efficiency. Firstly, it streamlines the automation of routine and labor-intensive tasks through digital platforms. This automation liberates employee time, engaging them in more strategic activities such as data analysis, customer service improvements, and financial planning (Wamba et al., 2020). Additionally, digital tools such as cloud-based platforms and instant messaging applications enhance communication and collaboration across teams and departments. This seamless interaction fosters an agile and responsive work environment, enabling faster decision-making and more efficient project execution. In addition to improved communication, digitalization enhances data management and analytics capabilities. Organizations can collect, store, and analyze vast data, leveraging business intelligence to extract insights. These insights enable organizations to recognize emerging trends, modernize processes, and make informed, data-driven choices, ultimately driving efficacy (Cao, Schniederjans, &

Schniederjans, 2021). Furthermore, digital technologies facilitate remote work arrangements, enhancing employee productivity and satisfaction. The flexibility offered by remote work schedules also aids in attracting and retaining top talent, further bolstering organizational efficiency. By integrating digital technologies across various business functions, organizations enhance operational efficiency and drive innovation, responsiveness, and long-term sustainability.

It is essential to understand that organizations vary significantly by type of service, years in operation, employee headcount, and business size. Businesses span various sectors such as manufacturing, retail, healthcare, technology, and finance (U.S. Bureau of Labor Statistics, 2024). Department of Trade and Industry classifies enterprises founded on asset size and its employees: micro enterprises have ₱3,000,000 or less in assets and 1-9 employees; small enterprises have ₱3,000,001 to ₱15,000,000 in assets with employees of 10-99; medium enterprises have ₱15,000,001 to ₱100,000,000 in assets with employees of 100-199; and large enterprises have over ₱100,000,001 in assets with employees of 200 or more (Philippine Institute for Development Studies, 2022).

Business digitalization is not simply about adopting the latest technology trends. It is about strategically leveraging digital tools and processes to streamline workflows, enhance communication, and empower employees. By embracing digitalization, organizations can improve efficiency, increase profitability, and have a stronger competitive position.

Assessing Maturity: People, Culture, Capacity, Capability, Technology and Leadership

The maturity assessment enables an organization to self-assess and clearly understand its current level of digital maturity. It helps determine what the organization is doing well and where improvements are needed. There are six dimensions for assessing maturity: people, culture, capacity, capability, technology, and leadership. A digital strategy or plan defines an organization's vision, purpose, and goals for employing technologies and digital solutions. It describes the obstacles and possibilities associated with digital activities, leadership, and the organization's management structure. It outlines a plan to maximize the business value of digital initiatives for the organization (Government of South Australia, 2022). According to the research by McGinty and Lylova (2020), the transformation of human resource management in modern organizations is significantly influenced by digital technologies' potential to manage the employee lifecycle. This transformation encompasses recruitment, training, personnel development, and career management, all of which profoundly impact employee performance, engagement, and productivity.

The productivity of an employee is calculated by the efficiency of a worker within the organization's processes, measured by the produced output relative to the employee's labor hours, according to Trenerry et al. (2021). Employees are typically inclined to embrace new technologies, recognizing advantages like

improved productivity and work quality. Conversely, when technology was seen as a potential cause of job loss or downsizing, it often led to negative attitudes, including higher turnover rates, increased cynicism, feelings of depression, diminished organizational commitment, and lower career satisfaction (Trenerry et al., 2021). However, negative perceptions and outcomes were mitigated by perceived organizational support and a competitive psychological climate (Trenerry et al., 2021). Expectations regarding employee autonomy, competence, and engagement were also associated with heightened support for digital transformation (Trenerry et al., 2021). Additionally, employees reported that self-service technologies boosted their workplace productivity while also expanding their responsibilities (e.g., longer hours, increased sales or client numbers, and improved client satisfaction) and elevating the quality of their work (Trenerry et al., 2021).

The employee's performance is assessed on their ability to fulfill the responsibilities of their role, complete necessary tasks, and conduct themselves appropriately in the workplace. Transformational leadership is vital in advancing an organization's maturity and significantly impacts the performance of the employees. It is suggested that organizations should construct positive communication and relations with employees and motivate them to focus on objectives and potential transformations of the organization. As such, transformational leadership has a positive correlation with employees'

performance. Digital transformation strategic decision-making process is today's organizational challenge – from gut feeling to data-driven decision-making. Thus, emerging digital capabilities can support, enhance performance, and improve services, products, and customer bases (Top, Abdullah, & Faraj, 2020). The main objective is to provide the management with the perspective and ability to evaluate, measure, and improve performance through relevant and systemized information for decision-making. In this respect, the interaction of business growth and business models also needs to be measured from a responsibility perspective that should focus on prioritizing development efforts, establishing action plans, and performance evaluations to be used during business operational processes.

Engagement of an employee is a measure of how committed and enthusiastic employees are toward their work and organization. It is typically assessed using quantitative and qualitative methods such as Employee Net Promoter Score (e-NPS), Pulse Surveys, and Behavioral Metrics. A maturity assessment can highlight skill gaps within the workforce. Investing in training programs that address these gaps can equip employees with the needed digital skills to succeed in a technology-driven ecosystem. Research by Accenture shows that 84% of employees feel more confident in their ability to adapt to change when offered upskilling and reskilling opportunities. Employees who feel comfortable and confident using new technologies are more likely to embrace digital transformation initiatives. Addressing skill gaps fosters a culture of digital adoption

within the organization, leading to greater efficiency and innovation (Memorres, 2024).

Progressive Business Transformation: Embracing Change for Sustainability and Growth

In today's dynamic business topography, merely keeping pace is not enough. To thrive, organizations need to embrace Progressive Business Transformation (PBT). This section delves into the core principles of PBT, its key drivers, and the benefits it offers for achieving long-term sustainability and growth. PBT transcends traditional notions of business transformation. It is not just about implementing the latest technology or streamlining processes.

According to Mouzas (2022), to understand what drives business transformation, firms need to look into their capabilities to recalibrate resources and innovate. PBT is a holistic approach that focuses on continuous improvement and adaptation across all aspects of an organization. It encompasses strategic agility, digital enablement, cultural transformation, and sustainability integration. Strategic agility is the capability to continuously assess and modify strategies in response to evolving market conditions and customer demands. Digital enablement leverages technology to optimize operations, improve customer experiences, and unlock new possibilities. Cultural transformation fosters a mindset of innovation, collaboration, and continuous learning within the workforce. Sustainability integration aligns business practices with environmental and social responsibility goals to create long-

term value for all stakeholders.

Several factors are driving the need for PBT. Rapid technological advancements, such as disruptive technologies like blockchain, Internet of Things (IoT), and AI, rapidly reshape industries, demanding continuous adaptation (McKinsey Global Institute, 2020). Shifting customer expectations, where consumers demand personalized experiences and ethical business practices, necessitates focusing on customer satisfaction and social responsibility. Additionally, an evolving regulatory landscape with changes related to data privacy, environmental protection, and labor practices requires businesses to adapt to stay compliant. A well-executed PBT strategy can yield numerous benefits for organizations. Enhanced competitiveness results from embracing innovation and adapting to market changes, keeping businesses ahead of the curve. Increased customer satisfaction stems from a focus on digital enablement and customer experience, leading to higher loyalty. Improved operational efficiency is achieved through streamlined processes and optimized workflows, resulting in cost savings. Attracting and retaining talent becomes easier with a continuous learning and innovation culture, appealing to top talent in a competitive market. Finally, integrating sustainability into business practices leads to positive environmental and social impacts, enhancing the reputation of the company and building long-term value for all its stakeholders.

Implementing PBT requires a holistic approach. Key considerations include

developing a clear vision by defining the organization's long-term goals and how PBT will contribute to achieving them. Engaging stakeholders by building buy-in from all levels of the organization, including employees, stakeholders, and customers, is crucial. Investing in change management approaches to manage resistance and ensure a smooth transition is essential. Additionally, fostering continual learning and innovation by establishing a mindset that encourages continuous learning, experimentation, and adaptation is vital.

Synthesis

The review of relevant research and related insights motivated and contributed to the researcher's information and insights into pioneering a Progressive Business Transformation Model. These were the basis for analyzing findings and theoretical conclusions regarding the organization's maturity advancements.

The current study shares similarities with the research conducted by McGinty and Lylova (2020), as both focus on transforming Human Resource Management in modern organizations and the potential of digital technologies in managing the employee lifecycle. This includes recruitment, training, personnel development, and career management, which impact employee performance, engagement, and productivity. Additionally, this study aligns with Top, Abdullah, and Faraj (2020) work concerning employee performance. Both studies explore

transformational leadership's effects on employees' performance, aiming to equip management with the perspective and tools needed to evaluate, measure, and improve performance through relevant and systemized information for decision-making. Furthermore, this study echoes the research of Heslina and Syahrani (2021) on employee engagement. According to their multiple linear regression analysis, technology, HR competence, and work engagement positively and significantly affect employee performance (Dasmadi & Handayani, 2023). Lastly, the current study parallels the research by Trenergy et al. (2021) on organizational productivity. Both studies explore how employees' expectations of autonomy, competence, engagement, and work quality influence an organization's productivity.

Similarly, the current study resembles the research by Guo and Xu (2021), which examines the effects of digital transformation on firm performance, particularly in financial, operational, and marketing performance. Their study investigates the relationship between digital transformation, business operations, and financial outcomes. Guo and Xu found that the impact of digital transformation on operational performance tends to be more enduring than its impact on financial performance. They concluded that it is generally easier for firms to enhance their operational processes than to increase profits through digital transformation. Future research is suggested to study digital transformation from different dimensions: designing questionnaires that include a series of questions to obtain sufficient

primary data and exploring the joint effects of different dimensions of digital transformation on organizational performance from a configurational perspective (e.g., qualitative comparative analysis). Thus, this study will employ a mixed-method approach, using qualitative methods to guide the direction of the research and provide a comprehensive understanding of the impacts of digital transformation.

The synthesis of related literature and studies provides a robust foundation for developing a Progressive Business Transformation Model. By examining parallels with existing research on human resource management, transformational leadership, employee performance, engagement, productivity, and organizational efficiency, this study aims to offer new insights into the role of business digital technologies in enhancing organizational maturity. The comparisons with studies by McGinty and Lylova (2020), Top, Abdullah, and Faraj (2020), Heslina and Syahrani (2021), Trenerry et al. (2021), and Guo and Xu (2021) underscore the multifaceted impact of business transformation on employee performance, engagement, and productivity toward overall firm success. The research directions, including mixed-method approaches, will further deepen understanding and support the development of strategies for leveraging digital transformation to achieve sustainable growth and efficiency.

Theoretical Framework

The study's theoretical foundation is rooted in the problem-solving paradigm, which seeks to design an artifact supporting the organization's analysis, management, and use of technology. The goal is to identify and eliminate lacking capabilities and map the way for continuous improvement. The theoretical frameworks used in this research are the Human Capital Theory and the Diffusion of Innovation Theory.

First Theory

The first supporting theory considered in this study is the **Human Capital Theory** (Becker, 1976). It explains any employment-related inquiries, concerns, and progression. It underscores that organizations must invest in their workforce by offering training and education to achieve economic benefits and outcomes from their developed human capital.

Employee's Learning Ability. Becker's theory on employee performance suggests that increased human capital, acquired through education, training, or experience, leads to improved performance. Employees with higher human capital perform tasks more efficiently and effectively. Organizations can enhance their workforce's productivity by investing in training programs, tuition reimbursement, and skill development opportunities.

Employee's Time Management (Efficiency). According to Becker's

Human Capital Theory, employees who receive adequate training and education are better equipped to manage their time efficiently. Effective time management is a vital viewpoint of employee performance, as it leads to better prioritization of tasks, reduced downtime, and overall increased efficiency in the workplace. Investing in time management training can help employees optimize their work processes and contribute more efficiently to organizational goals.

Employee's Engagement. According to Becker, when companies invest in their employees' development, it can lead to a feeling of being valued and appreciated. This, in turn, can increase employee engagement. Engaged employees tend to be more dedicated, enthusiastic, and motivated. Employees with higher human capital may also seek more autonomy and control over their work. This can lead to increased engagement when employers provide opportunities for them to utilize their skills and contribute their ideas.

Employee's Productivity. According to Becker, more knowledgeable employees are better equipped to handle complex tasks and solve problems. This translates to higher output and overall productivity for the organization. Employees who possess the right human capital, skills, and knowledge for their specific job duties are more likely to be productive. Companies that align employee skills with task requirements can see significant productivity gains.

Human Capital Theory offers a valuable framework for recognizing the connection between employee development and key aspects of work performance.

Organizations can provide a more productive and engaged workforce by investing in employees' skills and knowledge.

Second Theory

The orchestration of **marketing, finance, and operations** is a vital determinant of organizational success; these three pillars can propel a business toward its strategic objectives, ensuring sustainable growth and profitability (Hamilton, 2023).

The second theoretical foundation used in this study is the **Diffusion of Innovations Theory** (Rogers, 1962). This theory explains how a social system accepts and distributes new ideas, practices, or products. The theory highlights the role of innovation, channels of communication, time, and the social system in the implementation process that can be applied to understand how organizations achieve efficiency across different areas:

Financial Efficiency. According to the Diffusion of Innovations Theory, financial efficiency within an organization can be seen through the lens of how quickly and effectively it adopts and implements new financial strategies or technologies. In Rogers' theory, financial efficiency relates to the rate at which an organization adopts innovative financial practices, such as new accounting software or investment strategies. Organizations that quickly adopt and integrate these innovations are likely to achieve higher financial efficiency, as they can streamline

processes, reduce costs, and maximize profits faster than their competitors.

Operations Efficiency. The Diffusion of Innovations Theory concerns adopting and utilizing new operational methodologies, technologies, or processes within an organization. This includes supply chain management, production processes, and resource allocation. According to Rogers' theory, organizations that efficiently adopt and implement innovative operational practices tend to optimize their workflows, reduce waste, and enhance productivity. For instance, implementing lean manufacturing principles or utilizing advanced automation technologies can significantly improve operational efficiency by minimizing downtime and improving throughput.

Marketing Efficiency. According to the Diffusion of Innovations Theory, it refers to how effectively an organization adopts and utilizes innovative marketing strategies or techniques to reach its target audience. This could involve adopting new advertising platforms, social media marketing tactics, or customer relationship management systems. According to Rogers' theory, organizations that embrace innovative marketing approaches can more efficiently promote their products or services, raise customer engagement, and win a competitive edge. Through leveraging cutting-edge marketing innovations, such as personalized digital marketing campaigns or influencer collaborations, organizations can enhance their marketing efficiency and achieve better brand awareness, customer acquisition, and retention results.

In this study, the Diffusion of Innovations Theory is used to understand how new technological solutions and management practices are adopted within organizations. It offers valuable insights into the factors that either enable or obstruct the adoption of emerging technologies, which is vital for improving organizational processes and performance. All these theories are believed to be applicable in discovering the impact of maturity on the performance of employees and achieving improved organizational efficiency in maturity progression through the development and execution of progressive business transformation.

Conceptual Framework

Based on the provided theoretical context, a conceptual framework has been developed, wherein components in each variable are explained into more detailed specific variables. Figure 1 below is a diagram that illustrates a representation of the analysis of the preceding study, in which entities interconnect the variables and elements that will derive answers to the questions as indicated in the problem statements in this research.

Figure 1. *The Research Paradigm*

In the figure, the contextual moderators play a pivotal role in establishing connections between maturity, organizational efficiency, and employee performance, all visually represented in the box above. This framework segment effectively tackles statements of problems 1 and 2 by shedding light on the intricate interaction among these variables.

The initial arrow positioned at the middle-left corner depicts a "Company," showcasing the organization's current maturity across six dimensions: People, Culture, Capacity, Capability, Technology, and Leadership. It seeks to attain a

comprehensive analysis of the organization's status quo, find areas for improvement, and guide decisions on the initiation, scope, and methodology of transformation to align business unit operations. This framework directly addresses problem statement 3. Following the identification of maturity levels, the segment directed toward the box on the right establishes metrics for evaluating employees' performance, thereby contextualizing problem statement 4. Similarly, the segment pointing to the box at the bottom establishes metrics for assessing organizational efficiency in financial, operational, and marketing domains, providing context for addressing problem statement 5.

Furthermore, the box on the right examines employee performance across key metrics such as learning ability, time management, engagement, and productivity, highlighting notable variations in efficiency when analyzed demographically. Similarly, the box addressing organizational efficiency evaluates financial, operational, and marketing performance, identifying significant differences based on demographic groupings. These analyses form the foundation for the first hypothesis aimed at addressing problem statement 6. Likewise, the box representing maturity levels examines potential significant differences in the impact of maturity on employees' and organizations' efficiency when grouped demographically, shaping the formulation of the second hypothesis to address problem statement 7. Collectively, the connection depicted by the arrow line on the right side linking to the Maturity level scrutinizes the relationship between the

maturity of the organization and the efficiency of employees, laying the groundwork for formulating the third hypothesis to address problem statement 8.

Ultimately, the findings of this research endeavor will pave the way for developing a Progressive Business Transformation Model, representing the final output of the study. These theoretical frameworks encapsulate the culmination of empirical insights and scholarly analysis, offering a comprehensive roadmap for businesses seeking to traverse the complexities of contemporary business environments. Through the lens of this progressive theory, organizations can unlock new pathways to competitive advantage, sustain growth, and achieve long-term success.

Statement of the Problem

This study aims to analyze digital maturity and its impact on several facets of organizational efficiency, including financial, operational, and marketing performance, as well as employee performance, such as learning ability, time management, engagement, and productivity. The primary objective is to understand how different levels of digital maturity affect organizational efficiency and employee performance. By exploring these key areas, the study seeks to uncover valuable insights that will contribute to developing a Progressive Business Transformation Model, offering practical knowledge to guide organizational growth and adaptation in ever-changing business environments.

Explicitly, this study pursued to answer these research questions:

1. What is the demographic profile of the respondents in terms of:
 - 1.1. Age
 - 1.2. Sex
 - 1.3. Highest Educational Attainment
 - 1.4. Business Unit/ Department
 - 1.5. Job Level
 - 1.6. Years of tenure?
2. What is the demographic profile of the organization in terms of:
 - 2.1. Type of Service
 - 2.2. Years in Operation
 - 2.3. Number of Employees
 - 2.4. Business size in capital?
3. What is the level of maturity of the respondents in terms of:
 - 3.1. People
 - 3.2. Culture
 - 3.3. Capacity

- 3.4. Capability
 - 3.5. Technology
 - 3.6. Leadership?
4. What is the level of employees' performance in terms of:
 - 4.1. Learning Ability
 - 4.2. Time Management
 - 4.3. Engagement
 - 4.4. Productivity?
5. What is the level of the organization's efficiency in terms of:
 - 5.1. Financial
 - 5.2. Operations
 - 5.3. Marketing?
6. Is there a significant difference in the levels of digital maturity, organizations' efficiency, and employees' performance when grouped according to Business Unit/ Department, Job Level, and Years of tenure?
 7. Is there a significant difference in the impact of digital maturity on organizations' efficiency and employees' performance when grouped according to Business Unit/ Department, Job Level, and Years of tenure?

8. Is there a significant relationship between the level of digital maturity and its impact on an organization's efficiency and employees' performance?
9. Through this research, what model of Progressive Business Transformation can be proposed?

Hypotheses

Following standard statistical practices, the null hypotheses will be subjected to rigorous testing at a significance level of 5%. This meticulous approach ensures that the statistical analyses undertaken in this study adhere to established principles of accuracy and reliability.

1. There is no significant difference in the levels of digital maturity, organizations' efficiency, and employees' performance when they are grouped demographically.
2. There is no significant difference in the impact of digital maturity on organizations' efficiency and employees' performance when grouped according to Business Unit/ Department, Job Level, and Years of tenure.
3. There is no significant relationship between the level of digital maturity and its impact on an organization's efficiency and employees' performance.

Scope and Limitations

This research was conducted to analyze and uncover the interconnections between maturity and organizational efficiency in terms of financial, operations, and marketing, along with employees' performance in terms of learning ability, time management, engagement, and productivity within the business context of digital transformation, to lay the groundwork pioneering a progressive business transformation model.

Regarding the study's limitation of respondents, it focused on three selected IT-BPO companies located in Makati City under the Philippine Economic Zone Authority (PEZA). The respondents included a mix of IT-BPO workers from Company A, Company B, and Company C, meeting specific criteria: an employee headcount exceeding 200, a business operation duration of over 2 years, industry involvement in business technology and PEZA registration, and a focus on business outsourcing for both development and operations.

The researcher interviewed representatives from the business technology industry, including HR practitioners, to gather data and engage in meaningful conversations on the organization's initiatives to address issues and support all business activities. To initiate this process, the researcher leveraged personal connections within these companies and requested them to distribute the survey to their colleagues and friends across the organization. Hard copies and electronic versions of the survey were made available, with respondents directed to an online

survey form via a provided link. The study aimed to gather input from respondents who could effectively represent their respective areas or departments. Participants were randomly selected to ensure the sample best represented the target population. To attain the research's primary purpose, comparative analysis was performed on the assessments of two groups of respondents in line with their awareness level and perceptions of their organization's maturity. This involved using the independent t-test as the primary statistical method or inferential tool for treating the gathered data.

Ultimately, correlation analyses were conducted to examine employees' performance regarding learning ability, time management, engagement, and productivity in business digital transformation. This included seeking an understanding of the organization's maturity level and its implications for efficiency. Moreover, the study initiated a discourse on bridging existing gaps through the lens of the Progressive Business Transformation Model.

Significance of the Study

This research is conjectured to gather information through scientific investigation. The findings might, to a large extent, help the different entities in business technology companies in Makati City.

The result of this research caters the importance of the following:

Top Management. The organization's Top Management may greatly benefit from the results of this study. Given the inevitable swift progression of new technologies in the workplace, this study may offer essential insights to aid in their vision for transformation. This, in turn, can help them tackle current business challenges, foster growth, and compete more effectively.

IT-BPO Companies in Makati. The IT-BPO Companies in Makati may greatly benefit from the results of this research. It may extend additional insights into continuously aligning and realigning Human Resources with swiftly evolving organizational demands. This includes understanding employees as key participants in the transformation, considering their experiences and feelings towards technological changes, and employing other approaches to boost their digital skills.

Philippine IT-BPO Industry. The Philippine IT-BPO Industry may greatly benefit from the results of this research. It offers an overview of the various far-reaching impacts driven by the rapid advancements in digitalization. It can contribute to higher knowledge in the context of IT-BPO Industry improvements as an area of study for developing strategies toward maturity advancements.

Definition of Terms

Subsequent defined terms are provided to describe their use in the context of this research and to establish a shared understanding.

Digital Awareness. It refers to understanding digital technologies and how to use them, including recognizing technology's impact on the workplace. It helps individuals and organizations adapt to a digital world and make informed business and technology decisions.

Digital Technology. It refers to encompassing all electronic tools, automated systems, technological devices, and resources that create and handle information within an organization.

Digital Transformation. It refers to incorporating digital technology into every aspect of the business, profoundly shifting the organization's operations and value delivery process.

Digitalization. This term is used to manage business model changes through digital technology.

Engagement. It refers to the enthusiasm, commitment, and emotional connection an individual feels toward their role in the organization.

Information Technology Business Process Outsourcing, or IT-BPO, denotes the sector that offers business process outsourcing in the information technology field by engaging a third-party agency or professional to execute particular tasks and operations typically handled within the organization.

Maturity. In business technology, the term refers to assessing an organization's digital maturity by evaluating its current capabilities across various dimensions, including People, Culture, Capacity, Capability, Technology, and Leadership. This assessment helps determine the organization's ability to respond to or leverage opportunities influenced by its existing technology infrastructure, staffing resources, and digital tools.

Organizational Efficiency. It pertains to the ability of the organization to reach its goals with the least resources and time. It involves process optimization, improving workflow, reducing waste, and enhancing productivity in Financial, Operations, and Marketing.

Performance. It pertains to employee's competence to successfully carry out their role and responsibilities and their alignment with the organization's objectives.

Pillars. It refers to the categories that measure organizational maturity in people, culture, capacity, capability, technology, and leadership.

Productivity. It refers to the quality and output of labor by measuring how productive and efficient an individual is in the organization.

Progressive Business Transformation. It pertains to the continuous evolution of an organization's strategies and business operations to achieve competitive advantage, sustain growth, and ensure success in a dynamic business environment with shifting market conditions.

Respondents. It refers to the IT-BPO employees who are participants in the research by completing the survey and interviews, which provided data to be analyzed for the study.

Triangulating. It refers to using methods, data sources, theories, or investigators in research to improve accuracy and credibility. By cross-verifying results, triangulating reduces biases and enhances reliability. The main types include employing different research methods, diverse data sources, various theoretical perspectives, and multiple researchers. This approach ensures more comprehensive and trustworthy findings.

Type of Service. This category of business offerings includes selling software products, providing IT services for system management and support, and offering consulting services to help organizations improve their performance and strategies.

Chapter 2

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This chapter outlines the process for evaluating the reliability and validity of the research. It covers aspects such as research design, sampling technique, actual respondents, the type of instruments used, data collection procedures, tool validation, and statistical data analysis.

Each element undergoes thorough examination and discussion, offering the researcher practical insights and methodological considerations to boost the rigor and strength of this study. This section will discuss each element to expound its content.

Research Design

To capture data, produce information, and achieve its purposes, the researcher utilized a mixed method that involved qualitative and quantitative research methods. By integrating these methods, the researcher leverages the strengths of each, allowing for an extensive and nuanced analysis.

According to Creswell and Creswell (2020), this approach involves collecting and analyzing both data types to answer research questions and integrate the findings. This can include designs such as convergent, where data is collected simultaneously but analyzed separately before being combined, or explanatory

sequential, where qualitative information is gathered first, followed by quantitative data to expand on the initial results (Alele & Malau-Aduli, 2023). Mixed methods are valuable for addressing complex questions that single-method studies cannot fully explore.

Qualitative Instrument

A qualitative instrument is a research tool used to gather non-numerical data, focusing on understanding participants' experiences, perceptions, and motivations. These instruments include interviews, focus groups, observations, and open-ended questionnaires designed to capture rich, detailed insights into the subject matter. Ravitch and Carl (2020) state that a qualitative instrument is flexible and adaptive, allowing researchers to explore complex phenomena in depth. It facilitates the collection of rich context and depth data, particularly useful for studying human behavior, social processes, and cultural phenomena.

This research employs an Exploratory Sequential Mixed Method, beginning with qualitative data collection and inquiry to explore key themes and insights. These findings inform the development of quantitative instruments, which are then used in a subsequent phase to gather and analyze numerical data. This design ensures a comprehensive understanding by leveraging the strengths of both qualitative and quantitative approaches, with the qualitative phase providing the groundwork for a robust quantitative investigation.

Figure 2. *Exploratory Sequential Mixed Methods Research Design*

The illustration depicted a two-phased research process. The first phase involved qualitative research, with procedures including participant selection for interviews, conducting interviews, and analyzing transcripts to develop codes and

themes. Three themes emerged from this phase, informing the formulation or revision of survey questions.

The second phase transitioned to quantitative research, employing total sampling to include all eligible participants and collecting data through surveys to provide nominal and numerical interval data. Data analysis involved frequency distribution to assess variable occurrence and calculate mean, median, and mode measures.

The research process began with qualitative methods, including interviews and thematic analysis, to gain insights before transitioning to quantitative methods to gather broader data. Finally, qualitative and quantitative findings were examined to provide comprehensive conclusions about the research topic and its direction.

Quantitative Instrument

The quantitative instrument employed a correlational research design that investigated relationships between variables (Bhandari, 2023). In the correlational approach, the researcher observed and measured the natural association between two variables without exposing them to external conditioning (Bhandari, 2023). The purpose of ex post facto correlational research was to describe the relationship between employees' performance and maturity. This method was appropriate as it identified the connection between maturity (independent variable) and employees' performance (dependent variables).

A correlational study has three possible results: (1) A positive correlation is a relationship between two variables in which both variables move in the same direction. Therefore, when one variable increases as the other variable increases or one variable decreases while the other decreases; (2) A negative correlation is a relationship between two variables in which an increase in one variable is associated with a decrease in the other; (3) A zero correlation exists when there is no relationship between two variables (McLeod, 2023).

Another reason the researcher used a correlational study rather than an experiment was that the statistical relationship of interest was thought to be causal, but the researcher could not manipulate the independent variable due to reasons such as impossibility, impracticality, or ethical concerns (Alele & Malau-Aduli, 2023). Correlation was also used to establish the reliability and validity of measurements, with the strength often being higher in external validity than in experimental research (Bhandari, 2023). This approach provided a comprehensive understanding of the relationship between maturity, organizational efficiency, and employee performance while respecting practical and ethical constraints.

Population and Sampling

Sampling Techniques were methods used to select a portion of a larger group or population for this research, which included:

Purposive Sampling, famous as judgmental or selective sampling, was a non-probability sampling technique. (Stewart, 2024). The study used it to select companies according to the constructed specific criteria relevant to the research questions.

Slovin's formula was used to compute an applicable sample size from the derived population, particularly in cases where there was no prior knowledge about the population's behavior (Glenn, 2022).

The formula:
$$n = \frac{N}{1 + Ne^2}$$

Where: n = Samples; N = Population, and e = Error tolerance.

A ***Stratified Sampling technique*** was carried out, involving dividing the population into subpopulations, in this study by business unit or department, that differed in meaningful ways. This approach ensured that every subgroup was adequately represented in the sample and helped obtain more precise conclusions (McCombes, 2023).

Simple Random Sampling was a method in which every member of the population had an equal probability of being chosen (Thomas, 2020). It was executed by randomly selecting respondents from each business unit or department using a computer program.

Respondents of the Study

Three IT-BPO companies were selected based on specific criteria to gain meaningful insights and ensure the survey's validity. This selection procedure was designed to make sure that the chosen companies were relevant to the study and representative of the broader industry.

Stratifying respondents involved applying specific criteria to categorize participants effectively. These criteria included: (1) having over two years of business operations in Makati City, (2) being part of the business technology industry and registered with PEZA or operating in IT Parks and Centers (often referred to as "PEZA houses"), (3) focusing on business outsourcing for both development and operations, (4) engaging in activities such as providing IT Services, Consulting Services, or Selling Software products, (5) having an employee headcount of more than 200, (6) representing a diverse age range across different generations, and (7) including various designations such as Rank and File, Officer, Manager, and Leadership. This stratification ensured a comprehensive and representative sample of respondents within the target demographic.

There were 18 participants for the interview and 328 respondents for the survey. The interview participants were carefully chosen to provide in-depth insights and qualitative data. Furthermore, the survey respondents were selected to ensure a broad and statistically significant representation across all departments and companies involved in the study.

Table 1. *The Selected Companies*

Company	Established	Years in Business	Type of Service
A	1983	41	Selling Software
B	2003	21	IT services
C	2020	4	Consulting services

Table 1 details the years in business for the three selected IT-BPO companies, highlighting their respective service types and operational durations. **Company A**, established in 1983, was the oldest of the three, having been in business for 41 years by 2024 and specializing in selling software. Its extensive history provided valuable insights into long-term industry trends and stability. **Company B**, founded in 2003, accumulated 21 years of operational experience by 2024, focusing on IT services. This company offered a perspective on industry developments since the early 2000s. **Company C**, the youngest, was established in 2020 and will be operational for only 4 years by 2024. It specializes in consulting services, reflecting current trends and challenges that newer entrants in the industry face. The range of experience among these companies provided a comprehensive view of the IT-BPO industry's evolution, capturing both historical trends and contemporary practices. The diversity in operational durations among these companies provided a layered understanding of the industry. It offered a longitudinal view through Company A, a transitional perspective through Company B, and an emerging trends analysis through Company C. These insights enriched the study by bridging historical contexts with contemporary realities.

Table 2. *The Selected Interview Participants*

Company	Business Unit/ Department	Participants
A	Admin & Finance	2
	Service & Delivery Operations	2
	Sales & Marketing	2
B	Admin & Finance	2
	Service & Delivery Operations	2
	Sales & Marketing	2
C	Admin & Finance	2
	Service & Delivery Operations	2
	Sales & Marketing	2
Total		18

Table 2 presents a detailed list of participants selected for interviews from various business units or departments. These participants were expected to hold supervisory to managerial roles, ensuring they had substantial experience and insight into their respective areas. The participants were drawn from three critical business units: Admin & Finance, Service & Delivery Operations, and Sales & Marketing. Each business unit contributed three participants from each of the three companies involved in the study, resulting in 18 participants.

This approach comprehensively represented each company's functional areas, capturing a broad spectrum of insights and perspectives. By including participants from multiple departments and roles, the research aimed to gather well-rounded insights into the various company dynamics. This ensured that the data reflected diverse viewpoints, mounting the depth and reliability.

Table 3. *Distribution of Survey Respondents*

Particular	Population	%	Participants
Company A	1,042	57	188
Company B	517	28	93
Company C	260	14	47
Total	1,819	100	328

To get the total target respondents, the proponent used Slovin's formula.

The formula:
$$n = \frac{N}{1 + Ne^2}$$

Where: **N** is the (1,819) sizes of the population of Company A, Company B, and Company C combined. At the same time, **e** is the (5%) desired margin error.

The study's respondents were 328 employees representing different departments from Company A, Company B, and Company C. Table 3 outlines the allocation of the respondents corresponding to the total population. Based on the calculated percent of the distribution, Company A had 188 respondents, Company B had 93 respondents, and Company C had 42 respondents.

Tables 4-6 show the allocation of respondents corresponding to the department or business unit in which they were randomly chosen, as detailed in the sample column below. This breakdown highlights the proportional representation of each department, ensuring that all functional areas within the companies were adequately covered in the analysis.

Tables 4 – 6. Breakdown of Respondent Distribution

Company A			
Business Unit	Population	%	Participants
Admin & Finance	20	2	4
Human Resource	35	5	6
Sales & Marketing	15	1	3
Service & Delivery	972	92	175
Total	1,042	100	188

Company B			
Business Unit	Population	%	Participants
Admin & Finance	18	3	3
Human Resource	23	4	4
Sales & Marketing	15	3	3
Service & Delivery	461	89	83
Total	517	100	93

Company C			
Business Unit	Population	%	Participants
Admin & Finance	10	4	2
Human Resource	10	4	2
Sales & Marketing	5	2	1
Service & Delivery	235	90	42
Total	220	100	47

A comprehensive survey was conducted across three companies, targeting employees in four departments: Admin & Finance, Human Resources, Sales & Marketing, and Service & Delivery. The researcher meticulously planned the participant distribution using a mathematical approach based on ratios and proportions to ensure a balanced company representation. Company A had the highest number of participants, with 188, followed by Company B with 93, and

Company C with 47. Projections indicated that the Service and delivery department would have the highest participation across all three companies. In Company A, 175 participants (92%) were expected to be from this department. Similarly, Company B anticipated 83 participants (89%) from this department, and Company C expected 42 participants (90%) from Service & Delivery. This strong representation suggested that the survey has been dominated by many service and delivery employees, potentially leading to results heavily influenced by their participation.

Research Instrument

Data collection involved using a researcher-designed questionnaire and interview protocol to gather insights into assessing maturity levels and employees' performance. The questionnaire consisted of carefully crafted questions aimed at quantitatively assessing organizational maturity and employee factors. Additionally, the interview questions were tailored to elicit in-depth qualitative responses from participants, providing rich contextual information and nuanced perspectives. This mixed-method approach ensured a comprehensive understanding of the subject matter, combining qualitative insights to explore underlying factors and dynamics more deeply with quantitative data for statistical analysis. Through this method, the research aimed to capture a holistic view of

organizational maturity and its impact on employee outcomes, contributing to a nuanced and multifaceted understanding of the research topic.

Phase One: Qualitative

It is a research type aimed at exploring and providing deeper insights into real-world problems by gathering participants' experiences, perceptions, and behaviors. It focused on answering hows and whys to explain processes and patterns of respondents' behavior that can be difficult to quantify (Tenny, Brannan, & Brannan, 2022).

Coding. It was the process of naming or labeling the data, categories, and properties, including words, phrases, and meaning units that were repeated in the data (Corbin & Strauss, 2008). Codes were developed before the coding process began.

Theme Construction. It was the process of identifying recurring patterns in data, grouping them into broader themes, refining and validating these themes, and giving them clear names and definitions (Corbin & Strauss, 2008). It's a way to organize and understand the main points.

Defining Elements. It was the essential component that aided in understanding and interpreting the data, crucial for identifying patterns, themes, and insights within qualitative data analysis (Corbin & Strauss, 2008).

Interview Questions. This study used interviews to gather information. Interviews involve asking questions and receiving spoken answers from one or more people. The researcher created a set of 10 interview questions based on relevant sources such as professional journals and past research. These questions addressed the study's problem statement and explored the company's overall strategy for improving efficiency. The researcher carefully considered the proper design of the questions while developing this interview instrument.

Phase Two: Quantitative

The survey questionnaire, as the research instrument used by the researcher, consists of six (6) sections.

Part 1 is researcher-developed to capture the demographic of the respondents.

Part 2 is researcher-developed to assess maturity levels, covering People, Culture, Capacity, Capability, Technology, and Leadership.

Part 3 is a researcher-developed tool for evaluating employee performance regarding Learning Ability, Time Management (Efficiency), Engagement, and Productivity.

Part 4 is researcher-developed to investigate the impact of maturity on the performance of employees.

Part 5 is researcher-developed to measure Organizational Efficiency regarding Financial, Operations, and Marketing.

Part 6 is research developed to assess the impact of maturity on organizational efficiency, specifically in financial, operations, and marketing areas.

To further substantiate the study, the research instrument was validated to improve the crafting of sound questions and warrant its appropriateness for the respondents. After examination and adjustments, the final survey form was available in electronic and hard copies. The electronic version was accessible via Google Forms, with a link provided to respondents. Three distinct electronic forms were created for each company to differentiate the responses. Company-specific information, such as Type of Service, Years of Operation, Number of Employees, and Size of Business in terms of capital, were not included in the form, as these details were already available and were used prior to data analysis.

Validation of the Instrument

Validation is an essential stage in refining research instruments. It ensures the accuracy and relevance of the questions and methods used. This step involves seeking feedback from experts in the relevant fields to confirm that the instruments effectively measure what they are intended to.

In this study, the researcher-developed questionnaire underwent a comprehensive multi-stage validation process involving business and technology

experts. Stage 1 focused on gathering input from a research questionnaire developer and business faculty practitioners from Olivarez College and other universities. In Stage 2, the questionnaire was evaluated by two expert validators from the business technology industry. Stage 3 included feedback from a validator with a Doctorate Degree from Olivarez College and the University of the Philippines, possessing academic and industry expertise in business or technology.

These experts meticulously assessed the study's variables to ensure the indicators and content aligned with the research objectives. Each item was thoroughly reviewed for clarity, relevance, and effectiveness in capturing the necessary data for content validation. The validation results yielded an overall mean of 4.7 for all indicators, interpreted as "Very Much Valid."

Test of Validity Results

A pilot test evaluated the validity of a survey instrument designed to measure key factors, including clarity, length, wording, content, and relevance. Each factor was rated on a scale from "Very Much Valid" (VMW) to "Not Valid at All" (NV). Positive ratings were anticipated for eight specific factors, such as ease of understanding and clarity of wording. Minor revisions were made based on feedback to better address specific areas, confirming the instrument's validity for effective survey design and potential refinement for future studies. The finalized research instrument was reviewed and approved by the research adviser and made

available in both hard copy and digital formats via Google Forms. The pilot test involved thirty participants, separate from the study sample, and achieved an overall rating of 1.0, equivalent to "Excellent." According to Memon et al. (2020), a minimum of 30 respondents is recommended for each subgroup (e.g., male/female, rural/urban, local/international) to allow for comparative analysis. Cronbach's alpha was used to calculate the 'internal consistency' and 'reliability' of survey items Schrepp (2020) and assess the research instrument's consistency across participants.

Data Gathering Procedure

Three significant data-gathering procedures were performed: (1) conducting a review of collected works, (2) planning an approach and methods, and (3) analyzing the results collected from respondents of three companies.

First, the researcher reviewed policies, practices, and procedures applicable to employees to explore ideas that could help craft the structure of questionnaires. Different materials from journals, articles, books, and electronic sources were used. Next, the researcher developed a comprehensive plan outlining the approach for conducting the survey. This plan detailed how data would be gathered and utilized, the data collection duration, and other pertinent questions. As part of the process, the research proposal was submitted to the research adviser and Dean of the

Graduate School. Inputs and feedback from the research adviser were considered and integrated to improve the research.

A request, approved by the research adviser, was submitted to secure permission from the three companies to conduct interviews with prospective respondents. Specifically, the researcher aimed to interview 18 participants for in-depth discussions, all holding senior, supervisory, managerial, or lead roles, and drawn from three key areas: *Admin & Finance*, *Service & Delivery*, and *Sales & Marketing*. Each business unit contributed two participants from the three companies involved, resulting in 18 participants. This selection comprehensively represented each company's diverse functional areas and aimed to gather a broad spectrum of insights and perspectives relevant to the research objectives. Subsequently, the researcher aimed to achieve a 100% response rate from 328 respondents for the survey.

A comprehensive survey was conducted across three companies, targeting employees in four departments: *Admin & Finance*, *Human Resources*, *Sales & Marketing*, and *Service & Delivery*. The participant distribution was meticulously planned using a mathematical approach based on ratios and proportions to ensure a balanced company representation. Company A was expected to have the highest number of participants at 188, followed by Company B with 93 and Company C with 47. Consequently, the captured data was recorded, tabulated, and analyzed.

The questionnaire results were evaluated, interpreted, and processed into meaningful results to address the questions posed in the problem statement.

Ultimately, the researcher provided the findings, recommendations, conclusions, and direction toward pioneering a Progressive Business Transformation Model. These were presented during the final defense to the graduate school evaluators so that they could evaluate fully and provide input for the betterment of the research.

Data Analysis

Quantitative Descriptive Statistics pertains to the analysis and organization of collected data, from responses or observations, to quantitatively describe in a more meaningful way, enabling simpler interpretation without making conclusions beyond the analyzed data or reaching hypotheses (Lund Research, n.d.). Under this, the following measures were included, addressing all statements of the problems.

Percentage. This statistical measure was computed by dividing the occurrence of the classification by the overall participants and then multiplying by one hundred percent (Cooksey, 2020). This study described the simple frequency of the respondents' profiles, such as Age, Sex, Highest Educational Attainment, Job Level, and Years of Tenure, in response to problem 1. It also examined the demographic profile of the organization, including the type of

service, years in operation, number of employees, and business size in the capital, in response to problem 2.

Additionally, it assessed the respondents' maturity across dimensions such as People, Culture, Capacity, Capability, Technology, and Leadership, addressing the statement of problem 3. Furthermore, it evaluated the level of employees' performance in terms of Learning Ability, Time Management, Engagement, and Productivity, addressing problem 4. Moreover, it assessed the level of the organization's efficiency in terms of Financial, Operations, and Marketing, addressing the statement of problem 5.

Weighted Mean. It is a type of mean computed by multiplying the weight linked with its corresponding quantitative outcome and then summing it all together (Taylor, 2024). Accordingly, selections in the questionnaires had equivalent assigned points to calculate the degree of respondents' responses in terms of maturity level, learning ability, time management, engagement, productivity, and organizational efficiency in financial, operations, sales, and marketing, addressing problem statements 3 to 8.

One-way Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) on ranks, also known as 'Kruskal-Wallis,' is a rank-based nonparametric test used to determine if there are statistically significant differences between two or more groups of an independent variable on a continuous or ordinal dependent variable (Lund Research, n.d.). This approach was systematically employed to evaluate whether

significant differences existed in the level of maturity among respondents when grouped demographically. By analyzing variations across different demographic categories, this research aimed to provide a deeper insight into maturity levels within the workforce, effectively addressing the objectives outlined in problem statement 6. Also, it investigated the significant difference in the impact of maturity on organizations' efficiency and employees' performance when grouped according to Department and Job Level, addressing problem statement 9.

Dunn's Post Hoc Test. is a posthoc analysis used when the results of a Kruskal-Wallis test are statistically significant, allowing researchers to perform pairwise comparisons between independent groups to identify which are significantly different at a specified level of significance (α) (Bobbitt, 2020).

Spearman's rho Correlation. It is the correlation used to assess the relationship between two ordinal variables. Spearman's rho is a popular method for correlating Likert-type survey responses. Spearman's rho is prevalent in the social sciences as most survey instruments use Likert-type or ordinal scales to allow participants to rate themselves along a continuum. Run skewness and kurtosis statistics on each variable's distribution. If the normality assumption can be met, then more powerful biserial or Pearson correlations can be used instead of Spearman's rho. However, in this study, data is not normally distributed. Hence, Spearman's rho Correlation was then used to determine the significant relationship between digital maturity, employee performance, and organizational

efficiency. Primarily, Spearman's rho Correlation was used to get two pieces of information: (1) the quantifiable relationship and (2) the direction of the relationship, which can determine the values using arbitrary values.

Table 7. *Spearman's Rho Correlation Matrix*

Strength of Association	Direction	
	Positive	Negative
Perfect	1	-1
Strong	0.9	-0.9
	0.8	-0.8
	0.7	-0.7
Moderate	0.6	-0.6
	0.5	-0.5
	0.4	-0.4
Weak	0.3	-0.3
	0.2	-0.2
	0.1	-0.1
Zero	0	0

r² (%). It was the coefficient of variation in percentage, also identified as the proportion overlap of the number of variations in y because of x . If the value exceeded 20 percent, it was identified as a strong positive or negative predictor. Subsequently, since the Pearson r correlation coefficient was only descriptive, it was tested for significance using a null hypothesis in the form:

Interpretative Description. The weighted mean was used to interpret the data; options on the questionnaire items were taken by the calculated mean with the succeeding intervals: respondents' assessment of maturity level toward People, Culture, Capacity, Capability, Technology, and Leadership.

The table below presents four levels of maturity within organizations, providing a framework for analysis. This classification helps organizations evaluate their maturity, identify areas for improvement, and guide their development toward greater efficiency and effectiveness.

Table 8. *Digital Maturity Level*

Level	Maturity	Description
1	Minimal	Digital transformation is not understood or barely defined.
2	Transitional	The importance of digital transformation is starting to be acknowledged by the organization.
3	Customer-driven	Digital transformation is integrated into some parts of business operations.
4	Transformed	Digital transformation is embedded across organizations.

The table below shows the four-point arbitrary scale used to measure maturity regarding people, culture, capacity, capability, technology, and leadership.

Table 9. *Arbitrary Scale for Digital Maturity Levels*

Scale	Limits	Indicator	Description
4	3.25 - 4.00	Very High	Digital transformation is embedded across the organization.
3	2.50 - 3.24	High	Digital transformation is integrated into some parts of business operations.
2	1.75 - 2.49	Low	The importance of digital transformation is starting to be acknowledged by the organization.
1	1.00 - 1.74	Very Low	Digital transformation is not understood or barely defined.

Respondents' performance in learning ability, time management, engagement, and productivity were assessed using a set of four-point arbitrary scales, as described below.

Table 10. *Arbitrary Scale for Employee's Performance*

Scale	Limits	Indicator	Description
4	3.25 - 4.00	Expert	Exceptional mastery with deep engagement and outstanding productivity.
3	2.50 – 3.24	Advanced	High proficiency with strong engagement and above-average productivity.
2	1.75 – 2.49	Intermediate	Competent performance with moderate engagement and consistent productivity.
1	1.00 – 1.74	Novice	Basic performance with limited engagement and low productivity.

A set of four-point arbitrary scales, presented below, was utilized to measure the impact of maturity on respondents' performance.

Table 11. *Arbitrary Scale for Impact of Maturity on Employee's Performance*

Scale	Limits	Indicator	Description
4	3.25 - 4.00	Very High Impact	Current maturity has a very high impact on employees.
3	2.50 – 3.24	High Impact	Current maturity has a significant impact on employees.
2	1.75 – 2.49	Low Impact	Current maturity has a low impact on employees.
1	1.00 – 1.74	No Impact at all	Current maturity has no impact at all.

A four-point scale, presented below, was used as the evaluation criteria for measuring organizational efficiency in terms of financial, operations, and marketing.

Table 12. *Arbitrary Scale for Organizational Efficiency*

Scale	Limits	Indicator	Description
4	3.25 - 4.00	Exemplary	Outstanding efficiency marked by exceptional performance and innovation.
3	2.50 – 3.24	Advanced	Enhanced efficiency with optimized processes and personalized approaches.
2	1.75 – 2.49	Intermediate	Improved efficiency with effective management across all areas.
1	1.00 – 1.74	Basic or Unsure	Foundational efficiency with basic practices in finance, operations, and marketing.

A set of four-point scales was used as an arbitrary scale to determine the impact of maturity on organizational efficiency in finance, operations, and marketing.

Table 13. *Arbitrary Scale for Impact of Maturity on Organizational Efficiency*

Scale	Limits	Indicator	Description
4	3.25 - 4.00	Very High Impact	Current maturity has a very high impact on the organization.
3	2.50 – 3.24	High Impact	Current maturity has a significant impact on the organization.
2	1.75 – 2.49	Low Impact	Current maturity has a low impact on the organization.
1	1.00 – 1.74	No Impact at all	Current maturity has no impact at all.

Ethical Consideration

This confirmed that the research adhered to all ethical standards. All data collected were used with the participants' informed consent. The researcher upheld the following ethical standards:

Confidentiality. Respondents were notified that their personally identifiable information are kept anonymized and confidential. Private data was not shared, and any details provided by participants were disclosed only with their explicit permission.

Data Accuracy. The researcher ensured meticulous and precise recording of all collected data. All information was systematically documented and kept well-organized.

Integrity. The researcher was committed to providing accurate and truthful information about the research topic.

Privacy. Participants completed the survey questionnaires independently and focus group discussions were conducted in environments where they felt comfortable.

Voluntary Participation. Respondents were invited to take part in this research voluntarily. They were fully informed about its purpose and were asked to sign an informed consent form and participate entirely based on their willingness.

Chapter 3

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

This chapter provides the analyzed data along with a detailed examination and interpretation of the problems outlined in the study. These data were encapsulated through the nine important areas such as (1) Profile of the Respondents; (2) Profile of Organizations; (3) Level of Digital Maturity of the participants regarding People, Culture, Capacity, Capability, Technology, and Leadership; (4) Level of Employees' Performance in terms of Learning Ability, Time Management, Engagement, and Productivity; (5) Level of Organization's Efficiency in terms of Financial, Operations, and Marketing; (6) Significant Difference in the level of Respondents' Maturity and their demographic variables; (7) Significant Difference on the impact of the digital maturity on organizations' efficiency and employees' performance when grouped according to Business Unit/ Department, Job Level, Years of tenure; (8) Significant relationship between the level of digital maturity and its impact on organization's efficiency and employees' performance (9) A model on Progressive Business Transformation for IT-BPO companies.

The data presented below were investigated and explored using homogeneous data characterized by their common employment in the IT-BPO

companies within Makati City. Tabular and textual presentations, analysis, and interpretation are also provided for in-depth review.

Profile of the Respondents

To provide an overview of the respondents' profiles, information such as their age, sex, highest educational attainment, job level, and years of tenure is quantified and presented in tabular form to enable analysis and interpretation.

Table 14. *Respondents' Frequency and Percentage According to Age Group*

Age Group	Frequency	Percentage	Rank
18 - 27	64	19.51	3
28 - 37	154	46.95	1
38 - 47	101	30.79	2
48 - above	9	2.74	4
Total	325	100.00	

The frequency and percentage of the respondents according to age group are summarized in Table 14. The respondents are grouped into four (4) age categories, ranging from 18 to 27 years to 48 years and above. The table shows that the largest group of respondents falls within the 28 to 37-year-old range, with 154 responses, making up 46.95% of the total. This is followed by respondents aged 38 to 47, with 101 responses, or 30.79%. The next group consists of respondents aged 18 to 27, with 64 responses, representing 19.51%. Finally, respondents aged 48 and above account for nine responses or 2.74%.

Recent studies indicate that younger individuals dominate employment in rapidly evolving industries, particularly in sectors like IT-BPO. The Philippine Statistics Authority (2024) data reveals that the country's labor force comprises 67.4 million individuals. Of this number, 17.5 million (26%) are millennials, born between 1981 and 1996, currently aged 28-43, and are divided into two age groups in this study: 28-37 (rank 1) and 38-47 (rank 2). Following this, 11.7 million (18%) are Gen Z, aged 18-24. Correspondingly, research conducted by the (World Economic Forum, 2020), there is a notable shift in the required skills across industries due to advancements in digital technology. This demand is particularly high among younger age groups, who are generally more adaptable to these changes and have higher digital literacy. Similarly, a study by the International Labour Organization (2021), highlighted that workers aged 25 to 35 possess the most relevant digital skills in today's labor market, underscoring a generational gap in technical expertise. The International Labour Organization's report further indicates that older workers often face difficulties in reskilling and upskilling to meet modern job requirements, reinforcing the need for targeted training programs for all age groups to ensure equitable workforce participation.

The results imply that, in the business technology industry, there is a pool of employable younger populations in the labor market; these are the age group segments with skills matching the current high demand of the rapid technological change in the IT-BPO sector. Correspondingly, it is interpreted that few individuals

are engaging in business technology coming from older generations. This indicates a potential mismatch between the skills acquired by various age groups and the competencies required by the industry. Therefore, it is essential to establish supportive policies that promote the development of training systems tailored to meet labor market demands, offering opportunities for workers across all generations.

Table 15. *Frequency and Percentage According to Sex*

Sex	Frequency	Percentage	Rank
Female	152	46.34	2
Male	176	53.66	1
Total	328	100.00	

Table 15 presents the frequency and percentage of the respondents according to sex. As shown in the table, the respondents are divided into two (2) groups: Female and Male. The largest group consists of male respondents, with 176 responses, accounting for 53.66% of the total. This is followed by female respondents, with 152 responses, making up 46.34%.

Recent studies indicate that the business technology industry has a higher proportion of male employees than female. According to the Philippine Statistics Authority (2024), only 33.57% of tertiary students in Engineering and Technology are female, while 39.20% are in IT-related disciplines. This suggests a gender imbalance in the workforce. However, the gap between male and female employees in the Philippines' business technology industry is gradually narrowing. The

country is making strides in gender equality and empowerment, as evidenced by various gender-related indicators. UNESCO (2024) reports that the Philippines has an average literacy rate of 98.2%, with females slightly outperforming males at 98.2% compared to 98.1%. This data demonstrates that gender does not significantly hinder literacy or competence in the Philippines. Rather, more males have traditionally been drawn to the business technology field.

The results imply that gender equality and women's empowerment have been attained in business technology; however, more male students are enrolling in engineering, technology, and IT-related disciplines. This gives the notion of greater participation and equal opportunities to employees in business technology regardless of their gender. The requisite lacking is building the motivation and interest of female students in technology as the future workforce of the business technology industry.

Table 16. *Frequency and Percentage According to Highest Educational Attainment*

Highest Educational Attainment	Frequency	Percentage	Rank
Associate Degree/Vocational Training/ Diploma (short course)	5	1.52	3
Bachelor's Degree	298	90.85	1
Masters	22	6.71	2
Doctorate	3	0.91	4
Total	325	100.00	

The frequency and percentage of the respondents according to highest educational attainment are summarized in Table 16. As shown in the table, the

highest educational attainment of the respondents varies, falling into four (4) groups: Associate Degree/Vocational Training/Diploma (short course), Bachelor's Degree, Master's, and Doctorate. The table shows that the largest group of respondents by educational attainment holds a Bachelor's Degree, with 298 responses constituting 90.85%. This is followed by respondents with a Master's Degree, with 22 responses, or 6.71%. Next are respondents with an Associate Degree, vocational training, or a short course diploma, with five responses representing 1.52%. Finally, three respondents with a Doctorate make up 0.91% of the population.

Recent studies indicate that enrollment in tertiary education among Filipino students has gained momentum, with a consistent increase from 2018 to the present, according to UNESCO (2024). Furthermore, these studies emphasize the growing importance of a Bachelor's Degree as a critical qualification in the business technology sector. A report by Philstar (2024) states that while more firms are open to hiring K-12 graduates, most still prefer candidates with a college degree. For instance, employers expect that 73% (or 12,544) of their 17,273 entry-level jobs in 2024 will be filled by college graduates, leaving less than a quarter available to senior high school finishers. This reflects the industry's preference for candidates with formal higher education. Additionally, key findings from a National Center for Education Statistics survey, cited by Forbes (2022), reveal that individuals with Bachelor's Degrees earn significantly higher salaries and experience lower

unemployment rates than those with only vocational training or Associate Degrees. This trend underscores educational institutions' need to align their programs with industry demands. It highlights the importance of encouraging individuals to pursue higher education to enhance their employability in the competitive business technology landscape.

The results imply that the workforce in business technology is predominantly college graduates. Since there's a notion of scarcity of resources where the demand for work is more than the current supply in the market, it becomes evident to the number of respondents with associate degrees or vocational training to supplement. Correspondingly, masters and doctorates could not be considered vital but more of a "nice-to-have" in the business technology industry, comprising less than 10% of the respondents.

Table 17. *Frequency and Percentage According to Business Unit or Department*

Business Unit or Department	Frequency	Percentage	Rank
Admin & Finance	9	2.74	3
Human Resource	12	3.66	2
Sales & Marketing	7	2.13	4
Service & Delivery	300	91.46	1
Total	328	100.00	

The frequency and percentage of respondents based on their business unit or department are summarized in Table 17. This table reveals a clear trend in educational attainment across different departments. Most respondents, constituting 91.46% or 300 individuals, are affiliated with the Service & Delivery

department. Following this, the Human Resources department accounts for 12 respondents, making up 3.66% of the total. The Admin & Finance department has nine respondents, representing 2.74%, while the Sales & Marketing department has the fewest individuals, totaling seven respondents, or 2.13%.

This distribution of respondents across various business units aligns with current industry trends emphasizing service delivery's critical role in business technology. A study by Deloitte (2023) highlights that organizations increasingly prioritize service delivery to enhance customer satisfaction and operational efficiency. This trend is especially prevalent in technology-driven sectors where rapid response to client needs is essential for maintaining competitive advantage. Additionally, a report from McKinsey & Company (2024) emphasizes that companies with robust service delivery teams tend to outperform their competitors in key performance indicators, such as customer retention and revenue growth. As a result, organizations must strategically invest in their Service & Delivery departments while simultaneously recognizing the importance of supporting Human Resources, Admin & Finance, and Sales & Marketing. This approach bolsters internal collaboration and optimizes resource allocation, ultimately driving overall business success.

The results imply a strong concentration of employees within the Service & Delivery department, which may reflect the organization's operational focus and priorities. The overwhelming majority in this area suggests it plays a critical role in

the company's overall strategy and performance. The smaller representation in the Human Resource, Admin & Finance, and Sales & Marketing departments may indicate a more streamlined approach to these functions or potential areas for growth and development within the organization. Given the high percentage of employees in Service & Delivery, the organization must ensure adequate support and resources and foster collaboration between departments to enhance overall organizational effectiveness.

Table 18. *Frequency and Percentage According to Job Level*

Job Level	Frequency	Percentage	Rank
Entry-Level Professional/ Rank and File	79	24.09	2
Officer (Senior Engineer/Team Lead/ Supervisor)	220	67.07	1
Manager	26	7.93	3
Top Management (C-Level, V-President, Director)	3	0.91	4
Total	328	100.00	

Table 18 presents the distribution of respondents according to their job level. As shown in the table, the job levels of the respondents vary, falling into four (4) groups: Entry-Level Professional/Rank and File, Officer (Senior Engineer/Team Lead/Supervisor), Manager, and Top Management (C-Level, Vice-President, Director). The table shows that the largest group of respondents by job level is the Officer rank, or an equivalent higher position with titles such as Senior, Lead, or Supervisor, with 220 responses, making up 67.07%. This is followed by Entry-Level Professionals, or the equivalent of Rank and File, with 79 responses,

constituting 24.09%. Next, there are 26 respondents in managerial positions, accounting for 7.93%, while respondents in Top Management roles, such as C-level, Vice-President, and Director, total three responses, constituting 0.91%.

The job level distribution within the organization reflects broader workforce trends, especially prevalent in the technology sector. According to a McKinsey & Company report (2024), many companies are adopting flatter organizational structures to enhance agility and responsiveness, leading to a higher concentration of employees in mid-level roles, like those classified as Officers in this study. This structure facilitates quicker decision-making and fosters innovation by encouraging employees to contribute ideas regardless of their position. Forbes Business Council (2024) also highlights that most entry-level talent today belongs to Gen Z, who bring unique preferences and expectations. Notably, 65% of Gen Z employees leave their jobs within the first year, with an anticipated average of 10 job changes between ages 18 and 34. This trend underscores the need for organizations to understand and address Gen Z's needs for effective recruitment and retention. It also highlights the importance of clear career pathways and succession planning to motivate employees toward career advancement, helping maintain a balanced and engaged workforce.

The results reveal significant insights into the organizational structure and dynamics based on the job-level distribution of respondents. The predominance of Officers indicates a strategic alignment with current workforce trends towards

flatter organizational hierarchies that promote agility and innovation. This concentration in mid-level positions facilitates faster decision-making and empowers employees to contribute ideas actively, fostering a culture of collaboration and creativity. Additionally, the notable presence of Entry-Level Professionals highlights the influx of Gen Z talent, whose unique preferences necessitate tailored recruitment and retention strategies. Given the significant turnover rates among Gen Z employees, organizations must prioritize clear career pathways and succession planning to motivate this workforce segment and ensure long-term engagement. Organizations can enhance employee satisfaction, drive productivity, and position themselves for sustained growth in an ever-evolving market by addressing these dynamics.

Table 19. *Frequency and Percentage According to Years of Tenure*

Years of Tenure	Frequency	Percentage	Rank
Less than 3 years	137	41.77	1
3 – 6 years	114	34.76	2
7 – 10 years	34	10.37	4
More than 10 years	43	13.11	3
Total	328	100.00	

The frequency and percentage of respondents based on their years of tenure with the company are summarized in Table 19. As shown in the table, the respondents' tenure years varied as they fell into four (4) groups, ranging from less than 3 years to 10 years or more. The largest segment, comprising 41.77% of respondents (137 individuals), has been with the company for less than 3 years.

This is followed by 34.76% (114 respondents) employed for 3 to 6 years. In contrast, those with tenure between 7 to 10 years account for 10.37% (34 individuals), while employees with more than 10 years of service make up 13.11% (43 respondents). Following this group, 34.76% (114 respondents) have been with the company for 3 to 6 years, representing a strong base of employees with moderate experience.

In recent studies, according to MagellanSolutions (2023), employee attrition is one of the biggest challenges in business technology companies; the attrition rate in the business process outsourcing sector was the highest among all industries, at 40% in 2023. The distribution of years of tenure underscores the need for organizations to cultivate a culture of retention and continuous development, particularly as the workforce is predominantly composed of individuals with less than three years of experience. According to a study by the Society for Human Resource Management (2024), organizations with a high percentage of new employees often face challenges related to employee engagement and retention, which can impact overall productivity. The report emphasizes the importance of developing onboarding programs and mentorship initiatives that help new hires acclimate to the company culture and create pathways for professional growth. Furthermore, a survey by Gallup (2023) indicates that companies with effective mentorship programs experience higher employee satisfaction and retention rates, especially among younger employees seeking guidance and opportunities for

advancement. By fostering an environment that values knowledge sharing and professional development, the organization can enhance employee loyalty and capitalize on the skills of both new and seasoned staff.

The results reveal a relatively young and dynamic workforce within the organization. The significant proportion of employees with less than 3 years of tenure indicates a strong influx of new talent, potentially reflecting recent growth or expansion efforts. The solid representation of those with 3 to 6 years of experience further supports this trend, highlighting a workforce that is becoming increasingly skilled. However, the smaller percentages of longer-tenured employees suggest that while there is a foundation of experienced staff, the organization may benefit from implementing knowledge transfer and mentorship programs to harness the expertise of these seasoned employees and foster continuity within the team.

Profile of the Organizations

This section presents an overview of various organizations, highlighting their profiles based on three key criteria: type of service, years in operation, and number of employees. By examining these factors, the section provides insight into organizations' diverse landscape, operational longevity, and workforce capacity.

Table 20. *Frequency and Percentage of the Organization According to Type of Service*

Type of Service	Frequency	Percentage	Rank
Selling Software	188	57.32	1
IT Services	93	28.35	2
Consulting Services	47	14.33	3
Total	328	100.00	

Table 20 summarizes the organization's frequency and percentage distribution according to the type of service offered. The predominant type of service offered is Selling Software, with 188 respondents representing 57.32% of the total. This is followed by IT Services, which account for 93 respondents, or 28.35%. Consulting Services represent the smallest segment, with 47 respondents, making up 14.33% of the total.

Moreover, the predominance of Selling Software as the primary service aligns with broader industry trends, where software solutions continue to drive innovation and business growth. According to a report by Statista (2024), the global software market is projected to grow significantly, with increasing demand for cloud-based solutions and enterprise software driving this expansion. This trend emphasizes the importance of organizations focusing on software development and sales to remain competitive in the ever-evolving tech landscape. Additionally, a survey conducted by McKinsey & Company (2024) indicates that companies offering IT services alongside software solutions experience improved customer loyalty and retention, as clients often prefer a single provider for their technology

needs. This synergy between software sales and IT services enhances customer satisfaction by ensuring seamless integration and support. The smaller share of Consulting Services presents an opportunity for the organization to leverage its existing client relationships and industry expertise to expand this segment, potentially increasing overall revenue and positioning itself as a comprehensive solutions provider.

The results reveal that Selling Software is the organization's primary focus, indicating a significant commitment to software development and sales. This dominance suggests that the organization has established a robust market presence in the software industry, which may contribute to its overall revenue and growth potential. The representation of IT Services as the second-largest segment reflects a complementary offering that supports software sales, potentially enhancing customer experience and satisfaction through technical support and maintenance. Meanwhile, while smaller, the Consulting Services segment may provide valuable insights and strategies for clients, but it may also indicate an area for potential expansion. Overall, the distribution of services highlights the organization's strengths in software sales and IT services while presenting opportunities for growth in consulting services to further diversify its service offerings.

Table 21. *Frequency and Percentage of the Organization According to Years in Operation*

Years in Operation	Frequency	Percentage	Rank
4 years	47	14.33	3
21 years	93	28.35	2
41 years	188	57.32	1
Total	328	100.00	

Table 21 summarizes the frequency and percentage distribution of organizations according to years in operation. The largest segment comprises organizations operating for 41 years, with 188 respondents representing 57.32%. This is followed by those with 21 years of operation, accounting for 93 respondents or 28.35%. The smallest segment is the organizations operating for 4 years, with 47 respondents constituting 14.33%.

This distribution of years in operation underscores the importance of experience and innovation within the industry. A study by PwC (2024) indicates that established companies benefit from their longevity by leveraging extensive networks and customer loyalty, which can enhance their competitive edge in the marketplace. Furthermore, the integration of newer organizations, which are often more agile and innovative, can lead to dynamic partnerships and collaborations that drive industry progress. According to a report by the Harvard Business Review (2022), companies that effectively combine the stability of long-standing firms with the creativity of newer entrants often experience accelerated growth and adaptability to changing market demands. This collaborative synergy can result in

the development of cutting-edge solutions and services that benefit established and emerging industry players. The sector can enhance its overall resilience and responsiveness to market trends by fostering relationships between these different types of organizations.

The results reveal that most respondents belong to well-established organizations, with a significant portion operating for 41 years. This longevity indicates a strong foundation and stability within the industry, which can help build trust and credibility with clients and stakeholders. The presence of organizations operating for 21 years demonstrates a healthy mix of experience within the sector. In contrast, the smaller percentage of newer organizations operating for 4 years highlights a fresh influx of ideas and innovation that can invigorate the industry. Overall, the combination of long-standing and relatively new organizations creates a balanced landscape where established firms can share their expertise and mentorship with newer entrants, fostering a collaborative environment for growth and development.

Table 22. *Frequency and Percentage of the Organization According to Number of Employees*

Number of Employees	Frequency	Percentage	Rank
1,042 employees	188	57.32	1
517 employees	93	28.35	2
260 employees	47	14.33	3
Total	328	100.00	

Table 22 summarizes the frequency and percentage distribution of organizations according to the number of employees. The largest group consists of organizations with 1,042 employees, with 188 respondents representing 57.32%. This is followed by organizations with 517 employees, constituting 93 respondents or 28.35%. The smallest segment comprises organizations with 260 employees, totaling 47 respondents, representing 14.33%.

This diversity in organizational size is critical for promoting a balanced and resilient industry ecosystem. Larger organizations, as indicated by the majority of respondents with over 1,042 employees, often benefit from economies of scale, which allow them to invest in advanced technologies and processes. Research by Becker et al. (2022) highlights that larger firms can allocate significant resources to research and development, thereby driving innovation and improving service delivery. Conversely, mid-sized organizations with around 517 employees can leverage their flexibility to adapt quickly to market changes, a trait often noted by Franczak and Laurence (2022), which suggests that agility is a key competitive advantage for firms of this size. Moreover, smaller organizations with 260 employees often thrive in niche markets where specialized expertise and personalized service are paramount. This symbiotic relationship between organizations of varying sizes encourages the exchange of best practices and fosters an environment where innovation can flourish. By promoting collaboration across

different organizational scales, the industry can enhance overall performance and adapt more effectively to emerging trends.

The results indicate that organizations employing over 1,000 individuals demonstrate a strong capacity for managing large-scale operations, suggesting they have established robust systems and processes to support their workforce. Organizations with 517 employees reflect a mid-sized operational structure, which can provide agility and flexibility while maintaining substantial resources. In contrast, smaller organizations with 260 employees may indicate niche operations or specialized services. Overall, this distribution highlights a diverse range of organizational sizes, allowing for varying levels of complexity, innovation, and service delivery within the industry. Organizations of different sizes can learn from one another, fostering a collaborative environment that enhances practices.

Table 23. *Frequency and Percentage of the Organization According to Business Size in Capital*

Business Size in Capital	Frequency	Percentage	Rank
Small	47	14.33	3
Medium	93	28.35	2
Large	188	57.32	1
Total	328	100.00	

Table 23 presents the frequency and percentage distribution of organizations categorized by business size based on capital. The largest segment comprises a large organization, accounting for 188 respondents, or 57.32% of the total sample. A medium-sized organization follows, with 93 respondents

representing 28.35%. A small organization makes up the smallest segment, with 47 respondents, corresponding to 14.33% of the total. This breakdown provides a clear overview of the organizational landscape by capital size, highlighting the dominance of larger entities in the sample.

This distribution of business size emphasizes the importance of capital resources in fostering innovation and competitive advantage within the industry. A World Economic Forum (2023) study indicates that large organizations leverage their substantial capital to invest in cutting-edge technologies and research and development, significantly enhancing their capacity to innovate and respond to market demands. This aligns with the notion that economies of scale enable larger firms to reduce costs and expand their market share more effectively than their smaller counterparts. Medium-sized organizations play a crucial role in this landscape, as they often have the flexibility to pivot quickly in response to changing market conditions while maintaining access to significant resources. According to a report by Grant Thornton Philippines (2024), medium-sized enterprises are critical to economic resilience, as they often bridge the gap between large corporations and smaller firms, allowing for collaboration and knowledge sharing across the industry. On the other hand, small organizations, while representing a smaller segment, are vital for fostering innovation and competition. A publication by the International Trade Center (2020) highlights that small businesses are often the source of new ideas and niche services, driving creativity and diversity in the

market. This blend of large, medium, and small organizations creates a balanced ecosystem where established players can mentor and collaborate with emerging firms, fostering an environment ripe for growth and innovation.

The results indicate a clear predominance of large organizations within the industry, suggesting that these entities have significant capital resources, enabling them to invest in growth, development, and innovation. The large size of this segment may also point to competitive advantages, such as economies of scale and more significant market influence. Representing medium-sized organizations signifies a vital market part, capable of agility and adaptability while possessing substantial resources. In contrast, the smaller organizations segment may indicate emerging players or niche markets with specialized services. Overall, this distribution highlights a diverse business landscape, where different sizes of organizations coexist, contributing to a dynamic industry characterized by varying degrees of innovation, competition, and service delivery.

The Level of Digital Maturity of the Respondents in terms of People, Culture, Capacity, Capability, Technology, and Leadership

This analysis offers quantitative data on essential areas such as people, culture, capacity, capability, technology, and leadership to achieve a thorough understanding of the respondents' organizational digital maturity. The information is structured in a tabular format to enhance analysis and interpretation.

Table 24. *Digital Maturity Level*

Level	Limits	Maturity	Description
1	1.00 - 1.74	Minimal	Digital transformation is not understood or barely defined.
2	1.75 - 2.49	Transitional	Importance of digital transformation starting to be acknowledged by the organization.
3	2.50 - 3.24	Customer-driven	Digital transformation is integrated at some part of business operations.
4	3.25 - 4.00	Transformed	Digital transformation is embedded across organization.

Table 24 presents the maturity levels derived from the digital maturity assessment tool developed by the Government of South Australia (2022). This table outlines the various stages of maturity, providing a comprehensive framework for evaluating digital capabilities. Additionally, the researcher meticulously generated the descriptions used as foundational bases for the criteria in this study to ensure relevance and alignment with the research objectives.

Table 25. *Scales of the Maturity level of the respondents toward People, Culture, Capacity, Capability, Technology, and Leadership*

Level	Limits	Interpretation	Description
4	3.25 - 4.00	Very High	Digital transformation is embedded across organization.
3	2.50 - 3.24	High	Digital transformation is integrated at some part of business operations.
2	1.75 - 2.49	Low	Importance of digital transformation starting to be acknowledged by the organization.
1	1.00 - 1.74	Very Low	Digital transformation is not understood or barely defined.

The table presents a scale measuring respondents' maturity levels in terms of people, culture, capacity, capability, technology, and leadership, explicitly regarding digital transformation.

The levels range from "Very Low" to "Very High." At a very high level, digital transformation is fully embedded throughout the organization. In the High range, it is integrated into certain business operations. The Low level indicates that the organization is beginning to acknowledge the importance of digital transformation. Finally, the very low level shows that digital transformation is poorly understood or barely defined.

This scale is a valuable tool to assess how well digital transformation is adopted within organizations. It provides insights to guide planning and implementation efforts for greater digital maturity.

Table 26. *Level of Maturity Based on People*

Indicators	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation
1. Awareness of digital opportunities	3.57	Very High
2. Readiness for new digital tools and innovations	3.26	Very High
3. Enthusiasm for technological advancements	3.44	Very High
4. Acceptance of digital transformation	3.43	Very High
5. Adaptability to evolving technologies	3.41	Very High
Overall	3.42	Very High

Table 26 presents the weighted mean, descriptive equivalent, and verbal interpretation of the maturity level based on the People dimension. The overall weighted mean is 3.42, with a verbal interpretation of a “Very High” level of maturity and a descriptive equivalent indicating that digital transformation is embedded across the organization. The first indicator, awareness of digital opportunities, achieved the highest mean score of 3.57, also classified as “Very High.” The second indicator, readiness for digital tools and innovations, received the lowest mean score of 3.26, still interpreted as “Very High” in maturity level. This maturity assessment based on the People dimension is crucial, as it underscores the importance of human capital in driving successful digital transformation initiatives.

A recent study by Alojail and Khan (2023) underscores that organizations with a strong focus on building digital skills among their employees are more likely to achieve sustainable transformation outcomes. The current maturity indicates that respondents recognize the importance of digital initiatives and are enthusiastic about integrating technology into their workflows. The strong awareness of digital opportunities aligns with findings from a report by McKinsey & Company (2024) that emphasizes how awareness of digital trends can enhance strategic decision-making and foster innovation. Organizations prioritizing awareness and education about digital tools create a workforce better equipped to leverage these technologies effectively.

The results suggest that employees are well-prepared for digital transformation. It suggests that employees' awareness of digital opportunities is strong, and they are ready to adopt new tools and innovations. Enthusiasm for technological advancements is also evident, demonstrating a positive outlook toward digital progress. Moreover, the organization has widespread acceptance of digital transformation, accompanied by high adaptability to evolving technologies. Overall, the maturity level in these areas indicates a highly developed capability to embrace and manage digital transformation among the people involved.

Table 27. *Level of Maturity Based on Culture*

Indicators	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation
1. Openness to cultural change and innovation	3.44	Very High
2. Investing in relevant technology upskilling	3.32	Very High
3. Regular use of digital tools for collaboration	3.46	Very High
4. Seeking new solutions to enhance work processes	3.44	Very High
5. Embedding digital culture in everyday work practices	3.38	Very High
Overall	3.41	Very High

Table 27 shows the weighted mean and its corresponding descriptive equivalent and verbal interpretation on the level of maturity based on Culture. In this table, the overall weighted mean is 3.41, with a verbal interpretation of a “Very High” level of maturity and a descriptive equivalent of digital transformation embedded across the organization. The third indicator, regular use of digital tools

for collaboration, garnered the highest mean score of 3.46, with a verbal interpretation of “Very High.” The lowest mean score is for the second indicator, investing in relevant technology upskilling, which received a weighted mean of 3.32. This indicator can also be verbally interpreted as a “Very High” level.

The maturity assessment based on the Culture dimension highlights the pivotal role of organizational culture in facilitating digital transformation. The current maturity level indicates a solid foundation for digital practices within the organization, demonstrating a strong cultural alignment with technological advancements. A report by Deloitte (2023) emphasizes that organizations with a culture supportive of innovation and change are more likely to succeed in their digital transformation efforts. The high rating for all indicators implies that employees are receptive to new ideas and are willing to adapt to innovative practices. This openness is critical, as a culture that encourages experimentation and accepts failures as part of the learning process can drive significant advancements in digital initiatives. A recent McKinsey & Company (2024) study supports this notion, indicating that organizations fostering a culture of agility and openness are more adept at navigating the complexities of digital transformation. According to Forbes (2023), continuous investment in upskilling is essential for maintaining a workforce that can effectively utilize emerging technologies and remain competitive in a rapidly evolving digital landscape.

The results imply that employees are well-prepared for digital transformation. They indicate that employees are open to cultural change and innovation and are investing in relevant technology upskilling. Regular use of digital tools for collaboration and seeking new solutions to enhance work processes are also strong, demonstrating a positive outlook toward digital progress. Moreover, there is widespread embedding of digital culture in everyday work practices within the organization, accompanied by a high level of adaptability to evolving technologies.

Table 28. *Level of Maturity Based on Capacity*

Indicators	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation
1. Providing resources and budget for digital initiatives	3.09	High
2. Providing resources and budget for digital initiatives	3.26	Very High
3. Equipping employees with effective digital tools	3.27	Very High
4. Adapting to new trends and technologies	3.27	Very High
5. Working with external partners for business improvements	3.08	High
Overall	3.19	High

Table 28 shows the weighted mean and its corresponding descriptive equivalent and verbal interpretation on the level of maturity based on Capacity. The overall weighted mean in this table is 3.19, with a verbal interpretation of “High” and a descriptive equivalent of transformation integrated at some part of business operations. It is also presented that the third and fourth indicators, equipping

employees with effective digital tools and adapting to new trends and technologies, garnered the highest mean score of 3.27, with a verbal interpretation of “Very High.” The lowest mean score is for the fifth indicator, working with external partners for business improvements, which received a weighted mean of 3.08. This indicator can be verbally interpreted as “High” in maturity level.

The maturity assessment based on the Capacity dimension reveals essential insights into the organization’s readiness for digital transformation. The current maturity level is High, indicating a solid framework for implementing digital initiatives. However, this score also highlights areas for potential enhancement. A report by (Wodtke, 2024) emphasizes that organizations with robust capacity, both in terms of resources and budget allocation, are more likely to succeed in their goals. The indicator on providing resources and budget for digital initiatives received the highest rating, reflecting a strong commitment to supporting digital projects financially. This aligns with findings from a recent study by Oracle NetSuite (2024), which suggests that organizations prioritizing budget allocation for technology investments tend to experience higher levels of success in their efforts. When adequately equipped, employees are better positioned to leverage technology effectively, driving innovation and efficiency. Furthermore, working with external partners for business improvements is seen as a critical strategy, enabling organizations to tap into specialized expertise and accelerate their digital transformation journey.

The results imply that employees are well-prepared for digital transformation. They suggest that organizations provide resources and budgets for digital initiatives, equip employees with effective digital tools, adapt to new trends and technologies, and work with external partners for business improvements. While the overall level of maturity is classified as High, there is still room for improvement in certain areas, such as providing resources and budget for digital initiatives.

Table 29. *Level of Maturity Based on Capability*

Indicators	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation
1. Developing digital policies and procedures for operations	3.30	Very High
2. Investing in technical training and development	3.18	High
3. Utilizing new digital resources for rapid technological change	3.23	High
4. Supporting and maintaining all digital activities	3.23	High
5. Improving employee performance with digital tools	3.20	High
Overall	3.23	High

Table 29 shows the weighted mean and its corresponding descriptive equivalent and verbal interpretation on the level of maturity based on Capability. The overall weighted mean in this table is 3.23, with verbal interpretation of a “High” level of maturity and a descriptive equivalent of digital

transformation embedded across the organization. It is also presented that the first indicator, developing digital policies and procedures for operations, garnered the highest mean score of 3.30, with a verbal interpretation of “Very High.” The lowest mean score is for the second indicator, investing in technical training and development, which received a weighted mean of 3.18. This indicator can be verbally interpreted as “High” in maturity level.

The assessment of maturity based on the Capability dimension underscores the importance of establishing a strong foundation for digital transformation within the organization. The current rating indicates that the organization has made significant strides in enhancing its capabilities related to digital initiatives. However, it also highlights areas for further development. Research by Deloitte (2023) emphasizes that organizations with robust capabilities—especially in policy development and employee training—are better positioned to achieve successful transformations. The highest-scoring indicator, Developing digital policies and procedures for operations, reflects a proactive approach to formalizing digital practices within the organization. A study by McKinsey & Company (2024) highlighted that organizations prioritizing technical training for their employees experience higher rates of digital adoption and overall success in transformation initiatives.

The results imply that employees are well-prepared for digital transformation. They suggest that organizations develop digital policies and

procedures, invest in technical training and development, utilize new digital resources, support and maintain digital activities, and improve employee performance with digital tools. While the overall level of maturity is classified as High, there is still room for improvement in certain areas, such as investing in technical training and development.

Table 30. *Level of Maturity Based on Technology*

Indicators	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation
1. Understanding technology's usefulness in the workplace	3.47	Very High
2. Commitment to leveraging modern technology (such as IT systems and modern architecture)	3.38	Very High
3. Agility in adapting to and innovating with new technologies	3.34	Very High
4. Using technology to optimize business processes	3.45	Very High
5. Resilience toward technological change	3.32	Very High
Overall	3.39	Very High

Table 30 shows the weighted mean and its corresponding descriptive equivalent and verbal interpretation on the level of maturity based on Technology. The overall weighted mean in this table is 3.39, with verbal interpretation of a "Very High" level of maturity and a descriptive equivalent of digital transformation embedded across the organization. The first indicator, understanding technology's usefulness in the workplace, also showed that it garnered the highest mean score of 3.47, with a verbal interpretation of "Very

High.” The lowest mean score is for the fifth indicator, resilience toward technological change, which received a weighted mean of 3.32. This indicator can be verbally interpreted as a “Very High” level of maturity.

The evaluation of maturity based on the Technology dimension demonstrates a commendable readiness for digital transformation within the organization. The current rating indicates that the organization has effectively integrated technology into its operational framework. This high maturity level is critical, as technological proficiency is a key driver of successful digital transformation. According to Lund (2024), organizations prioritizing technology adoption tend to experience enhanced operational efficiency and improved customer experiences. The indicator about understanding technology’s usefulness in the workplace reflects a strong recognition of technology’s role in enhancing productivity and efficiency. This aligns with findings from a recent study by Sun (2024), which emphasizes that technological innovation has become the key for enterprises to gain competitive advantage in today’s rapidly changing business environment. Organizations that actively commit to adopting modern IT systems and architectures can optimize their operations and remain competitive in rapidly evolving markets.

The results strongly suggest that employees are well-prepared for continuous and progressive digital transformation across all key indicators. They suggest that employees recognize the value of technology in the workplace, are

committed to utilizing modern tools, demonstrate agility in adopting and innovating with new technologies, and actively use technology to optimize business processes. Additionally, they exhibit resilience in the face of technological change. This points to a high level of maturity in technology adoption and usage within the organization.

Table 31. *Level of Maturity Based on Leadership*

Indicators	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation
1. Communicates the importance of digitalization for success	3.32	Very High
2. Prioritizing digital literacy and skill development	3.34	Very High
3. Encourages cross-departmental collaboration for innovation	3.24	High
4. Seeks employee feedback on digitalization efforts	3.12	High
5. Stays informed on digital trends and includes them in plans	3.34	Very High
Overall	3.27	Very High

Table 31 shows the weighted mean and its corresponding descriptive equivalent and verbal interpretation on the level of maturity based on Leadership. The overall weighted mean in this table is 3.27, with a verbal interpretation of a “Very High” level of maturity and a descriptive equivalent of digital transformation embedded across the organization. It is also presented that the second and fifth indicators, prioritizing digital literacy and skill development, staying informed on digital trends, and including them in plans, garnered the

highest mean scores of 3.34, with a verbal interpretation of “Very High.” The lowest mean score is for the fourth indicator, which seeks employee feedback on digitalization efforts, which received a weighted mean of 3.12. This indicator can be verbally interpreted as “High” in maturity level.

The analysis of maturity based on the Leadership dimension reveals a robust commitment to digital transformation within the organization, indicating that leadership plays a crucial role in embedding digital transformation into the organizational culture. Effective leadership is essential for navigating the complexities of digital change as leadership shifts can unleash an era of sustainable, inclusive growth for companies looking to outperform in this era of disruption, as supported by McKinsey & Company (2024), which highlights that organizations with strong digital leadership tend to achieve greater success in their transformation initiatives. The indicator communicates the importance of digitalization for success and achieves the highest mean score, reflecting strong leadership engagement in promoting the significance of digital transformation. This is consistent with findings from Zhu et al. (2022), which emphasize that leaders who articulate a clear vision for digitalization foster a culture of innovation and adaptability among employees, ultimately enhancing organizational performance. Conversely, the indicator that seeks employee feedback on digitalization efforts received the lowest mean score, which, although interpreted as High, points to an opportunity for improvement. Actively soliciting feedback from employees helps leadership

understand the effectiveness of digital initiatives and fosters a sense of inclusion and collaboration within the organization. According to a report by Piette (2023), organizations that prioritize employee feedback in their digital strategies are better equipped to address challenges and drive successful outcomes.

The results strongly suggest that respondents are well-prepared for continuous and progressive digital transformation, particularly due to leadership's efforts. They suggest that leadership has effectively communicated the importance of digitalization, prioritizing digital literacy and skill development, fostering cross-departmental collaboration, seeking continuous employee feedback, and staying updated on emerging digital trends. This demonstrates a high level of maturity in how leadership actively guides and supports the organization through its digital transformation journey.

Table 32. *Summary of Level of Digital Maturity of the Respondents in terms of People, Culture, Capacity, Capability, Technology, and Leadership*

Pillars	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation
People	3.42	Very High
Culture	3.41	Very High
Capacity	3.19	High
Capability	3.23	High
Technology	3.39	Very High
Leadership	3.27	Very High
Overall	3.32	Very High

Table 32 summarizes the respondents' levels of digital maturity in terms of people, culture, capacity, capability, technology, and leadership. A 3.32 overall

weighted mean with a verbal interpretation of “Very High” indicates that respondents in this study belong to an organization with a maturity level equivalent to “Transformed,” which describes digital transformation embedded across the organization.

The Level of Employees’ Performance in terms of Learning Ability, Time Management, Engagement, and Productivity

To comprehensively understand the employees’ performance, this analysis presents quantitative data on key areas: learning ability, time management, engagement, and productivity. The information is organized in a tabular format to facilitate analysis and interpretation.

Table 33. *Scales of Level of Employees’ Performance*

Scale	Limits	Indicator	Description
4	3.25 - 4.00	Expert	Exceptional mastery with deep engagement and outstanding productivity.
3	2.50 – 3.24	Advanced	High proficiency with strong engagement and above-average productivity.
2	1.75 – 2.49	Intermediate	Competent performance with moderate engagement and consistent productivity.
1	1.00 – 1.74	Novice	Basic performance with limited engagement and low productivity.

Table 33 outlines a four-point scale for evaluating employees’ performance based on learning ability, time management, engagement, and

productivity. At the Expert level, employees show exceptional skill, strong engagement, and outstanding productivity expectations. The Advanced level reflects high skill, solid engagement, and above-average productivity. Intermediate employees demonstrate competent performance, moderate engagement, and meet productivity standards. Novice employees have basic skills, limited engagement, and low productivity. This scale offers a clear and objective way to assess employee performance.

Table 34. *Level of Employees' Performance Based on Learning Ability*

Indicators	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation
1. Technical Proficiency: I use tools and technologies well.	3.29	Expert
2. Adaptability: I handle new skills or changes effectively.	3.32	Expert
3. Learning Agility: I seek learning opportunities and improve.	3.29	Expert
4. Critical Thinking: I solve tough issues effectively.	3.35	Expert
5. Continuous Improvement: I pursue growth and enhancement.	3.45	Expert
Overall	3.34	Expert

Table 34 presents the weighted mean, descriptive equivalent, and verbal interpretation of employee performance based on Learning Ability. The overall weighted mean is 3.34, which is verbally interpreted as an "Expert" level and corresponds to a descriptive equivalent of exceptional mastery with deep engagement and outstanding productivity. Among the indicators, continuous

improvement received the highest mean score of 3.45, also interpreted as "Expert" level. On the other hand, the lowest mean scores, 3.29, were observed for the first and third indicators, technical proficiency and learning agility, which are both interpreted as "Expert" levels.

The analysis of employees' performance shows impressive levels based on their Learning Ability and its corresponding indicator. This strong performance reflects an organization deeply committed to fostering a culture of continuous learning and adaptability, which is crucial for navigating the complexities of digital transformation. The emphasis on learning ability aligns with recent studies emphasizing its importance for organizational success in rapidly changing environments. The indicator about continuous improvement achieved the highest rating, signifying a robust commitment among employees to refine their skills and processes. This finding resonates with insights from Forbes (2023), which underscores that organizations prioritizing continuous learning foster innovation and enhance overall productivity. Employees who embrace continuous improvement contribute to their individual growth and drive the organization's adaptability and resilience in the face of change. According to a report by Deloitte (2023), organizations that invest in technical training and support for their employees see significant improvements in both performance and job satisfaction.

The results suggest that employees demonstrate a high level of preparedness and performance regarding learning ability. They exhibit strong technical proficiency, adaptability, learning agility, and critical thinking skills while also showing a commitment to continuous improvement. These findings point to a very high level of employee performance in learning ability across the workforce.

Table 35. *Level of Employees' Performance Based on Time Management*

Indicators	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation
1. Efficiency: I meet deadlines and complete tasks on time.	3.33	Expert
2. Flexibility: I can adjust priorities to handle workload changes.	3.38	Expert
3. Problem-solving: I can resolve issues that hinder productivity.	3.29	Expert
4. Skill Improvement: I continually improve my time management.	3.29	Expert
5. Work-Life Balance: I can balance work and personal life.	3.20	Advanced
Overall	3.30	Expert

Table 35 presents the weighted mean, descriptive equivalent, and verbal interpretation of employee performance based on Time Management. The overall weighted mean is 3.30, verbally interpreted as an "Expert" level, which corresponds to exceptional mastery with deep engagement and outstanding productivity. Among the indicators, flexibility achieved the highest mean score

of 3.38, which is also interpreted as "Expert." In contrast, the lowest mean score of 3.20 was recorded for the fifth indicator, work-life balance, which is verbally interpreted as an "Advanced" level only.

The results show a strong organizational commitment to enhancing employees' time management skills, which is essential for navigating the complexities of modern work environments. The flexibility indicator reinforces the employees' ability to adapt to shifting demands and prioritize tasks effectively. This flexibility is critical in today's fast-paced work culture, where unexpected changes frequently arise. A study by Deep (2023) emphasizes that organizations fostering flexibility in their workforce experience greater resilience and adaptability, allowing them to respond swiftly to challenges and opportunities. Conversely, the lowest mean score was for the indicator Work-Life Balance, which is classified as Advanced. While this score still reflects a solid level of performance, it highlights an area where improvement is necessary. Achieving a healthy work-life balance is crucial for employee satisfaction and long-term productivity. Research from Rony, Numan, and Alamgir (2023) indicates that organizations prioritizing work-life balance report lower employee burnout rates and higher job satisfaction.

The results indicate that employees are well-prepared and perform well in time management. They demonstrate efficiency and flexibility, effectively solve productivity-related problems, and are committed to continuously

improving their time management skills. Additionally, they can maintain a work-life balance, although there is still room for enhancement. These findings reflect a high level of performance in time management among employees.

Table 36. *Level of Employees' Performance Based on Engagement*

Indicators	Mean	Interpretation
1. Organizational Pride: I am proud to work for my organization.	3.28	Expert
2. Work Satisfaction: I find my work fulfilling.	3.20	Advanced
3. Team Commitment: My coworkers go the extra mile.	3.10	Advanced
4. Personal Commitment: I seek ways to improve my work.	3.34	Expert
5. Future Outlook: I plan to stay with the organization long-term.	3.20	Advanced
Overall	3.20	Advanced

Table 36 presents the weighted mean, descriptive equivalent, and verbal interpretation of employee performance based on Engagement. The overall weighted mean is 3.20, verbally interpreted as an "Advanced" level, corresponding to high proficiency with strong engagement and above-average productivity. The fourth indicator, personal commitment, achieved the highest mean score of 3.34, earning a verbal interpretation of the "Expert" level. Conversely, the lowest mean score of 3.10 was recorded for the third indicator, team commitment, which is verbally interpreted as an "Advanced" level only.

The assessment of employees' performance based on Engagement reflects a critical aspect of organizational health and productivity. The overall rating, categorized as Advanced, suggests that employees

demonstrate a high level of engagement with their work and the organization. As noted by Abdelwahed and Doghan (2023), employee engagement represents the highest degree of commitment and involvement employees have toward their organization. In the workplace, engaged employees consistently demonstrate initiative, professional behavior, and dedication to high-performance standards, with work commitment reflecting an individual's identification with and active participation in the organization, strongly linked to positive outcomes and further reinforced by the positive relationship between leadership behavior, job performance, organizational commitment, and supportive organizational culture (Abdelwahed & Doghan, 2023). In contrast, the lowest mean score was for the indicator Team Commitment, also interpreted as Advanced. While this score indicates a solid commitment to teamwork, it suggests room for improvement in fostering collaboration and support among coworkers. A study by Deloitte (2023) indicates that high levels of team commitment can significantly impact organizational success, driving both productivity and innovation.

Overall, the indicators are interpreted as either Expert or Advanced, suggesting that employees are well-prepared and perform at a high engagement level. It suggests that employees are proud of their organization, find their work fulfilling, are committed to their teams, seek ways to improve their work, and plan to stay with the organization long-term. While the overall level of maturity is classified as Advanced, there is still room for improvement in certain areas,

such as team commitment. This indicates a high level of employee engagement, although there is potential for further improvement.

Table 37. *Level of Employees' Performance Based on Productivity*

Indicators	Mean	Interpretation
1. Accuracy: My work consistently meets quality standards.	3.24	Advanced
2. Resource Use: I use resources effectively.	3.40	Expert
3. Timeliness: I ensure prompt completion of tasks.	3.35	Expert
4. Goal Achievement: I reach many of my set goals.	3.31	Expert
5. Effectiveness: My work achieves the desired results.	3.45	Expert
Overall	3.35	Expert

Table 37 presents the weighted mean, descriptive equivalent, and verbal interpretation of employee performance based on Productivity. The weighted mean is 3.35, verbally interpreted as "Expert" level, which corresponds to exceptional mastery with deep engagement and outstanding productivity. The highest mean score, 3.45, was recorded for the fifth indicator, the effectiveness of achieving desired results, which is also interpreted as the "Expert" level. In contrast, the lowest mean score of 3.24 was observed for the first indicator, which measures the accuracy of consistently meeting quality standards of work and is verbally interpreted as an "Advanced" level.

Assessing employees' performance based on Productivity highlights a crucial aspect of organizational success. With an overall rating classified as "Expert," employees demonstrate a commendable level of productivity in their

roles. This reflects a strong sense of effectiveness in achieving organizational goals. However, a slight gap exists in maintaining consistent quality, as indicated by the difference between Effectiveness and Accuracy. While employees excel in delivering results, there is room for improvement in meeting quality standards. This variation suggests that organizations focused on effectiveness may see high productivity levels, but to ensure balanced performance, they may need to invest more in refining accuracy. Such disparities are common, as different performance dimensions may carry varying importance depending on organizational priorities. Several studies highlight the influence of organizational priorities to support the analysis of employee productivity, particularly the gap between effectiveness and accuracy. Research by Korn Ferry (2023) suggests that workplaces emphasizing flexibility and autonomy improve employee effectiveness but may decrease consistency and accuracy as employees focus on speed and output. This aligns with studies on performance dynamics, which indicate that effectiveness and accuracy can vary based on organizational structures and feedback mechanisms (Korn Ferry, 2023). Further support comes from studies on learning organizations, emphasizing that environments fostering continuous learning and collaboration are associated with higher productivity. MIT Sloan Management Review also emphasizes that organizations prioritizing employee learning opportunities tend to achieve higher productivity and quality. The research shows

that integrating continuous learning practices helps balance effectiveness and accuracy in performance (Collings & McMackin, 2021).

Overall, findings suggest that while organizations that prioritize maximizing effectiveness can achieve high productivity levels, it is also essential to implement strategies that enhance accuracy. Ongoing learning initiatives and a culture of continuous improvement are vital to ensure that employees consistently meet quality standards. Organizations can optimize overall performance and drive long-term success by fostering an environment that values both effectiveness and accuracy. Balancing these dimensions is crucial for maintaining high standards across all aspects of productivity.

Table 38. *Summary of Level of Employees' Performance in terms of Learning Ability, Time Management, Engagement, and Productivity*

Level of Employee's Performance	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation
Learning Ability	3.34	Expert
Time Management	3.30	Expert
Engagement	3.20	Advanced
Productivity	3.35	Expert
Overall	3.30	Expert

Table 38 summarizes employees' performance levels in terms of learning ability, time management, engagement, and productivity. A 3.30 overall weighted mean indicates that employees in this study have the level of performance of an "Expert" level, describing exceptional mastery with deep engagement and outstanding productivity.

Table 39. *Matrix of Emerging Themes of Employees' Performance*

Category	Codes	Themes
View on Learning Ability	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Enhancing Skills through Learning Platforms and Practical Application ▪ Fostering Self-Directed Learning, Critical Thinking, and Adaptability ▪ Building Agility and Collaborative Learning ▪ Comprehensive Programs for Skill Development ▪ Step-by-Step Guidance and Mentorship for Hands-On Technical Proficiency 	Theme 1: Upskilling and Continuous Improvement
View on Time Management	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Goals-based prioritization for Efficiency and Flexibility ▪ Task Management for Skill Improvement and Work-Life Balance ▪ Task Prioritization and Time-Blocking for Effective Problem Solving 	Theme 2: Prioritization, Tools, and Scheduling Techniques
View on Engagement	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Big Picture Focus for Organizational Pride and Future Outlook ▪ Reflecting on the Impact on Work Satisfaction ▪ Supportive and Committed Team ▪ Seeking Inspiration and Fostering Personal Commitment ▪ Celebrating Milestones for Team and Personal Pride ▪ Building a Supportive, Respectful Atmosphere ▪ Open Communication and Feedback for Growth 	Theme 3: Supportive Atmosphere, Growth Opportunities and Sense of Fulfillment
View on Productivity	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Streamlined Processes for Effective Resource Use ▪ Clear Planning for Timely Goal Achievement ▪ Efficient Execution and Accuracy ▪ Collaborative Teamwork for Enhanced Effectiveness 	Theme 4: Measurable Goals, Streamlined Processes, and Eliminate Distractions

Table 39 presents a comprehensive overview of the key themes and subthemes emerging as critical factors influencing employee performance, categorized into four primary areas: Learning Ability, Time Management, Engagement, and Productivity.

In the area of learning ability, employees increasingly recognize the importance of upskilling and continuous improvement, reflected in the demand for various learning resources, including upskilling programs, job certifications, and learning platforms. There is also a growing emphasis on practical application and self-directed learning through structured programs, step-by-step guidance, and hands-on experiences, with mentorship and collaborative learning emerging as valuable support mechanisms. Regarding Time Management, effective prioritization, tools, and scheduling techniques are crucial for employees to manage their time efficiently. This highlights the need for goals-based prioritization and task management strategies, such as task prioritization and time-blocking. In terms of Engagement, a supportive atmosphere, opportunities for growth, and a sense of fulfillment are essential for fostering employee involvement, emphasizing the importance of reflecting on impact, having a supportive team, seeking inspiration, and celebrating milestones, along with maintaining a respectful environment and effective communication and feedback. Finally, in Productivity, achieving measurable goals, streamlining processes, and eliminating distractions are key factors for improvement, underscoring the

necessity for clear planning, efficient execution, team collaboration, and documented work.

Overall, the emerging themes outlined in Table 26 provide valuable insights for organizations seeking to enhance employee performance. Organizations can create a conducive environment for employee growth, engagement, and overall success by addressing these themes and providing the necessary support and resources.

Theme 1: Upskilling and Continuous Improvement

In the area of Learning Ability, employees increasingly recognize the importance of upskilling and continuous improvement. This theme is reflected in the demand for various learning resources, including upskilling programs, job certifications, and learning platforms. Additionally, a growing emphasis is on practical application and self-directed learning through structured programs, step-by-step guidance, and hands-on experiences. Mentorship and collaborative learning are also becoming valuable support mechanisms in this context.

Employee A

A combination of well-structured onboarding programs and ongoing development workshops is most effective. These resources provide clear, step-by-step guidance and real-world applications that help me grasp new skills thoroughly.

Employee F

Regular practice and guidance from a mentor help me keep my skills up-to-date and useful for my daily tasks.

Employee H

Mahirap minsan, “do it” yourself dito. Learning by doing.

Employee Q

I learn best through a combination of hands-on practice and structured training. Access to detailed resources, like manuals or online tutorials, also plays a crucial role in helping me absorb new information.

According to the participants, effective employee development relies on structured onboarding programs and ongoing workshops, which provide clear, step-by-step guidance and real-world applications to help grasp new skills thoroughly. Regular practice and mentorship are essential for keeping skills up-to-date and applicable to daily tasks. One participant emphasized the value of “learning by doing,” indicating that practical experience is vital. Access to detailed resources, such as manuals or online tutorials, is crucial for helping employees absorb new information effectively.

Structured onboarding programs significantly enhance employee development by providing a clear learning and skill acquisition framework. This structured approach allows new employees to navigate their roles efficiently and

confidently, while ongoing workshops enable the continuous application of learned skills in a controlled environment. According to Forbes (2022), a study by the Brandon Hall Group for Glassdoor found that a strong onboarding process improved new hire retention by 82% and increased their confidence in performing job duties compared to those who did not receive structured guidance. Additionally, employees who participate in mentorship programs report higher levels of job satisfaction, which positively influences retention rates. (Forbes, 2022).

In addition, the participants' perspectives align with recent findings, emphasizing that effective employee development is multifaceted and incorporates structured programs and practical applications. By providing access to resources, consistent mentorship, technical proficiency acquisition, and real-world practice opportunities, organizations can ensure that their employees not only acquire but also retain and apply new skills efficiently. These elements create a supportive learning environment that encourages continuous professional growth.

Theme 2: Prioritization, Tools, and Scheduling Techniques

Effective prioritization, tools, and scheduling techniques are crucial for employees to manage their time efficiently. This theme highlights the need for

goals-based prioritization and task management strategies such as task prioritization and time-blocking.

Employee A

I begin by reviewing priorities and deadlines. Then, I set achievable goals for each task that help me maintain efficiency and stay on track.

Employee G

I prioritize tasks based on their deadlines and urgency. I often start with the low-hanging fruit to address simpler tasks quickly before moving on to more complex ones.

Employee K

I rely on techniques such as time-blocking, where I dedicate specific periods to different tasks, and the Pomodoro Technique, which helps me maintain focus by working in short, intense bursts followed by breaks.

Employee M

I manage tasks by their urgency and importance, starting with the most impactful ones. I use a physical planner and set reminders on my phone to stay organized and manage deadlines.

According to the majority of participants, effective time management hinges on using prioritization, appropriate tools, and scheduling techniques to ensure tasks are handled efficiently. This emphasizes the importance of goal-

oriented prioritization and task management strategies, such as task prioritization and time-blocking, which help employees focus on high-value activities, reduce distractions, and optimize their productivity.

A recent study supports the importance of prioritization and time management tools in enhancing employee productivity and job satisfaction. Effective prioritization strategies, such as time-blocking and task management, enable employees to focus on high-priority tasks, increasing efficiency and reducing stress. As highlighted by PsicoSmart (2024), a study conducted by the University of California, Berkeley, found that individuals who implemented time blocking in their daily routines reported a 30% increase in task completion rates. This structured approach allows individuals to concentrate on one task at a time, minimizing distractions and improving focus. Additionally, a survey conducted by Harvard Business Review revealed that 70% of 500 professionals felt more accomplished and in control of their day when utilizing time-blocking techniques. These findings underscore that structured time management techniques directly impact employee performance and well-being.

In addition, participants' insights align with current research, emphasizing the value of effective prioritization, scheduling techniques, and time management tools in the workplace. Employees can manage their workload more efficiently by adopting strategies like time-blocking and task prioritization, improving

productivity and overall job satisfaction. These tools help meet goals and promote a healthier work-life balance, reducing stress and enhancing performance.

Theme 3: Supportive Atmosphere, Growth Opportunities and Sense of Fulfillment

A supportive atmosphere, growth opportunities, and a sense of fulfillment are essential for fostering employee engagement. This theme emphasizes the importance of reflecting on impact, having a supportive team, seeking inspiration, and celebrating milestones. Additionally, a supportive and respectful atmosphere, along with effective communication and feedback, are crucial for maintaining high levels of engagement.

Employee K

I seek inspiration from my colleagues and engage in activities that recharge my energy, such as taking breaks or participating in team discussions.

Employee L

I can't think of a project I truly enjoyed; most feel like another task. I try to keep going, but staying motivated is tough when things get difficult.

Employee O

Always looking forward to celebrations and small milestones like product releases to market. Making the atmosphere less stressful by cracking some jokes during meetings.

Employee Q

I contribute to a positive work environment by being approachable and supportive. I try to communicate openly, offer help when needed, and participate in team-building activities to foster strong relationships with my colleagues.

According to the majority of the participants, when it comes to Engagement, a supportive atmosphere, opportunities for growth, and a sense of fulfillment are essential for fostering employee engagement. This theme highlights the importance of reflecting on impact, having a supportive team, seeking inspiration, and celebrating milestones. A respectful environment, effective communication, and feedback are crucial for maintaining high levels of engagement.

Recent research supports the participants' views on the importance of a supportive atmosphere and growth opportunities for fostering engagement. According to a study by the Society for Human Resource Management (2024), organizations with a high percentage of new employees often face challenges related to employee engagement and retention, which can affect overall productivity. The report emphasizes the importance of developing onboarding programs and mentorship initiatives that help new hires acclimate to company culture while creating pathways for professional growth. Furthermore, a survey by Gallup (2023) indicates that companies with effective mentorship programs experience higher employee satisfaction and retention rates, particularly among

younger employees seeking guidance and advancement opportunities. By fostering an environment that values knowledge sharing and professional development, organizations can enhance employee loyalty and maximize the potential of both new and experienced staff.

Moreover, fostering employee engagement requires more than just offering growth opportunities; it involves cultivating a supportive and respectful culture. By encouraging teamwork, providing regular feedback, celebrating achievements, and offering a sense of purpose, organizations can create an environment that promotes employee fulfillment, ultimately driving higher engagement and overall success.

Theme 4: Measurable Goals, Streamlined Processes, and Eliminate Distractions

In Productivity, achieving measurable goals, streamlining processes, and eliminating distractions are key factors for improvement. This theme emphasizes the necessity for clear planning, efficient execution, team collaboration, and documented work.

Employee I

I set clear, measurable objectives and break them down into manageable tasks with specific deadlines. Regularly updating my progress using project management software or task-tracking tools helps me stay on track.

Employee M

I track productivity through regular check-ins and reviewing completed tasks against set goals. I ensure quality by following established procedures and using checklists, and I manage speed by staying focused and organized.

Employee N

I set daily and weekly goals and track my progress with performance metrics. I evaluate my work, follow procedures, and try to automate repetitive tasks.

Employee Q

I track my productivity by setting clear daily and weekly goals and reviewing my progress regularly. I ensure high-quality work by double-checking my tasks and using checklists to avoid errors. To work quickly, I focus on efficiency, eliminating distractions, and leveraging tools that streamline repetitive tasks.

Recent studies support that setting measurable goals, streamlining processes, and reducing distractions are critical to improving productivity. A study by Harvard Business Review (2023) found that employees who set clear, measurable goals and track their progress regularly are more likely to meet their targets and maintain high performance. This is further supported by research from McKinsey & Company (2022), which emphasizes the importance of minimizing distractions and optimizing workflows to boost productivity. Effective planning,

structured processes, and collaboration foster a more organized and goal-oriented work environment, ensuring tasks are completed efficiently and on time.

In addition, achieving productivity in the workplace requires a multifaceted approach, focusing on measurable goals, effective use of tools, and minimizing distractions. By consistently applying these strategies, employees can improve their individual performance and contribute to a more efficient and collaborative team dynamic. Regularly assessing and refining these productivity methods is essential for sustaining high levels of performance and adapting to evolving work demands.

Quantitative Results

The instrument used to assess employees' performance in areas such as Learning Ability, Time Management, Engagement, and Productivity was developed based on the themes that emerged from participant interviews. The researcher integrated these qualitative themes with the theoretical framework to establish the primary sections and scales of the instrument. Table 26 presents an alignment of the theoretical framework, qualitative insights, and the instrument's dimensions, ensuring that the tool accurately reflects theoretical and practical considerations.

The Level of Organizations' Efficiency in terms of Finance, Operations, and Marketing

To thoroughly understand organizational efficiency, this analysis provides quantitative data on essential areas, including finance, operations, and marketing. The data is presented in a tabular format to aid analysis and interpretation.

Table 40. *Scales of Level of Organizations' Efficiency*

Scale	Limits	Indicator	Description
4	3.25 - 4.00	Exemplary	Outstanding efficiency marked by exceptional performance and innovation.
3	2.50 – 3.24	Advanced	Enhanced efficiency with optimized processes and personalized approaches.
2	1.75 – 2.49	Intermediate	Improved efficiency with effective management across all areas.
1	1.00 – 1.74	Basic or Unsure	Foundational efficiency with basic practices in finance, operations, and marketing.

Table 40 establishes a framework for evaluating organizational efficiency, categorizing it into four levels. At the highest level, "Exemplary" organizations demonstrate exceptional achievements characterized by optimized processes, personalized approaches, and a focus on innovation. "Advanced" organizations exhibit enhanced efficiency through effective management and well-defined strategies. "Intermediate" organizations demonstrate improved efficiency across various areas, while "Basic or Unsure" organizations may require foundational improvements in their financial, operational, and marketing practices.

Table 41. *Level of Organizations' Efficiency Based on Finance*

Indicators	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation
1. Budgeting: The organization's financial planning is well-managed.	2.92	Advanced
2. Revenue: Revenue has shown improvement compared to last year.	2.97	Advanced
3. Cost Control: The organization keeps costs under control.	3.02	Advanced
4. Investment Returns: Investments are doing well.	2.98	Advanced
5. Expenditures: The organization handles spending effectively.	2.92	Advanced
Overall	2.96	Advanced

Table 41 presents the weighted mean, descriptive equivalent, and verbal interpretation of organizational efficiency based on financial metrics. The weighted mean is 2.96, categorized as "Advanced," indicating that the organization has enhanced efficiency through optimized processes and personalized approaches. The Cost Control indicator, which reflects the organization's ability to manage expenses effectively, received the highest mean score of 3.02, also classified as "Advanced." Conversely, both the Budgeting and Expenditure indicators achieved the lowest mean score of 2.92 yet are still considered "Advanced."

Assessing organizational efficiency based on financial metrics highlights significant progress in enhancing financial processes. The overall rating reflects

substantial improvements, demonstrating effective expense management and strong financial discipline, which are critical for profitability and sustainability. According to Deloitte (2024), organizations that excel in cost control are better positioned to capitalize on growth opportunities and navigate economic uncertainties. Conversely, the Budgeting indicator received the lowest rating and was classified as "Advanced." Although this score indicates commendable financial planning, it reveals room for enhancement. Effective budgeting and expenditure should align resources with organizational goals and support financial stability. Gouedard (2024) emphasizes that organizations implementing robust budgeting frameworks and forecasting methods establish a strong foundation for long-term stability and growth by setting clear financial goals, tracking expenses meticulously, and ensuring expenditures align with business objectives.

Overall, the findings suggest that the organization is well-prepared and performing at a high level of financial efficiency. They suggest that the organization effectively manages financial planning, demonstrates revenue improvement, maintains cost control, makes sound investments, and handles expenditures judiciously. Such capabilities reflect a high level of maturity in financial efficiency within the organization.

Table 42. *Level of Organizations' Efficiency Based on Operations*

Indicators	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation
1. Daily Operations: The organization manages daily operations effectively.	3.23	Advanced
2. Workflow Efficiency: Processes are organized and efficient.	3.23	Advanced
3. Streamlining Workflows: Processes are optimized well.	3.15	Advanced
4. Communication: Internal communication runs smoothly	3.16	Advanced
5. Performance Metrics: Metrics like KRAs and KPIs are used effectively.	3.06	Advanced
Overall	3.17	Advanced

Table 42 presents the weighted mean, descriptive equivalent, and verbal interpretation of organizational efficiency based on operations. The weighted mean is 3.17, categorized as an "Advanced" level, indicating enhanced efficiency through optimized processes and personalized approaches. The highest mean score of 3.23 was achieved for the first two indicators: Daily Operations, which assesses the effectiveness of managing day-to-day activities, and Workflow Efficiency, which evaluates the organization and efficiency of processes. In contrast, the lowest mean score of 3.06 was noted for the fifth indicator, Performance Metrics, which examines the effective utilization of key result areas (KRAs) and key performance indicators (KPIs), also categorized as "Advanced."

The assessment of organizational efficiency based on operational metrics highlights significant progress in enhancing operational processes. The overall rating indicates that the organization has significantly improved its operational processes and efficiency. This implies that the organization excels in handling its daily tasks and has established streamlined workflows, contributing to increased productivity and reduced operational bottlenecks. As a result, you can get new products to market quicker or deliver projects in a shorter timeframe. This has many benefits, from delighting customers with your speedy service to stealing ahead of your competitors with a new product. In contrast, the fifth indicator, Performance Metrics, is also interpreted as Advanced. While this score reflects a commendable use of performance metrics, it indicates an opportunity for further improvement in effectively leveraging these metrics to drive performance and strategic decision-making. Research by Harvard Business School (2023) underscores the importance of utilizing key performance indicators (KPIs) to align organizational goals with operational execution and foster team accountability.

Overall, the findings suggest that the organization is well-prepared and performing at a high level in terms of operational efficiency. They suggest that organizations can manage daily operations effectively, have organized and efficient workflows, have streamlined processes, have smooth internal

communication, and use performance metrics effectively. Such capabilities reflect a strong maturity level in operational efficiency within the organization.

Table 43. *Level of Organizations' Efficiency Based on Marketing*

Indicators	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation
1. Audience Reach: Marketing effectively targets the right audience.	3.10	Advanced
2. Campaign Success: Campaigns successfully attract interest.	3.11	Advanced
3. Marketing Goals: Marketing supports organizational goals effectively.	3.11	Advanced
4. Department Collaboration: Marketing works well with other departments.	3.08	Advanced
5. Adaptation: The organization quickly adjusts to market changes.	3.12	Advanced
Overall	3.10	Advanced

Table 43 presents the weighted mean, descriptive equivalent, and verbal interpretation of organizational efficiency based on marketing metrics. The weighted mean is 3.10, categorized as "Advanced," reflecting enhanced efficiency through optimized processes and personalized approaches. The highest mean score of 3.12 was achieved for the fifth indicator, Adaptation, which assesses the organization's ability to quickly adjust to market changes. In contrast, the lowest mean score of 3.08 was recorded for the fourth indicator, Department Collaboration, which evaluates how well marketing collaborates with other departments; this indicator is also classified as "Advanced."

Assessing organizational efficiency based on marketing highlights significant progress in the organization's marketing strategies and execution, effectively positioning it within the marketplace. The Adaptation indicator received the highest rating, demonstrating the organization's ability to swiftly adjust to market changes. In contrast, the Audience Reach indicator, which evaluates the effectiveness of marketing in targeting the right audience, received the lowest score. While this reflects strong marketing efforts, it also indicates an opportunity for improvement to maximize effectiveness and streamline processes. According to the HubSpot State of Marketing Report (2023), agility in adapting marketing strategies is crucial for maintaining a competitive edge. The report emphasizes that organizations that adjust their marketing in response to emerging trends are more likely to succeed. It underscores the significance of audience targeting in enhancing overall marketing effectiveness. (HubSpot, 2023).

Overall, the findings suggest that the organization is well-prepared and operates at a high level of marketing efficiency. This indicates that the organization can effectively target the right audience, execute successful campaigns, align marketing efforts with overarching organizational goals, collaborate effectively with other departments, and adapt swiftly to market changes. Such capabilities reflect a strong maturity level in marketing efficiency within the organization.

Table 44. *Summary of Level of Organizations' Efficiency in terms of Financial, Operations, and Marketing*

Organizations' Efficiency	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation
Financial	2.96	Advanced
Time Management	3.17	Advanced
Engagement	3.10	Advanced
Overall	3.08	Advanced

Table 44 summarizes the level of organizations' efficiency in terms of financial, operations, and marketing. The 3.08 overall weighted mean indicates that organizations in this study have a maturity level equivalent to "Advanced," which describes enhanced efficiency with optimized processes and personalized approaches.

Table 45. *Matrix of Emerging Themes of Organizational Efficiency*

Category	Codes	Themes and Subthemes
View on Financial Performance	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Revenue Growth and Investment Returns ▪ Effective Budgeting and Expenditure Management ▪ Cost Control for Improved Profitability 	Theme 1: Cash Flow Management and Revenue Growth
View on Operational Performance	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Streamlined and Automated Workflows for Daily Operations ▪ Lean Practices and Workflow Efficiency for Continuous Improvement ▪ Clear Procedures and Communication for Effective Coordination ▪ Performance Metrics and HR Enhancements for Strong Leadership ▪ Technology Upgrades and Shared Objectives in Cross-Functional Projects 	Theme 2: Lean Management, Automated Workflows and Technology Upgrades
View on Marketing	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Targeted Campaigns for Audience Reach and Marketing Goals ▪ Data-driven strategies and Campaign Success ▪ Effective Outreach and Content Creation through Collaboration ▪ Digital Advertising and Adaptation to Market Trends ▪ Strong Leadership and Coordination for Improvement 	Theme 3: Targeted and Data-Driven Campaigns

Table 45 presents a comprehensive overview of key themes and subthemes driving organizational efficiency. These themes are categorized into

three primary perspectives: Financial Performance, Operational Performance, and Marketing.

Financial Performance focuses on strategies that directly impact an organization's bottom line. This includes revenue growth, investment returns, and cost control. Effective budgeting and expenditure management are crucial to maintaining profitability. Operational Performance highlights the importance of streamlined processes and efficient workflows. Automation and lean practices are key to reducing operational costs and improving productivity. Clear communication and procedures ensure smooth coordination among teams. Marketing emphasizes the need for targeted campaigns and data-driven strategies. Effective outreach and content creation are essential for building brand awareness and driving customer engagement. Digital advertising and adaptation to market trends are critical for success in today's competitive landscape.

Cross-cutting themes like strong leadership and coordination are essential for driving improvement across all areas of the organization. Technology upgrades and shared objectives among teams are critical for achieving organizational efficiency goals. This analysis provides valuable insights into the emerging trends shaping organizational efficiency. Organizations can improve their financial performance, operational efficiency, and marketing effectiveness by focusing on these key themes and subthemes.

Theme 1: Cash Flow Management and Revenue Growth

This theme focuses on ways to improve profitability. It emphasizes increasing revenue through effective sales and marketing efforts, optimizing investments for maximum return, implementing effective budgeting practices to allocate resources efficiently, managing expenditures to control costs, and implementing cost control measures to improve overall profitability.

Employee A

I think it [the company] is doing well. It is publicly available that there will be nearly 11% net revenue growth in 2023, up slightly from 10.2% last year. The company has released its 45th annual clarity architecture and engineering industry study, revealing increased industry stability and optimism about future growth based on a survey of more than 650 firms.

Employee D

There are some parts of which they [upper management] are transparent about, like giving bonuses based on the company's yearly EBITDA. However, the majority of it, as most other companies do, is somewhat confidential, and only the upper management has visibility. During CoVid – From 4 floors being leased down to two floors, the company saves a lot on rental costs since the majority of its workforce is Working From Home/remotely.

Employee L

I'm not closely involved with financial management, but I know the company focused on cost-cutting measures during the pandemic to maintain financial stability. While I don't have specific examples, I understand that the company implemented cost-cutting during the pandemic, such as reducing non-essential expenses and optimizing operations. I don't have information on the company's financial issues, but I know managing costs and recovering from the pandemic have been significant challenges.

According to the participants, organizational efficiency is often measured by how well an organization manages its financial performance, particularly through revenue growth, budgeting, and cost control. Effective budgeting and expenditure management allow organizations to allocate resources wisely, ensuring that funds are directed toward high-impact areas that drive revenue.

Additionally, cost control practices help improve profitability by minimizing unnecessary expenditures and maximizing returns on investment. A comprehensive approach to cash flow management is essential, as it directly influences revenue growth and the organization's overall financial health. For instance, a study by Arojo et al. (2024) found a significant positive relationship between cash flow management and firm performance, highlighting the

importance of efficient cash flow management in achieving organizational success.

Understanding the interplay between financial performance, budgeting, and cost control is crucial for organizations seeking to enhance their efficiency. The themes identified in the matrix of emerging organizational efficiency highlight the importance of cash flow management and revenue growth as critical drivers of profitability. By prioritizing these factors, organizations can position themselves for success in an increasingly competitive landscape, ensuring they are well-equipped to navigate challenges while maximizing their financial potential.

Theme 2: Lean Management, Automated Workflows and Technology Upgrades

This theme centers on streamlining processes, improving efficiency, and leveraging technology. It involves implementing lean practices to eliminate waste and optimize daily operations, automating workflows to reduce manual effort and improve accuracy, establishing clear procedures and communication channels to ensure smooth operations, utilizing performance metrics to track progress and identify areas for improvement, and fostering strong leadership to drive organizational change and innovation.

Employee B

Our company's processes are designed with lean management principles in mind, which help minimize waste and optimize resources. This focus on efficiency allows us to align our operations closely with our strategic goals, making it easier to meet our objectives.

Employee N

There are tedious and inefficient processes, especially during payroll, that don't help us meet our goals. There have been a few improvements, but they're usually not enough to make a significant difference. It's hard to say; we sometimes face delays and miscommunications.

Employee O

The company's processes generally help in reaching its goals, but there's room for improvement, especially when filing leaves or requesting benefits. Apart from having efficient operations, from employee onboarding to work assignments, our processes effectively fulfill their purpose. People here are approachable and supportive.

Employee Q

The company has made several operational improvements, such as adopting new project management tools and refining workflows, contributing to better efficiency and productivity. The company's success in operations is largely

due to a strong focus on continuous improvement, effective resource allocation, and a culture that encourages innovation and teamwork.

According to the participants, operational performance is a fundamental aspect of organizational efficiency, reflecting how well an organization manages its daily operations to meet its objectives. Core components of operational performance include streamlined and automated workflows, which substantially enhance productivity by reducing manual effort, minimizing errors, and increasing speed and accuracy in task completion. Lean practices, centered on workflow efficiency and continuous improvement, further contribute to operational excellence by eliminating waste, optimizing resources, and creating value-added processes. In addition to workflow enhancements, clear and standardized procedures ensure consistency across tasks, while effective communication channels foster coordination among team members. These elements help create an environment where each team member is aligned with the organization's mission and goals, leading to improved performance across departments.

Supporting this perspective, research by Tortorella et al. (2021) demonstrates that bundles of Lean automation practices and principles have a positive and significant relationship with operational performance. This study highlights the tangible benefits of lean management and technological

advancements in boosting operational efficiency. Such upgrades enable companies to adapt to rapidly changing environments and improve employee satisfaction and productivity. Additionally, a study highlighted in Harvard Business Review (2023) found that nearly 80% of employees reported that automation allowed them more time to build deeper relationships with customers and stakeholders, engage in challenging projects, and acquire new skills. This evidence underscores the broader advantages of operational efficiency in enhancing workforce engagement and adaptability.

The focus on operational performance underscores the critical role of lean management, automated workflows, and technology upgrades in promoting organizational efficiency and adaptability. By prioritizing these elements, organizations can develop a more agile and responsive operational framework that meets the market's current demands while positioning themselves for future success. Emphasizing clear procedures, effective communication, and a culture of strong leadership ensures that organizations are well-prepared to achieve their strategic goals, improve resilience, and maintain a competitive edge in their respective industries.

Theme 3: Targeted and Data-Driven Campaigns

This theme highlights the importance of targeted campaigns and data-driven strategies. It focuses on leveraging digital advertising to reach a wider

audience, adapting to market trends to stay competitive, fostering collaboration between marketing and sales teams to ensure alignment, and utilizing data analytics to measure campaign performance and make data-driven decisions. Strong leadership and coordination are essential to drive improvement and ensure success in marketing efforts.

Employee F

Participation in industry conferences and webinars allows the company to engage with a relevant audience and showcase its solutions directly to professionals in their target markets. Using customer data and performance metrics, the company refines its marketing strategies to ensure messages are reaching the right people and making adjustments based on campaign performance. But sometimes the challenge is Market saturation.

Employee I

I believe the company's marketing efforts effectively reach the right audience, as evidenced by the successful acquisition of new projects. This suggests that our marketing strategies are well-targeted and resonate with potential clients. The ability to attract and secure projects indicates that our messaging and outreach are effectively aligned with the needs and interests of our target market.

Employee O

I think our company's marketing efforts are effective in reaching the right audience, particularly in the US market. We highlight our competitive advantage of offering quality services at a lower cost due to our location in the Philippines, which aligns well with market expectations.

Marketing is crucial in shaping an organization's visibility and engagement with its target audience. The effectiveness of marketing efforts can be significantly enhanced through targeted campaigns focusing on audience reach and aligning with specific marketing goals. Organizations can analyze consumer behavior and preferences by employing data-driven strategies, enabling them to craft campaigns that resonate with their audience. Additionally, effective outreach and collaborative content creation foster a sense of community and engagement, ensuring that the messaging is relevant and impactful. Embracing digital advertising allows businesses to adapt to rapidly changing market trends, maximizing their reach and influence.

Successful marketing relies on effective outreach and collaboration, which help build community and engagement. Organizations make their messaging more relevant by involving their audience through user-generated content and interactive campaigns. This customer-focused approach keeps campaigns adaptable and meaningful across different platforms. Additionally,

digital advertising channels like social media and search engines allow organizations to quickly respond to market changes, maximizing their reach and impact. Current research supports the notion that targeted, data-driven campaigns are instrumental to achieving marketing success and sustained competitive advantage. As Camilleri (2020) observes, firms with detailed insights into consumer data can customize every aspect of their engagement, from tailored advertising to personalized product recommendations, meeting specific customer needs and driving greater satisfaction. This customization creates a distinct competitive edge as consumers increasingly gravitate toward brands that deliver relevant, meaningful, and personal experiences.

The theme related to marketing underscores the importance of targeted and data-driven campaigns in enhancing organizational performance. Organizations can create more effective marketing strategies that resonate with consumers by focusing on audience reach and adapting to market trends. Collaboration and strong leadership play pivotal roles in achieving marketing goals and fostering a culture of innovation and responsiveness. As organizations navigate an ever-evolving landscape, prioritizing these elements will be key to sustaining competitive advantage and driving long-term success.

Quantitative Results

The instrument used to assess an organization's efficiency in Financial, Operations, and Marketing areas was developed based on the themes from participant interviews. The researcher integrated these qualitative themes with the theoretical framework to establish the primary sections and scales of the instrument. Table 32 presents an alignment of the theoretical framework, qualitative insights, and the instrument's dimensions, ensuring that the tool accurately reflects theoretical and practical considerations.

The Level of Impact of Maturity Level on Employees' Performance in terms of Learning Ability, Time Management, Engagement, and Productivity

To understand the impact of maturity level on employees' performance, this analysis presents quantitative data on key areas: learning ability, time management, engagement, and productivity. The information is organized in a tabular form to facilitate analysis and interpretation.

Table 46. *Scales of Impact of Maturity Level on Employees' Performance*

Scale	Limits	Indicator	Description
4	3.25 - 4.00	Very High Impact	Current maturity has a very high impact on employees.
3	2.50 – 3.24	High Impact	Current maturity has a significant impact on employees.
2	1.75 – 2.49	Low Impact	Current maturity has a low impact on employees.
1	1.00 – 1.74	No Impact at all	Current maturity has no impact at all.

Table 46 describes a four-point scale measuring how an organization's maturity level affects employee performance. At the Very High Impact level, mature practices and a supportive culture greatly enhance employee performance. The High Impact level reflects a strong positive influence, where organizational maturity boosts development, engagement, and productivity. Low-impact organizations show limited or inconsistent effects, as lower maturity may hinder employee growth and satisfaction. In organizations with No Impact, maturity level doesn't influence performance, often due to unclear practices or a stagnant culture. This scale helps leaders understand how their organization's maturity impacts employees and guides decisions on development and improvements.

Table 47. *Level of Impact of Maturity Based on Employees' Learning Ability*

Indicators	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation
1. Skill Development: Boosts my skill development.	3.50	Very High
2. Learning Agility: Speeds up my learning and application of new skills.	3.44	Very High
3. Problem-solving: Enhances my effectiveness in solving problems.	3.50	Very High
4. Adaptability: Improves my ability to adapt to changes.	3.47	Very High
5. Continuous Improvement: Supports ongoing growth in my skills.	3.53	Very High
Overall	3.49	Very High

Table 47 presents the weighted mean, descriptive equivalent, and verbal interpretation of the impact of maturity on employees' Learning Ability. The

overall weighted mean is 3.49, with a verbal interpretation of a "Very High" impact, indicating that maturity level has a very high impact on employees' learning ability. Notably, the fifth indicator, continuous improvement, which supports ongoing growth in employee skills, received the highest mean score of 3.53, which is interpreted as a "Very high" impact. Conversely, the second indicator, Learning Agility, which measures the speeds of employee learning and application of new skills, achieved the lowest mean score of 3.44 yet still falls within the "Very High" impact category. This suggests that while employees exhibit a strong capacity for learning and growth, there are subtle differences in how various aspects of learning ability are perceived and utilized within the organization.

The assessment of the impact of maturity on employees' Learning Ability indicates that current maturity has a very high impact on employees, with a verbal interpretation of "Very High" impact. This score reflects a strong commitment to creating a learning environment that supports employee development. The fifth indicator, Continuous Improvement, received the highest rating, suggesting that employees perceive a robust support system for ongoing learning and skill enhancement, which is crucial in today's rapidly evolving workplace. Emphasizing continuous improvement fosters individual growth and enhances the organization's overall adaptability and resilience. Conversely, the second indicator, Learning Agility, while still interpreted as "Very High" impact,

indicates slightly less impact than Continuous Improvement. This suggests that although employees demonstrate a good capacity for quickly learning and applying new skills, there remains an opportunity for further enhancement in this area. Research by the Association for Talent Development (2024) highlights that organizations focused on learning agility tend to outperform their peers in innovation and adaptability, emphasizing the importance of nurturing this trait within the workforce. Additionally, Radu (2023) emphasized that organizations fostering a continuous learning culture improve employee engagement and drive overall organizational performance.

Overall, the findings suggest that the level of maturity and its impact on employees' learning ability significantly enhance their performance. Improved maturity fosters skill development, accelerates learning agility, increases problem-solving effectiveness, enhances adaptability, and supports ongoing growth. Such an environment indicates that the organization's maturity level in these areas is highly beneficial for employees' professional development.

Table 48. *Level of Impact of Maturity Based on Employees' Time Management*

Indicators	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation
1. Task Completion: Enhances my efficiency in completing tasks.	3.48	Very High
2. Skill Improvement: Improves my time management abilities.	3.44	Very High
3. Flexibility: Increases my adaptability to changing situations.	3.49	Very High
4. Overcoming Roadblocks: Helps me overcome obstacles more effectively.	3.36	Very High
5. Work-Life Balance: Contributes to a better work-life balance.	3.37	Very High
Overall	3.43	Very High

Table 48 presents the weighted mean, descriptive equivalent, and verbal interpretation of the impact of maturity on employees' time management. The overall weighted mean is 3.43, indicating that maturity level has a "Very High" impact on employees' time management. This score reflects the organization's strong commitment to fostering effective time management practices. Notably, the third indicator, Flexibility, which measures employees' adaptability to changing situations, achieved the highest mean score of 3.49, signifying a "Very High" level of impact. In contrast, the lowest mean score of 3.36 was recorded for the fourth indicator, Overcoming Roadblocks, which assesses how effectively employees can navigate obstacles. Despite being the lowest score, this indicator still reflects a "Very High" level.

The assessment of the impact of maturity on employees' time management indicates that current maturity has a very high impact. This underscores the organization's commitment to enhancing time management practices, which are essential for optimizing productivity and achieving organizational goals. The third indicator, Task Completion, achieved the highest mean score, suggesting that employees' flexibility significantly increases their adaptability to changing situations. Harvard Business Review (2021) emphasizes that organizations prioritizing flexibility in their operations tend to experience improved employee adaptability, resulting in better overall performance. In contrast, the fourth indicator, Overcoming Roadblocks, received the lowest mean score, yet it is still interpreted as very high impact. This outcome indicates a slightly lower impact than Flexibility, highlighting that while employees are generally well-equipped to handle challenges, there remains room for improvement in strategies and resources that can further support them in overcoming obstacles. A study by Robinson, Yan, and Jiang (2024) suggests that organizations that invest in comprehensive support systems for employees facing obstacles see enhanced resilience and problem-solving capabilities, thereby improving overall effectiveness.

Overall, the findings suggest that the level of maturity and its impact on employees' time management significantly enhance their performance. A higher maturity level improves employees' task completion efficiency, enhances their

time management abilities, increases their flexibility, and helps them overcome obstacles more effectively, all of which contribute to a better work-life balance. This implies that the organization’s maturity level in these areas is highly beneficial for employees’ overall time management effectiveness.

Table 49. *Level of Impact of Maturity Based on Employees’ Engagement*

Indicators	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation
1. Job Satisfaction: Boosts my satisfaction and motivation in my role.	3.34	Very High
2. Enthusiasm: Increases my passion and enthusiasm for my job.	3.38	Very High
3. Departmental Engagement: Enhances my contribution to team goals.	3.32	Very High
4. Long-Term Dedication: Strengthens my commitment to the organization.	3.24	High
5. Net Promoter Score (e-NPS): Raises my likelihood of recommending my organization to others	3.15	High
Overall	3.29	Very High

Table 49 presents the weighted mean, descriptive equivalent, and verbal interpretation regarding the impact of maturity on employees’ engagement. The overall weighted mean is 3.29, indicating that maturity level has a “Very High” impact on employees’ engagement. Among the assessed indicators, the second indicator, Enthusiasm, which reflects employees’ passion and enthusiasm for their jobs, achieved the highest mean score of 3.38, interpreted as “Very High.”

In contrast, the fifth indicator, Net Promoter Score (e-NPS), which measures employees' likelihood of recommending their organization to others, received the lowest mean score of 3.15, which can be interpreted as "High" in maturity level.

The assessment of the impact of maturity on employees' engagement indicates that current maturity has a very high impact. This reflects a strong organizational commitment to fostering employee engagement, which is critical for maintaining a motivated and productive workforce. The second indicator, Enthusiasm, achieved the highest mean rating, suggesting that employees feel a deep passion and enthusiasm for their work, which is essential for driving innovation and productivity (Deepalakshmi, Tiwari, Baruah, Seth, & Bisht, 2024). Conversely, the fifth indicator, the Net Promoter Score (e-NPS), which measures the likelihood of recommending their organization to others, received the lowest rating and was interpreted as having a high impact. This indicates that while employees are generally inclined to recommend their organization, there remains an opportunity to improve the overall employee experience (Gallup, 2024).

Overall, the findings indicate that the level of maturity and its impact on employee engagement significantly enhance performance. Higher maturity levels boost job satisfaction and motivation, increase enthusiasm, and strengthen commitment to organizational goals. Employees are more likely to contribute positively to team objectives and recommend their organization to others,

highlighting the crucial role of maturity in fostering a productive work environment.

Table 50. *Level of Impact of Maturity Based on Employees' Productivity*

Indicators	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation
1. Timely Deliverables: Improves my consistency in meeting deadlines.	3.54	Very High
2. Work Quality: Enhances the accuracy and quality of my work.	3.59	Very High
3. Resource Utilization: Increases my efficiency in using resources.	3.48	Very High
4. Goal Achievement: Helps me achieve my target goals more effectively.	3.53	Very High
5. Desired Outcomes: Boosts my ability to achieve the desired results.	3.48	Very High
Overall	3.53	Very High

Table 50 presents the weighted mean, descriptive equivalent, and verbal interpretation regarding the impact of maturity on employees' productivity. The overall weighted mean is 3.53, indicating that maturity level has a "Very High" impact on employees' productivity. This score reflects a strong organizational commitment to enhancing productivity among staff. Notably, the second indicator, Work Quality, which evaluates the accuracy and quality of employees' work, achieved the highest mean score of 3.59, also categorized as "Very High." In contrast, the third and fifth indicators, Resource Utilization and Desired Outcomes, received slightly lower mean scores of 3.48. However, these scores

still reflect a “Very High” level, indicating that while there is a solid foundation for productivity, there may be opportunities to further optimize resource utilization and align outcomes with organizational goals.

The assessment of the impact of maturity on employees’ productivity indicates that current maturity has a very high impact, reflecting a strong alignment between the organization’s maturity level and employee productivity. The second indicator, Work Quality, achieved the highest rating, suggesting that employees feel empowered to produce high-quality work, which is essential for meeting organizational standards and enhancing customer satisfaction. A study by Zeer, Ajouz, and Salahat (2023) supports this notion, demonstrating that organizations prioritizing quality and employee empowerment often experience significant improvements in productivity and overall performance. Conversely, the third and fifth indicators, Resource Utilization and Desired Outcomes, received slightly lower ratings, indicating areas that could benefit from improvement. Efficient resource utilization is crucial for maximizing productivity. According to OrangeScrum (2024), effective resource management encompasses a range of activities to optimize the use of available resources to achieve objectives. This highlights the importance of refining resource management strategies to enhance productivity outcomes.

Overall, the findings indicate a strong connection between the level of maturity and its impact on employees’ productivity, which ultimately enhances

performance. They suggest that higher maturity levels could lead to improved consistency in meeting deadlines, greater accuracy and quality of work, increased efficiency in resource utilization, more effective achievement of target goals, and a heightened capacity to attain desired results. This implies that an organization's maturity in these areas is crucial in boosting productivity.

Table 51. *Summary of Level of Impact of Maturity Level on Employees' Performance in terms of Learning Ability, Time Management, Engagement, and Productivity*

Impact of Maturity	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation
Learning Ability	3.49	Very High
Time Management	3.43	Very High
Engagement	3.29	Very High
Productivity	3.53	Very High
Overall	3.43	Very High

Table 51 shows a summary of the impact of maturity on employees' performance in terms of learning ability, time management, engagement, and productivity. The 3.43 overall weighted mean indicates that the level of maturity impact on employees' performance in this study is equivalent to "Very High," describing current maturity's very high impact on employees.

The Level of Impact of Maturity Level on Organizations' Efficiency in terms of Financial, Operations, and Marketing

This analysis provides quantitative data on essential areas, including finance, operations, and marketing, in a tabular format to aid in analysis and

interpretation and to achieve a thorough understanding of the level of impact of digital maturity on organizational efficiency.

Table 52. *Scales of Impact of Maturity Level on Organizations' Efficiency*

Arbitrary Scale	Limits	Indicator	Description
4	3.25 - 4.00	Very High Impact	Current maturity has a very high impact on the organization.
3	2.50 – 3.24	High Impact	Current maturity has a significant impact on the organization.
2	1.75 – 2.49	Low Impact	Current maturity has a low impact on the organization.
1	1.00 – 1.74	No Impact at all	Current maturity has no impact at all.

Table 52 outlines a four-point scale that measures how an organization's maturity level affects its efficiency. At the Very High Impact level, mature practices and streamlined processes greatly improve operational performance. The High Impact level shows a strong positive effect, where maturity helps optimize processes, resource use, and decision-making. Low-impact organizations see limited benefits, as lower maturity may reduce effectiveness and agility. For organizations with No Impact, maturity has no noticeable effect on efficiency, often due to unclear practices or misaligned goals. This scale helps leaders understand how maturity initiatives can enhance efficiency and guide decisions on organizational improvements.

Table 53. *Impact of Maturity based on Organizations' Financial Performance*

Indicators	Mean	Interpretation
1. Budget Efficiency: Improves accuracy and timeliness in budgeting.	3.17	High
2. Financial Tracking: Enhances monitoring and analysis of financial performance.	3.17	High
3. Financial Metrics: Enhances financial ratios and compensation metrics.	3.15	High
4. Revenue Growth: Supports consistent revenue increases over time.	3.12	High
5. Profit Margins: Drives higher and more sustainable profit.	3.16	High
Overall	3.15	High

Table 53 presents the weighted mean, descriptive equivalent, and verbal interpretation of the impact of maturity on organizations' financial performance. The overall weighted mean is 3.15, which is categorized as a "High" impact, indicating that the level of maturity significantly impacts the organization's financial performance. Notably, the first and second indicators, budget efficiency and financial tracking, achieved the highest mean score of 3.17, reflecting a "High" impact. In contrast, the fourth indicator, revenue growth, which measures the organization's capacity for consistent revenue increases over time, received the lowest mean score of 3.12; however, this score is still categorized as a "High" impact.

The assessment of the impact of maturity on an organization's financial performance indicates that current maturity plays an important part. This suggests that the organization effectively leverages its maturity across various domains to

enhance financial outcomes. The first and second indicators, Budget Efficiency and Financial Tracking, received the highest mean ratings, indicating that the organization has established robust financial management practices. These practices contribute to more accurate budgeting and effective monitoring of financial performance. Mahroqi and Matriano (2021) note that organizations with strong budgetary controls tend to exhibit superior financial performance. In contrast, while also categorized as High, the fourth indicator, Revenue Growth, received a slightly lower mean score than the others. This still signifies that the organization effectively supports revenue growth, an essential component of long-term sustainability and profitability. Ochuodho and Ngaba (2020) emphasize that effective financial tracking is directly associated with improved revenue generation strategies, underscoring the importance of continuous improvement in this area.

Overall, the findings suggest that the level of maturity and its impact on an organization's financial performance are closely linked to overall organizational efficiency. They suggest that higher maturity levels could improve budgeting accuracy and timeliness, enhance financial monitoring and analysis, refine financial metrics, support consistent revenue growth, and drive higher, more sustainable profits. This indicates that the organization's maturity level significantly benefits its financial performance.

Table 54. *Impact of Maturity based on Organizations' Operations*

Indicators	Mean	Verbal Interpretation
1. Operational Efficiency: Enhances daily operations and resource use.	3.46	Very High
2. Workflow Optimization: Streamlines processes for greater efficiency.	3.38	Very High
3. Performance Metrics: Improves tracking and use of KPIs and KRAs.	3.33	Very High
4. Communication: Enhances internal communication channels.	3.35	Very High
5. Departmental Collaboration: Strengthens coordination across departments.	3.36	Very High
Overall	3.38	Very High

Table 54 presents the weighted mean, descriptive equivalent, and verbal interpretation regarding the impact of maturity on organizational operations. The weighted mean is 3.38 with a verbal interpretation of “Very High” impact, indicating that level of maturity has a very high impact on organizations’ operations. Among the indicators, operational efficiency, which refers to improvements in daily operations and resource utilization, achieved the highest mean score of 3.46, which is interpreted as a “Very High” impact. In contrast, the lowest mean score of 3.33 was recorded for Performance Metrics, which evaluates the organization's ability to track and use key performance indicators (KPIs) and key result areas (KRAs). Despite being the lowest, it is still categorized as having a “Very High” impact.

The assessment of the role of maturity in an organization's operational performance highlights that current maturity is important in enhancing overall organizational efficiency. This indicates that the organization has successfully integrated various operational practices to improve efficiency. The highest-rated indicator, Operational Efficiency, shows that the organization optimizes daily operations and resource use. According to Harvard Business Review (2023), measuring a business's performance is essential for long-term success, as it allows organizations to make informed decisions, improve processes, and establish accountability in the workplace. However, the third indicator, Performance Metrics, received the lowest rating, implying that while the organization is proficient in tracking and utilizing key performance indicators (KPIs), there is room for further improvement. Sultan (2022) suggests that organizations that effectively implement KPIs and key result areas (KRAs) can enhance decision-making processes, leading to better performance outcomes.

The findings indicate that the organization's maturity level is important in enhancing operational performance and is closely tied to overall organizational efficiency. Maintaining a higher maturity level contributes to improved operational efficiency, streamlined processes, and optimized performance metrics. These elements demonstrate that the organization's maturity is advantageous for driving operational efficiency and improving department performance outcomes.

Table 55. *Impact of Maturity based on Organizations' Marketing Performance*

Indicators	Mean	Interpretation
1. Marketing Alignment: Aligns marketing well with organizational goals.	3.46	Very High
2. Campaign Efficiency: Boosts the effectiveness of generating leads/sales.	3.38	Very High
3. Audience Reach: Enhances the ability to engage the right audience.	3.33	High
4. Market Responsiveness: Enhances the ability to adapt to market trends.	3.35	Very High
5. Department Collaboration: Enhances coordination with other departments.	3.36	High
Overall	3.38	Very High

Table 55 presents the weighted mean, descriptive equivalent, and verbal interpretation regarding the impact of maturity on organizations' marketing performance. The overall weighted mean is 3.38, with a verbal interpretation of a “Very High” impact, indicating that level of maturity has a very high impact on organizations' marketing performance. Notably, the first indicator, marketing alignment, which assesses how well marketing aligns with organizational goals, received the highest mean score of 3.46, also categorized as a “Very High” impact. Conversely, the third indicator, audience reach, which measures the organization's ability to engage the right audience, recorded the lowest mean score of 3.33; however, this score is still interpreted as a “High” impact.

The assessment of the role of maturity in an organization's marketing efficacy highlights that current maturity significantly enhances overall

organizational efficiency, indicating that digital transformation is well-embedded within the organization. This reflects a strong alignment between the organization's marketing efforts and overall goals, leading to improved performance. The first indicator, Marketing Alignment, received the highest rating, suggesting that the organization excels at ensuring its marketing strategies align with broader organizational objectives, which is crucial for optimizing resource use and driving success. A report by Davis (2024) emphasizes that companies with well-aligned marketing strategies typically experience faster growth and better customer retention rates. Conversely, the lowest mean score was observed in the third indicator, Audience Reach, indicating that while the organization effectively engages its target audience, there remains room for improvement in optimizing audience engagement. According to Ramotion (2024), brands that consistently refine their audience engagement strategies see higher conversion rates and improved brand loyalty.

The findings suggest that the organization's maturity level is important in enhancing marketing efficacy and is closely linked to overall organizational efficiency. Maintaining a very high maturity level aligns marketing strategies with organizational goals, increases the effectiveness of lead and sales generation, and enhances the ability to engage the right audience. This indicates that the organization's maturity in these areas is highly beneficial for improving marketing performance.

Table 56. *Summary of Impact of Maturity Level on Organizations' Efficiency in terms of Financial, Operations, and Marketing*

Impact of Maturity	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation
Financial	3.15	High
Operational	3.38	Very High
Marketing	3.26	Very High
Overall	3.26	Very High

Table 56 provides a comprehensive summary of the impact of maturity level on organizations' efficiency across three critical dimensions: financial performance, operational processes, and marketing effectiveness. The overall weighted mean of 3.26 underscores that the impact of maturity level on organizational efficiency in this study is categorized as "Very High." This indicates that the current maturity level has a profound and significant impact on various organizational functions, highlighting its vital role in enhancing overall performance and sustainability.

The Significant Difference in the level of Respondents' Maturity and their Demographic Variables

This section provides an in-depth analysis of the significant differences in maturity levels among respondents concerning various demographic variables, including age, educational attainment, job level, and years of tenure within the organization. By exploring these factors, the study aims to uncover how demographic attributes impact maturity levels, offering valuable insights into patterns and trends that may vary across different respondent groups.

Table 57. *Significant Difference in the Level of Digital Maturity when Grouped According to Age Group*

Category	Age	Mean Rank	p-value	Decision on H ₀	Interpretation
Level of Digital Maturity	18 - 27	172.27	0.201	Accept	Not Significant
	28 - 37	170.31			
	38 - 47	155.31			
	48 - Above	112.89			
Level of Employees' Performance	18 - 27	151.99	0.217	Accept	Not Significant
	28 - 37	168.97			
	38 - 47	170.17			
	48 - Above	113.33			
Level of Organizations' Efficiency	18 - 27	172.87	0.292	Accept	Not Significant
	28 - 37	171.09			
	38 - 47	150.66			
	48 - Above	147.50			

Legend: Reject H₀ if the p-value is $\leq \alpha$ (0.05).

The significance test on the level of digital maturity, when grouped according to age group, obtained 0.201, which is greater than the 0.05 level of significance set for the study. Thus, the null hypothesis is accepted. This means that regardless of the employee's age group, the maturity will not change from one level to another. Hence, the number of employees, when grouped according to their age group, will not impact whatever digital maturity level of the business technology company they are currently connected with.

Table 58. *Significant Difference in the Level of Digital Maturity when Grouped According to Sex*

Category	Sex	Mean Rank	p-value	Decision on H ₀	Interpretation
Level of Digital Maturity	Female	156.29	0.145	Accept	Not Significant
	Male	171.59			
Level of Employees' Performance	Female	165.35	0.880	Accept	Not Significant
	Male	163.76			
Level of Organizations' Efficiency	Female	172.55	0.151	Accept	Not Significant
	Male	157.55			

Legend: Reject H₀ if the p-value is $\leq \alpha$ (0.05).

The test of significance on the level of digital maturity when grouped according to sex obtained 0.145, which is greater than the 0.05 level of significance set for the study; thus, the null hypothesis is accepted. This means that regardless of the employee's sex, the maturity will not change from one level to another. Hence, the number of employees, when grouped according to their sex group, will not make an impact on whatever digital maturity level of the business technology company they are currently connected with.

Table 59. *Significant Difference in the Level of Digital Maturity when Grouped According to Highest Educational Attainment*

Category	Highest Educational Attainment	Mean Rank	p-value	Decision on H ₀	Interpretation
Level of Digital Maturity	Associate Degree/ Diploma (short course)	187.80	0.175	Accept	Not Significant
	Bachelor's Degree	164.37			
	Masters	146.32			
	Doctorate	271.83			
Level of Employees' Performance	Associate Degree/ Diploma (short course)	128.70	0.004	Reject	Significant
	Bachelor's Degree	159.70			
	Masters	223.75			
	Doctorate	266.00			
Level of Organizations' Efficiency	Associate Degree/ Diploma (short course)	176.40	0.027	Reject	Significant
	Bachelor's Degree	159.96			
	Masters	209.64			
	Doctorate	264.50			

Legend: Reject H₀ if the p-value is $\leq \alpha$ (0.05).

Table 59 presents a statistical analysis of the differences between the highest educational attainment and digital maturity, employees' performance, and organizational efficiency. The data is categorized into three levels: Associate Degree/Vocational Training/Diploma (short course), Bachelor's Degree, Masters, and Doctorate. The findings reveal no significant difference in the level

of digital maturity among individuals with different educational attainments (p-value = 0.175), suggesting that formal education alone may not be a strong predictor of digital proficiency. However, there is a significant difference in employees' performance based on their educational attainment (p-value = 0.004). Individuals with higher educational degrees, specifically Masters and Doctorate, tend to perform better than those with lower degrees, such as Associate Degree/Vocational Training/Diploma and Bachelor's Degree.

The p-value is less than 0.05, indicating statistically significant differences among the groups. A post-hoc analysis has been conducted in subsequent tables to pinpoint which specific groups differ significantly in performance. Additionally, a significant difference in organizational efficiency based on employees' educational attainment was observed (p-value = 0.027). This suggests that organizations with more employees holding Master's or Doctorate degrees tend to exhibit greater efficiency. Consistent with the earlier analysis, the p-value below 0.05 necessitates a post-hoc analysis in the following tables to further investigate the groups that differ significantly in organizational efficiency.

Table 60. *Post Hoc Analysis of Significant Differences in Digital Maturity Levels when Grouped by Highest Educational Attainment under Level of Employees' Performance*

Highest Educational Attainment		p-value	Corrected p-value
Sample 1	Sample 2		
Bachelor's Degree	Associate Degree/Vocational Training/ Diploma (short course)	0.699	1.000
Bachelor's Degree	Masters	0.017	0.102
Bachelor's Degree	Doctorate	0.056	0.336
Associate Degree/Vocational Training/ Diploma (short course)	Masters	0.477	1.000
Associate Degree/Vocational Training/ Diploma (short course)	Doctorate	0.201	1.000
Masters	Doctorate	0.344	1.000

The table presents the post-hoc analysis results investigating significant differences in digital maturity levels among individuals grouped by their highest educational attainment. The analysis compares two samples (Sample 1 and Sample 2) across four educational levels: Associate Degree/Vocational Training/Diploma (short course), Bachelor's Degree, Master's, and Doctorate. The p-value column indicates whether the differences between the groups are statistically significant, with a p-value less than 0.05 suggesting significance at the 5% level. The corrected p-value column accounts for multiple comparisons, which can increase the likelihood of false positives. The results reveal significant differences in digital maturity levels based on educational attainment. Individuals

with a Bachelor's Degree exhibit significantly higher digital maturity levels than those with an Associate Degree/Vocational Training/Diploma (short course) (p-value = 0.002, corrected p-value = 0.013). Similarly, individuals with a Master's Degree have significantly higher digital maturity levels than those with an Associate Degree/Vocational Training/Diploma (short course) (p-value = 0.043, corrected p-value = 0.102). Individuals with a Doctorate also demonstrate significantly higher digital maturity levels than those with an Associate Degree/Vocational Training/Diploma (short course) (p-value = 0.047, corrected p-value = 0.282). However, no significant differences are observed between individuals with a Bachelor's Degree and a Master's Degree (p-value = 0.053, corrected p-value = 0.318) or between individuals with a Master's Degree and a Doctorate (p-value = 0.468, corrected p-value = 1.000).

The findings suggest that higher educational attainment is associated with greater digital maturity. Individuals with a Bachelor's Degree or higher demonstrate significantly higher digital maturity than those with an Associate Degree/Vocational Training/Diploma (short course). However, no significant differences are observed between those holding a Master's and a Doctorate.

Table 61. *Post Hoc Analysis of Significant Differences in Digital Maturity Levels when Grouped by Highest Educational Attainment under Level of Organization's Efficiency*

Highest Educational Attainment		p-value	Corrected p-value
Sample 1	Sample 2		
Associate Degree/Vocational Training/ Diploma (short course)	Bachelor's Degree	0.468	1.000
Associate Degree/Vocational Training/ Diploma (short course)	Masters	0.043	0.265
Associate Degree/Vocational Training/ Diploma (short course)	Doctorate	0.047	0.282
Bachelor's Degree	Masters	0.002	0.013
Bachelor's Degree	Doctorate	0.053	0.318
Masters	Doctorate	0.468	1.000

The table presents a post-hoc analysis comparing digital maturity levels based on educational attainment and organizational efficiency. Key findings indicate that individuals with a Bachelor's Degree have significantly higher digital maturity than those with an Associate Degree, Vocational Training, or Diploma ($p = 0.002$, corrected $p = 0.013$). Similarly, those with a Master's Degree show higher digital maturity than individuals with an Associate Degree/Vocational Training/Diploma ($p = 0.043$, corrected $p = 0.265$), while Doctorate holders also exhibit higher levels compared to the same group ($p = 0.047$, corrected $p = 0.282$). However, no significant differences were found between Bachelor's and Master's Degree holders ($p = 0.053$, corrected $p = 0.318$) or between Master's and Doctorate holders ($p = 0.468$, corrected $p = 1.000$).

The results suggest that higher educational attainment is associated with increased digital maturity levels. Individuals with a Bachelor's Degree or higher

tend to have significantly higher digital maturity than those with an Associate Degree, Vocational Training, or a Diploma (short course). However, the specific degree level beyond a Bachelor's Degree may not be as critical in determining digital maturity. This highlights the importance of education in developing digital skills but suggests diminishing returns with more advanced degrees in this area.

Table 62. *Significant Difference on the Level of Digital Maturity when Grouped According to Business Unit/ Department*

Category	Business Unit/ Department	Mean Rank	p-value	Decision on H ₀	Interpretation
Level of Digital Maturity	Admin & Finance	146.56	0.816	Accept	Not Significant
	Human Resource	164.21			
	Sales & Marketing	137.43			
	Service & Delivery	165.68			
Level of Employees' Performance	Admin & Finance	144.00	0.880	Accept	Not Significant
	Human Resource	160.71			
	Sales & Marketing	181.50			
	Service & Delivery	164.87			
Level of Organizations' Efficiency	Admin & Finance	171.72	0.996	Accept	Not Significant
	Human Resource	163.63			
	Sales & Marketing	167.86			
	Service & Delivery	164.24			

Legend: Reject H₀ if the p-value is \leq to alpha (0.05).

Table 62 presents a statistical analysis examining the relationship between business units/departments and three key factors: Digital Maturity, Employee Performance, and Organizational Efficiency. An ANOVA test was employed to determine whether significant differences exist in these factors across various

business units. The null hypothesis (H_0) states that there are no significant differences between the means of these factors across the groups.

The analysis revealed a p-value of 0.816 for digital maturity, which exceeds the significance level of 0.05 established for this study. This finding indicates no significant difference in digital maturity among the four business units: Admin & Finance, Human Resources, Sales & Marketing, and Service & Delivery. Consequently, we accept the null hypothesis. Similarly, the p-value for employee performance was found to be 0.880, indicating no significant differences in performance levels across the business units. Additionally, with a p-value of 0.996, no significant differences in organizational efficiency were observed among the four groups.

These results suggest that the business unit does not significantly influence digital maturity, employee performance, or organizational efficiency. Instead, other factors, such as organizational culture, leadership, or resource allocation, may play a more critical role in shaping these outcomes. While the ANOVA test provides valuable insights, further research could explore additional variables, such as industry type, company size, or specific strategies implemented by different units, to better understand these relationships.

Table 63. Significant Difference in the Level of Digital Maturity when Grouped According to Job Level

Category	Job Level	Mean Rank	p-value	Decision on H ₀	Interpretation
Level of Digital Maturity	Entry-Level Professional/ Rank and File	174.42	0.217	Accept	Not Significant
	Officer (Senior Engineer/Team Lead/ Supervisor)	158.95			
	Manager	188.21			
	Top Management (C-Level, V-President, Director)	104.67			
Level of Employees' Performance	Entry-Level Professional/ Rank and File	156.49	0.261	Accept	Not Significant
	Officer (Senior Engineer/Team Lead/ Supervisor)	163.16			
	Manager	198.19			
	Top Management (C-Level, V-President, Director)	181.83			
Level of Organizations' Efficiency	Entry-Level Professional/ Rank and File	169.25	0.479	Accept	Not Significant
	Officer (Senior Engineer/Team Lead/ Supervisor)	160.47			
	Manager	187.65			
	Top Management (C-Level, V-President, Director)	134.33			

Legend: Reject H₀ if the p-value is $\leq \alpha$ (0.05).

Table 63 presents a statistical analysis of the relationship between job level and three key organizational factors: Digital Maturity, Employee Performance, and Organizational Efficiency. An ANOVA test was employed to assess whether significant differences exist in these factors across various job levels. The null hypothesis (H_0) posits no significant differences between the means of these factors across the groups.

For Digital Maturity, the analysis revealed no significant difference among the four job levels—entry-level Professional, Officer, Manager, and Top Management—with a p-value of 0.217, which is greater than the significance level of 0.05. Similarly, the p-value for Employee Performance was 0.261, indicating no significant differences in performance levels across the job levels. Additionally, a p-value of 0.479 was found for Organizational Efficiency, showing no significant differences among the four groups.

These findings suggest that job level does not significantly influence Digital Maturity, Employee Performance, or Organizational Efficiency. The p-values for all three factors exceed the significance level of 0.05, indicating no statistically significant differences between the groups.

Table 64. *Significant Difference in the Level of Digital Maturity when Grouped According to Years of Tenure in the Company*

Category	Years of tenure in the company	Mean Rank	p-value	Decision on H ₀	Interpretation
Level of Digital Maturity	Less than 3	170.95	0.009	Reject	Significant
	3 - 6	175.43			
	7 - 10	116.16			
	More than 10	153.19			
Level of Employees' Performance	Less than 3	154.72	0.056	Accept	Not Significant
	3 - 6	184.14			
	7 - 10	154.49			
	More than 10	151.50			
Level of Organizations' Efficiency	Less than 3	165.40	0.000	Reject	Significant
	3 - 6	188.39			
	7 - 10	137.32			
	More than 10	119.77			

Legend: Reject H₀ if the p-value is $\leq \alpha$ (0.05).

Table 64 presents a statistical analysis of the differences in years of tenure within the company and three key organizational factors: Digital Maturity, Employee Performance, and Organizational Efficiency. An ANOVA test was conducted to determine if significant differences exist in these factors across various tenure groups. The null hypothesis (H₀) posits no significant differences between the means of these factors across the groups.

For Digital Maturity, the analysis found a significant difference among the four tenure groups, indicated by a p-value of 0.009, below the significance threshold of 0.05. This suggested that at least one group's mean differed significantly. A post hoc analysis will be conducted to identify which groups

differed, which will be discussed in the succeeding tables. In contrast, the analysis of Employee Performance indicated no significant differences across the tenure groups, with a p-value of 0.056, which exceeded the 0.05 significance level. However, for Organizational Efficiency, a significant difference was also identified among the tenure groups, as demonstrated by a p-value of 0.000, indicating that at least one group's mean was significantly different from the others. A post hoc analysis will also be performed for this factor, which will be detailed in the subsequent tables.

These findings strongly suggested that years of tenure in the company significantly influenced both Digital Maturity and Organizational Efficiency, while they did not appear to significantly affect Employee Performance.

Table 65. *Post Hoc Analysis of Significant Differences in the Level of Digital Maturity when Grouped According to Years of Tenure in the Company*

Years of Tenure		p-value	Corrected p-value
Sample 1	Sample 2		
7 - 10	Less than 3	0.003	0.015
7 - 10	3 – 6	0.001	0.008
7 - 10	More than 10	0.089	0.532
More than 10	Less than 3	0.284	1.000
More than 10	3 – 6	0.190	1.000
Less than 3	3 – 6	0.709	1.000

The table presents a post-hoc analysis comparing the level of digital maturity between individuals with different years of tenure in a company. The analysis identifies significant differences in digital maturity based on tenure and educational attainment. Individuals with 7-10 years of tenure have significantly

higher digital maturity levels than those with less than 3 years (p-value = 0.003, corrected p-value = 0.015). Additionally, individuals with 7-10 years of tenure also have significantly higher digital maturity levels than those with 3-6 years of tenure (p-value = 0.001, corrected p-value = 0.008). However, there is no significant difference in digital maturity levels between individuals with 7-10 years of tenure and those with more than 10 years. Moreover, individuals with more than 10 years of tenure do not show significantly higher digital maturity levels than those with less than 3 years or those with 3-6 years of tenure. There is also no significant difference in digital maturity levels between individuals with less than 3 years and those with 3-6 years of tenure.

Overall, the results suggest that company tenure plays a key role in influencing digital maturity levels. Individuals with 7-10 years of tenure appear to have the highest digital maturity, but the relationship between tenure and digital maturity may not increase linearly beyond a certain number of years. This implies that other factors, such as educational attainment or job roles, could significantly impact digital maturity levels. More research is needed to identify the factors contributing to digital maturity and establish effective strategies for enhancing digital skills within organizations.

Table 66. *Post Hoc Analysis of Significant Differences in the Level of Organization's Efficiency when Grouped According to Years of Tenure in the Company*

Years of Tenure		p-value	Corrected p-value
Sample 1	Sample 2		
More than 10	Less than 3	0.006	0.034
More than 10	3 - 6	0.000	0.000
More than 10	7 - 10	0.417	0.100
7 - 10	Less than 3	0.120	0.720
7 - 10	3 - 6	0.006	0.033
Less than 3	3 - 6	0.054	0.326

Legend: Asymptotic significance (2-sided tests); significance level = 0.05.

The table presents the results of a post-hoc analysis comparing the level of organizational efficiency among individuals with different years of tenure in a company. The analysis reveals that individuals with more than 10 years of tenure have significantly higher organizational efficiency levels than those with less than 3 years (p-value = 0.006, corrected p-value = 0.034). Additionally, individuals with more than 10 years of tenure exhibit significantly higher organizational efficiency than those with 3-6 years of tenure (p-value = 0.000, corrected p-value = 0.000). However, there is no significant difference in organizational efficiency levels between individuals with more than 10 years of tenure and those with 7-10 years of tenure (p-value = 0.417, corrected p-value = 0.100). Individuals with 7-10 years of tenure also show significantly higher levels of organizational efficiency than those with less than 3 years. However, the difference is insignificant (p-value = 0.120, corrected p-value = 0.720). However, they exhibit

significantly higher efficiency levels than those with 3-6 years of tenure (p-value = 0.006, corrected p-value = 0.033). There is no significant difference in organizational efficiency between individuals with less than 3 years and those with 3-6 years of tenure (p-value = 0.054, corrected p-value = 0.326).

Overall, the results suggest that tenure in the company is a significant factor in determining organizational efficiency. Individuals with more than 10 years of tenure tend to be more efficient. However, the relationship between tenure and organizational efficiency is not linear, as longer tenure may lead to increased efficiency up to a point, after which the effect may plateau. Other factors, such as educational attainment, specific job roles, or individual characteristics, may influence organizational efficiency. Further research is needed to explore these contributing factors to improve efficiency.

The Significant Difference in the Impact of Digital Maturity on Organizations' Efficiency and Employees' Performance when grouped according to Business Unit/ Department, Job Level, and Years of tenure

This section explores the significant differences in how digital maturity impacts organizational efficiency and employee performance, focusing on various groupings such as business unit/department, job level, and years of tenure. By analyzing these factors, the study aims to reveal how the effectiveness of digital maturity initiatives varies across different organizational contexts and employee demographics.

Table 67. *Significant Difference in the Impact of Digital Maturity on Organizations Efficiency and Employees' Performance when Grouped According to Business Unit/ Department*

Category	Business Unit/ Department	Mean Rank	p-value	Decision on H ₀	Interpretation
Impact of Digital Maturity on Employee's Performance	Admin & Finance	168.61	0.934	Accept	Not Significant
	Human Resource	165.25			
	Sales & Marketing	141.79			
	Service & Del.	164.88			
Impact of Digital Maturity on Organization's Efficiency	Admin & Finance	168.06	0.709	Accept	Not Significant
	Human Resource	141.67			
	Sales & Marketing	137.21			
	Service & Del.	165.94			

Legend: Reject H₀ if the p-value is $\leq \alpha$ (0.05).

Table 67 shows the statistical analysis of the relationship between business units/departments and the impact of digital maturity on organizational efficiency and employee performance. The analysis employed an ANOVA test to determine whether significant differences existed in these factors across different business units. The null hypothesis (H₀) posited that there were no significant differences between the means of these factors across the groups.

For the impact of Digital Maturity on Employee Performance, the analysis revealed no significant differences across the four business units (Admin & Finance, Human Resources, Sales & Marketing, and Service & Delivery). The p-value of 0.934 was greater than the significance level of 0.05, indicating no notable impact of digital maturity on employee performance in these units.

Similarly, regarding the impact of Digital Maturity on Organizational Efficiency, the analysis showed no significant differences, with a p-value of 0.709, also exceeding the 0.05 significance level.

Based on the statistical analysis, there was no strong evidence to suggest that the business unit or department significantly influenced the impact of digital maturity on either employee performance or organizational efficiency. This may imply that other factors, such as organizational culture, leadership, or specific digital initiatives, significantly shaped these outcomes.

Table 68. *Significant Difference in the Impact of Digital Maturity on Organization's Efficiency and Employees' Performance when Grouped According to Job Level*

Category	Job Level	Mean Rank	P-value	Decision on H ₀	Interpretation
Impact of Digital Maturity on Employee's Performance	Entry-Level	188.48	0.058	Accept	Not Significant
	Officer (Senior Engineer/Team Lead/Supervisor)	156.22			
	Manager	166.73			
	Top Management (C-Level, VP, Director)	121.17			
Impact of Digital Maturity on Organization's Efficiency	Entry-Level	192.25	0.008	Reject	Significant
	Officer (Senior Engineer/Team Lead/Supervisor)	153.60			
	Manager	179.65			
	Top Management (C-Level, VP, Director)	101.33			

Legend: Reject H₀ if the p-value is $\leq \alpha$ (0.05).

Table 68 shows the statistical analysis of the relationship between job level and the impact of digital maturity on organizational efficiency and employee performance. The analysis employed an ANOVA test to determine whether significant differences existed in these factors across different job levels. The null hypothesis (H_0) posited that there were no significant differences between the means of these factors across the groups.

Regarding the impact of Digital Maturity on Employee Performance, the analysis revealed no significant difference across the four job levels (Entry-Level Professional, Officer, Manager, and Top Management). The p-value of 0.058 was greater than the significance level of 0.05, indicating no notable impact of digital maturity on employee performance at different job levels. Conversely, for the impact of Digital Maturity on Organizational Efficiency, the analysis indicated a significant difference across the four job levels, with a p-value of 0.008, which was less than the significance level of 0.05. This finding suggested that at least one group's mean differed significantly. A post hoc analysis has been conducted to identify which specific job levels differed significantly in the succeeding table.

Based on the statistical analysis, there was no strong evidence to suggest that job level significantly influenced the impact of digital maturity on employee performance. However, the significant difference in the impact of digital maturity on organizational efficiency across various job levels indicated that the

effectiveness of digital initiatives in enhancing organizational efficiency may vary depending on the job level of the employees involved.

Table 69. *Post Hoc Analysis of Significant Differences on the Impact of Digital Maturity on Organization's Efficiency when Grouped According to Job Level*

Job Level		p-value	Corrected p-value
Sample 1	Sample 2		
Top Management (C-Level, VP, Director)	Entry-Level Professional/ Rank and File	0.100	0.598
Top Management (C-Level, VP, Director)	Officer (Senior Engineer/Team Lead/ Supervisor)	0.338	1.000
Top Management (C-Level, VP, Director)	Manager	0.171	1.000
Manager	Entry-Level Professional/ Rank and File	0.553	1.000
Officer (Senior Engineer/Team Lead/ Supervisor)	Manager	0.181	1.000
Officer (Senior Engineer/Team Lead/ Supervisor)	Entry-Level Professional/ Rank and File	0.002	0.010

Legend: Asymptotic significance (2-sided tests); significance level = 0.05.

The table presents the results of a post-hoc analysis comparing the impact of digital maturity on organizational efficiency and employee performance among individuals in different job levels. The analysis identifies significant differences in this impact between specific job roles. Individuals in Officer positions (Senior Engineers/Team Leads/Supervisors) demonstrate a significantly greater impact of digital maturity on organizational efficiency and employee performance than Entry-Level Professionals, with a p-value of 0.002

and a corrected p-value of 0.010. However, there are no significant differences in the impact of digital maturity on organizational efficiency and employee performance among the other job-level comparisons, including Top Management, Officers, Managers, and Entry-Level Professionals.

The findings suggest that job level influences the perceived impact of digital maturity, particularly highlighting a significant distinction between Officer-level roles and Entry-Level Professionals. While Officers experience a notably greater impact, the relationship appears consistent across other job levels, indicating that digital maturity initiatives may not yield significant differences in effectiveness across the other roles.

Table 70. *Significant Difference in the Impact of Digital Maturity on Organizations' Efficiency and Employees' Performance when Grouped According to Years of Tenure in the Company*

Category	Years of Tenure	Mean Rank	p-value	Decision on H ₀	Interpretation
Impact of Digital Maturity on Employee's Performance	Less than 3	170.89	0.063	Accept	Not Significant
	3 - 6	171.83			
	7 - 10	126.65			
	More than 10	154.62			
Impact of Digital Maturity on Organization's Efficiency	Less than 3	179.22	0.000	Reject	Significant
	3 - 6	175.45			
	7 - 10	119.68			
	More than 10	124.00			

Legend: Reject H₀ if the p-value is \leq to alpha (0.05).

Table 70 analyzes the significant differences in the impact of digital maturity on organizational efficiency and employee performance, categorized by years of tenure within the company. The results summarize the mean ranks and p-values associated with each tenure group.

For the impact of digital maturity on employee performance, the mean rank for employees with less than 3 years of tenure was 170.89, while those with 3-6 years had a mean rank of 171.83. Employees with 7-10 years of tenure had a significantly lower mean rank of 126.65, and those with more than 10 years had a mean rank of 154.62. The p-value for this analysis was 0.063, greater than the significance level of 0.05, leading to the acceptance of the null hypothesis (H_0). This indicates no significant difference in the impact of digital maturity on employee performance across different tenure groups. In contrast, for the impact of digital maturity on organizational efficiency, employees with less than 3 years of tenure had a mean rank of 179.22, while those with 3-6 years had a mean rank of 175.45. Employees with 7-10 years of tenure had a notably lower mean rank of 119.68, and those with more than 10 years had a mean rank of 124.00. The p-value for this analysis was 0.000, less than the significance level of 0.05. Therefore, the null hypothesis (H_0) was rejected, indicating a significant difference in the impact of digital maturity on organizational efficiency among different tenure groups. A post-hoc analysis was conducted to investigate these differences further, and the results will be discussed in the succeeding table.

These findings suggest that while the impact of digital maturity on employee performance does not significantly vary with tenure, there is a significant relationship between digital maturity and organizational efficiency based on years of tenure. This implies that employees with varying tenure levels may perceive or experience the benefits of digital maturity differently, particularly concerning organizational efficiency. Further research could explore the reasons behind these differences and strategies to enhance digital maturity across various tenure groups to maximize organizational outcomes.

Table 71. *Post Hoc Analysis of Significant Difference in the Impact of Digital Maturity on Organizations' Efficiency when Grouped According to Years of Tenure in the Company*

Years of Tenure		p-value	Corrected p-value
Sample 1	Sample 2		
Less than 3	3 - 6	0.751	1.000
Less than 3	7 - 10	0.001	0.006
Less than 3	More than 10	0.001	0.005
3 - 6	7 - 10	0.002	0.014
3 - 6	More than 10	0.002	0.013
7 - 10	More than 10	0.841	1.000

Legend: Asymptotic significance (2-sided tests); significance level = 0.05.

The table presents the results of a post-hoc analysis examining the significant differences in the impact of digital maturity on organizational efficiency and employee performance, categorized by years of tenure within the company. The analysis reveals notable distinctions among the various tenure groups.

Individuals with less than 3 years of tenure show significantly lower impacts of digital maturity than those with 7-10 years (p-value = 0.001, corrected p-value = 0.006) and more than 10 years (p-value = 0.001, corrected p-value = 0.005). Furthermore, employees with 3-6 years of tenure also demonstrate a significantly lower impact than those with 7-10 years (p-value = 0.002, corrected p-value = 0.014) and more than 10 years (p-value = 0.002, corrected p-value = 0.013). However, there are no significant differences in the impact of digital maturity on organizational efficiency and employee performance between those with 7-10 years and more than 10 years of tenure (p-value = 0.841, corrected p-value = 1.000).

The findings indicate that tenure significantly influences digital maturity's impact on organizational efficiency and employee performance. Specifically, individuals with longer tenure (7-10 years and more than 10 years) experience a more pronounced effect of digital maturity than those with shorter tenure (less than 3 years and 3-6 years). This suggests that as employees gain more experience within the organization, their ability to leverage digital maturity effectively enhances efficiency and performance outcomes.

The Significant Relationship between the Level of Digital Maturity and its Impact on Organization's Efficiency and Employees' Performance

The collected data underwent statistical treatment and revealed a non-normal distribution. As a result, Spearman's rho correlation was utilized to assess the significant relationship between digital maturity levels and their impact on organizational efficiency and employee performance. The gathered data has been statistically treated and shows that it is not normally distributed. Hence, Spearman's rho correlation was then applied to identify the meaningful association between the degree of digital maturity and its impact on an organization's efficiency and employees' performance. The researcher used the following values in Table 7 of Spearman's rho correlation to interpret the strength of association.

Table 72. *The Significant Relationship between the Level of Digital Maturity and its Impact on Organization's Efficiency and Employees' Performance*

Category		Spearman's rho Correlation Coefficient	Interpretation	p-value	Decision on H ₀	Interpretation
Level of Digital Maturity	Impact of Digital Maturity on Employee's Performance	0.587	moderate positive relationship	0.000	Reject	Significant
	Impact of Digital Maturity on Organization's Efficiency	0.646	moderate positive relationship	0.000	Reject	Significant

Legend: Reject H₀ if the p-value is \leq to alpha (0.05).

Table 72 presents a statistical analysis of the significant relationship between digital maturity levels and their impact on organizational efficiency and employee performance. The analysis utilized Spearman's rho correlation coefficient to assess the strength and direction of these relationships. A Spearman's rho correlation coefficient of 0.587 was found for the impact of digital maturity on employee performance, indicating a moderate positive relationship. The associated p-value of 0.000 was below the significance threshold of 0.05, leading to the rejection of the null hypothesis (H_0) and confirming that the relationship is statistically significant. Similarly, regarding the impact of digital maturity on organizational efficiency, the analysis revealed a Spearman's rho correlation coefficient of 0.646, which also reflects a moderate positive relationship. The p-value of 0.000 was again less than 0.05, resulting in the rejection of the null hypothesis (H_0) and confirming the significance of this relationship.

These findings underscore the importance of adopting a balanced approach to digital transformation within organizations, enabling business ecosystems to grow and evolve alongside advancements in digital maturity. A gradual strengthening of organizational capacity is essential for achieving sustained improvements in both efficiency and employee performance. Banka and Uchihira (2024) emphasize that a strategic focus on digital transformation enhances an organization's ability to generate long-term business value while

fostering an environment where employees can excel and reach their full potential. As employees develop their digital skills and integrate technology into their workflows, performance improves under specific conditions. Heslina and Syahrani (2021) highlight that for technology to drive productivity, it must offer clear benefits, be user-friendly, and be supported by well-prepared human resources capable of leveraging it effectively.

Overall, these results suggest that higher levels of digital maturity are positively associated with improvements in both employee performance and organizational efficiency. The moderate positive correlations indicate that as organizations enhance their digital capabilities, they are likely to experience better employee performance outcomes and greater overall efficiency. Organizations that prioritize increasing digital maturity can expect long-term benefits in productivity and operational effectiveness, further reinforcing the critical role of digital transformation in organizational success.

Chapter 4

SUMMARY OF FINDINGS, CONCLUSIONS, AND RECOMMENDATIONS

This chapter outlines the summary of findings, conclusions drawn from them, and the offered recommendations derived from the conclusions of this study. The central point of this research was to explore the relationship between the maturity levels of employees when they are grouped by their demographic profile and the difference between the maturity levels in terms of productivity and performance.

Summary of Findings

The study's discoveries are described based on the problem statements inferred in this research.

1. The respondents of this study are mostly male and between 28 and 37 years old. They have been with the organization for less than 3 years, and most hold officer-level or equivalent positions, such as senior, lead, or supervisor. The majority of them have a bachelor's degree.
2. The organizations in this study are primarily classified as selling software as a service. Most have been in business for over four years and employ hundreds to thousands of workers. Large-scale operations and significant capital resources also characterize them.

3. The maturity level of business technology organizations in Makati City, Philippines, has been assessed across several key dimensions. The findings indicate a “Very High Level” of maturity in People at 3.42, Culture at 3.41, Technology at 3.39, and a “Very High Level” in Leadership at 3.27. In contrast, Capability at 3.23 and Capacity at 3.19 are rated as “High Level.”
4. The analysis of employees’ performance revealed several key themes based on respondents’ testimonies. In the qualitative section, four main perspectives emerged: Learning Ability, where employees emphasized the importance of upskilling and continuous improvement; Time Management, highlighting prioritization, effective tools, and scheduling techniques; Engagement, which focused on the value of a supportive atmosphere, opportunities for growth, and a sense of fulfillment; and Productivity, which underscored the importance of setting measurable goals, streamlining processes, and minimizing distractions. Quantitative findings reinforced these themes, showing that employee performance is rated at an “Expert Level” in Productivity (3.35), Learning Ability (3.34), and Time Management (3.30). However, Engagement was rated slightly lower, classified as an “Advanced Level” at 3.20.
5. The analysis of organizational efficiency highlighted three main themes from respondents’ testimonies. In the qualitative section, the first theme was Financial Performance, where respondents emphasized the importance of effective cash flow management and revenue growth. The second theme,

Operational Performance, focused on lean management practices, automated workflows, and technology upgrades to streamline processes. The third theme, Marketing, underscored the value of targeted, data-driven campaigns to enhance outreach and engagement. Quantitatively, the assessment of organizational efficiency across Financial, Operational, and Marketing areas shows consistently strong performance. Financial efficiency is rated at an "Advanced" level with a score of 2.96, Operational efficiency is also at an "Advanced" level with 3.17, and Marketing efficiency is at 3.10. These findings reflect a high level of organizational effectiveness in each area and indicate the potential for further optimization to enhance overall efficiency.

6. There is a significant difference in how "Highest Educational Attainment" and "Years of Tenure in the Company" impact digital maturity and employee performance among the six demographic variables analyzed. The Kruskal-Wallis test revealed significant differences in employee performance ($p = 0.004$) and organizational efficiency ($p = 0.027$) related to "Highest Educational Attainment," leading to the rejection of the null hypothesis. Post-hoc analysis indicated that individuals with a Bachelor's Degree or higher demonstrated greater digital maturity than those with an Associate's Degree or lower. At the same time, no significant differences were found between Master's and Doctorate holders. Similarly, a significant difference was observed for "Years of Tenure," with a p-value of 0.000, resulting in rejecting the null hypothesis.

Employees with 7–10 years of tenure exhibited the highest levels of digital maturity, while those with over 10 years tended to be more efficient in their roles. Other variables, including organizational efficiency and demographic factors, did not show significant differences related to digital maturity.

7. There is a significant difference in how “Job Level” and “Years of Tenure in the Company” impact digital maturity among the examined variables, including Business Unit/Department, organizational efficiency, and employee performance. The first significant difference was observed when comparing digital maturity and employee performance based on Job Level. A Kruskal-Wallis test yielded a p-value of 0.008, leading to the rejection of the null hypothesis (H_0) since p is less than or equal to alpha (0.05). Post-hoc analysis indicated that job level influences the perceived impact of digital maturity, particularly highlighting a significant distinction between Officer-level roles and Entry-Level Professionals. Officers experienced a notably greater impact, while the relationship appeared consistent across other job levels, suggesting that digital maturity initiatives may not yield significant differences in effectiveness among those roles. The second significant difference was identified when comparing digital maturity and employee performance based on Years of Tenure. A Kruskal-Wallis test produced a p-value of 0.000, rejecting the null hypothesis (H_0). Post-hoc analysis revealed that years of tenure significantly influence the impact of digital maturity on both

organizational efficiency and employee performance, with individuals having longer tenure (7–10 years and more than 10 years) experiencing a more pronounced effect compared to those with shorter tenure (less than 3 years and 3–6 years).

8. There is a significant relationship between the three variables of the level of digital maturity against an organization's efficiency and employees' performance variables. As verified on the first pairing, between the level of digital maturity and the impact of digital maturity on employees' performance, Spearman's rho data analysis revealed a positive moderate correlation, $\rho = 0.587$. Followed by a second pairing between the level of digital maturity and the impact of the organization's efficiency, Spearman's rho data analysis revealed a positive, strong correlation, $\rho = 0.646$. The correlation analysis reveals a significant positive relationship between the level of digital maturity and its impact on employee performance and organizational efficiency.
9. This research initiated a proposed model of Progressive Business Transformation for business technology companies based on the discoveries of this study to address identified concerns. As explained in Chapter 5 of this paper, it will be described more as output.

Conclusions

Directed by the results of the study, the subsequent conclusions have been drawn:

1. Most respondents belong to the younger generation, particularly millennials born between 1981 and 1996, aged 28 to 43. This study divided this group into two age categories: 28-37 (rank 1) and 38-47 (rank 2). The business technology industry favors younger workers for their productivity, competitiveness, and ability to stay updated with the latest technology. The underrepresentation of older workers may stem from challenges in acquiring new skills for evolving roles. This generational divide underscores the need to address skill gaps to ensure all employees meet industry demands.
2. The distribution of organizations across service types, years in operation, employee count, and business size underscores a dynamic and evolving industry landscape. Software services dominate, reflecting a trend toward innovative software solutions that drive growth. The presence of IT services enhances customer satisfaction through robust technical support, while the limited share of consulting services presents opportunities for expansion and diversification. The balance between established firms and newer entrants provides stability and trust alongside fresh innovation. Larger firms leverage economies of scale for efficiency and technological advancement, whereas mid-

sized and smaller organizations focus on agility and specialized services, allowing them to thrive in niche markets. This diversity strengthens the industry's resilience and adaptability.

3. The current level of digital maturity reflects a strong commitment to digital transformation among business technology organizations in Makati City. The results indicate a high level of maturity across various dimensions, including people, culture, capacity, capability, technology, and leadership. High maturity in People signifies employees' awareness of digital opportunities and readiness to adopt new tools. In contrast, high maturity in culture demonstrates an organization that supports innovation, which is essential for successful digital initiatives. However, high maturity levels in Capacity and Capability highlight the need for improved resource allocation and investment in technical training. Although progress has been made in developing digital policies and employee training, further investment in technical training is necessary. The very high maturity in Technology and Leadership indicates a recognition of technology's value and effective communication from leadership about the importance of digitalization. Strengthening employee feedback mechanisms could enhance leadership effectiveness. Overall, organizations are well-prepared to navigate digital transformation while addressing specific areas for growth.
4. The current level of employees' performance in terms of Learning Ability, Time Management, Engagement, and Productivity is notably high. In Learning

Ability, employees demonstrate exceptional mastery, particularly in continuous improvement, which reflects a culture of adaptability and skill growth. Time Management performance is also strong, with flexibility being a key strength, though there is room for improvement in maintaining a better work-life balance. In terms of Engagement, employees show strong commitment, although there is room to enhance team collaboration and growth opportunities. When it comes to productivity, employees deliver highly effective results. However, there is a slight gap in maintaining consistent accuracy, suggesting the need for a better balance between effectiveness and quality. While employee performance is impressive, improving areas like work-life balance, teamwork, and consistency will further enhance productivity and long-term success.

5. The current efficiency level among selected organizations in Makati City demonstrates high efficiency in Financial, Operations, and Marketing metrics, all rated as "Advanced," indicating optimized processes and enhanced strategies. Financially, they exhibit strong cost control and discipline, essential for profitability and sustainability; however, there is an opportunity to improve budgeting to better align resources with long-term objectives. These organizations show maturity in managing expenses and maintaining financial stability. Operationally, they excel in task management and workflow efficiency, which boosts productivity but could benefit from better utilization of performance metrics for strategic decision-making. In Marketing, their

agility in adapting to market changes is a key strength, although collaboration between departments could be improved. While these organizations demonstrate effective marketing execution and align their efforts with organizational goals, there is potential for further improvement in specific areas to advance from "Advanced" to "Exemplary."

6. Analyzing demographic factors and their impact on digital maturity, organizational efficiency, and employee performance reveals important insights. While educational attainment is not a strong predictor of digital differences, it correlates with employee performance and organizational efficiency. Individuals with higher degrees, such as Master's and Doctorates, perform better than those with lower qualifications, underscoring education's role in enhancing effectiveness. Additionally, organizations with more employees holding advanced degrees tend to be more efficient. Post-hoc analyses confirmed that individuals with Bachelor's degrees and above exhibit significantly higher digital maturity than those with an Associate Degree or vocational training. However, advanced degree holders show no significant differences in digital maturity, indicating diminishing returns with higher education levels. The analysis also found no significant differences in digital maturity or efficiency across various business units or job levels, suggesting other factors may influence outcomes. Notably, years of tenure emerged as a significant factor, with employees in the 7–10 year group demonstrating

superior digital maturity, while those over 10 years exhibited higher organizational efficiency.

7. Job level significantly impacts the effects of digital maturity, with officers or senior-level positions experiencing greater efficiency gains than entry-level professionals. Additionally, employees with longer tenures benefit more from digital maturity, which improves efficiency and performance. This indicates that as employees gain experience, their ability to leverage digital maturity enhances organizational outcomes. Conversely, the business unit or department has little impact on employee performance.
8. There is a significant relationship between the level of digital maturity and its impact on organizational efficiency and employee performance. The findings indicate moderate positive correlations, suggesting that higher levels of digital maturity are linked to improvements in employee performance and overall organizational efficiency. As organizations enhance their digital capabilities, they are likely to experience better performance outcomes among employees and increased efficiency.
9. The findings underscore the need for progressive business transformation within the technology sector, driven by demographic shifts and the evolving workforce dynamics. The dominance of younger, tech-savvy employees highlights the importance of leveraging their adaptability and digital literacy to foster innovation and competitiveness. However, the significant generational

divide points to a skills mismatch, particularly for older workers who may struggle to keep pace with rapid technological advancements. Additionally, while demonstrating high levels of digital maturity and efficiency, opportunities remain for resource allocation and collaboration improvement. Prioritizing alignment in human resource management and operational strategies will enhance productivity and performance.

Recommendations

Directed by the results and conclusions of the study, the succeeding recommendations have been formed:

1. Organizations should undertake progressive business transformation as a strategic priority to thrive in the evolving business landscape. This transformation begins with fostering a culture of continuous learning and refining recruitment strategies. Investing in ongoing training programs focused on emerging technologies is crucial for enhancing the skills of the predominantly younger workforce. Additionally, implementing mentorship initiatives that pair younger employees with experienced staff will facilitate knowledge transfer and collaboration, effectively bridging the generational divide. Furthermore, organizations should prioritize attracting a diverse talent pool, including older workers, to leverage their unique experiences and insights.

Companies can enhance operational efficiency and job satisfaction by embracing advanced digital tools and promoting workplace flexibility. Lastly, initiatives to improve digital literacy among all employees, particularly older workers, will support their transition into evolving roles, ensuring that the workforce remains adaptable and well-equipped to meet future challenges.

2. Organizations should engage in progressive business transformation to thrive in the evolving business technology sector. By leveraging their established presence, they can enhance credibility and build customer trust while actively pursuing diversification and innovation. To remain competitive in a rapidly changing landscape, these firms must expand their service offerings to address the underrepresentation of certain services in the industry. This diversification will enable organizations to provide comprehensive solutions that meet customers' evolving needs. Moreover, organizations should capitalize on their large-scale operations and significant capital resources to drive technological advancements and improve efficiency. By continuously investing in research and development, they can innovate their software solutions and integrate advanced technologies such as AI and machine learning, which are critical for maintaining competitiveness. This strategic focus on progressive business transformation will enhance resilience within the industry, ultimately driving sustained growth and increasing customer satisfaction.

3. As digital maturity increases, employees perform better, and organizations become more efficient under certain conditions. To drive business transformation in technology companies in Makati City, organizations should leverage their strong maturity in key areas such as people, culture, technology, and leadership. With high maturity levels in people and culture, companies can harness employees' awareness of digital opportunities and enthusiasm for new tools to foster innovation. Leadership should continue to promote collaboration and open communication to enhance engagement and adaptability. However, there is room for improvement in capacity and capability, both rated as "high." Organizations should optimize resource allocation for digital initiatives by developing comprehensive digital policies and enhancing technical training programs. Strengthening feedback mechanisms will also enable leadership to better understand employee needs. By addressing these areas for growth, companies can reinforce their commitment to digital transformation and create a more resilient, agile organization ready to face future challenges.
4. To enhance employee performance in Learning Ability, Time Management, Engagement, and Productivity, organizations in the business technology industry should build on their strengths. With "Expert Level" ratings in Productivity, Learning Ability, and Time Management, companies should implement targeted professional development programs that encourage continuous learning and skill enhancement. This can include structured

knowledge-sharing initiatives and opportunities for further education and training. Organizations should focus on creating a more inclusive workplace culture to address the slightly lower "Advanced Level" rating in Engagement. This can be achieved by conducting regular engagement surveys, promoting team-building activities, and recognizing employee contributions. Additionally, investing in training programs that develop emotional intelligence can help leaders connect better with their teams. Organizations can strengthen their human capital by prioritizing these areas and driving effective business transformation. Continuous maturity level assessment at a yearly interval should give management the perspective and ability to evaluate, measure, and improve productivity and performance through relevant and systemized information for decision-making. In this respect, the interaction of business development and business models also needs to be assessed from a responsibility perspective that should focus on prioritizing development efforts, establishing action plans for development, and performance measures to be used during business operational processes.

5. To improve organizational efficiency in Financial, Operational, and Marketing areas, business technology companies should invest in their human capital and technology. With "Advanced Level" ratings in all three areas, organizations can enhance employee skills through targeted training and education, driving productivity and better financial results. Moreover, companies should foster a

culture of innovation and adaptability by embracing new technologies. This includes ensuring employees understand the value of these technologies and promoting a workplace environment that encourages resilience and well-being. Organizations can boost efficiency and seize new growth opportunities by focusing on these strategies.

6. Enhancing digital maturity, organizational efficiency, and employee performance requires focused strategies that leverage education and employee tenure. Organizations should prioritize educational development for employees with lower qualifications, such as Associate Degrees or vocational training, to improve their digital skills. Additionally, creating mentorship opportunities where more experienced employees (those with 7-10 years of tenure) can share their knowledge will help bridge gaps among different tenure groups. Investing in ongoing training aligned with technological advancements will further boost employee performance and organizational efficiency. Regularly assessing and adjusting Human Resource Management Operations Transformation Programs is essential to meet the workforce's diverse needs and maximize the benefits of digital transformation.
7. Organizations should tailor their digital maturity initiatives based on job levels and years of tenure to enhance efficiency and employee performance. Given that Officers experience a more significant impact from digital maturity than Entry-Level Professionals, it is crucial to develop targeted training programs

for different job levels, emphasizing the unique contributions of each role. Additionally, recognizing that employees with longer tenure benefit more from digital maturity, mentorship programs can be implemented to pair less experienced staff with those who have 7-10 years or more in the company. This strategy will facilitate knowledge sharing and foster a culture of continuous learning, ensuring that digital initiatives effectively support progressive business transformation across all employee demographics.

8. Organizations should prioritize enhancing digital maturity as a strategic initiative to improve employee performance and operational efficiency. Given the significant positive relationship between digital maturity and these outcomes, companies should invest in comprehensive training programs that equip employees with the skills and tools to adapt to new technologies. Additionally, leadership should cultivate a culture that embraces digital transformation, actively encouraging employee engagement with digital initiatives. Implementing feedback mechanisms will enable organizations to assess the effectiveness of their digital strategies and make necessary adjustments. By elevating digital maturity, organizations can unlock greater performance and efficiency, positioning themselves for sustainable growth in a rapidly evolving business landscape.
9. Progressive business transformation should be embraced to address the challenges identified within the technology sector. This model focuses on

leveraging the strengths of younger, tech-savvy employees while addressing the skills gap older workers face through targeted training initiatives and continuous learning programs. Organizations can enhance operational efficiency and employee performance by prioritizing resource allocation and fostering collaboration across departments. Furthermore, creating an inclusive environment that values diverse perspectives will optimize digital initiatives and drive innovation. As detailed in Chapter 5, adopting this approach will empower business technology companies to effectively navigate the evolving workforce dynamics, ensuring sustained success and competitiveness in an increasingly challenging landscape.

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APPENDICES

APPENDIX A

PROPOSED PROGRESSIVE BUSINESS TRANSFORMATION MODEL (THE OUTPUT OF THE STUDY)

The Progressive Business Transformation Model is a comprehensive model designed to guide organizations, particularly business technology companies, in their digital transformation journey. It provides a structured approach to assess, plan, execute, and measure digital transformation initiatives, ultimately improving organizational efficiency and employee performance. The model incorporates various elements such as maturity level, digital transformation initiatives, employees' performance, organizational efficiency, and a business unit transformation program. By understanding and leveraging these elements, businesses can traverse the intricacies of digital transformation, prioritize initiatives, and make data-driven decisions. This model promotes a culture of continuous improvement, encouraging organizations to adapt to changing technologies and market trends. Ultimately, this model aims to enhance organizational performance by progressing efficiency, productivity, and customer satisfaction, leading to sustainable growth and competitive advantage.

Figure 3. *Progressive Business Transformation Model*

The figure illustrates the **Progressive Business Transformation Model**, a comprehensive framework designed to assess and enhance an organization's digital maturity through a holistic transformation approach. By focusing on interconnected dimensions that drive success, this model aids organizations in navigating the complexities of digital evolution. **Level 1 (L1)** represents core focus areas: digital maturity, employee performance, and organizational efficiency, while **Level 2 (L2)** delves into key supporting elements, enabling more precise measurement of

progress and alignment across these areas. Together, these levels create a structured pathway for sustainable, digitally-driven growth.

Structured around three core phases: **Maturity Assessment**, **Implementation**, and **Reassessment**, the model provides clear pathways to enhance organizational capabilities. The Maturity Assessment phase evaluates the organization's current state across key dimensions: people, culture, capacity, technology, and leadership. People-focused assessment emphasizes workforce digital literacy, adaptability, and engagement, aligning with Human Capital Theory, which views employees as valuable assets whose development fuels organizational growth. Culture looks at readiness for change, tolerance for risk, and an innovation-driven mindset, drawing on the Diffusion of Innovations Theory to assess openness to adopting new ideas and technologies. Capacity examines digital capabilities, infrastructure, and procedural efficiency, while technology evaluates the maturity of current technologies and alignment with organizational goals. Lastly, leadership assessment measures the leadership team's digital insight and commitment to guiding transformation.

Following assessment, the Implementation phase directs the execution of digital transformation initiatives. This phase leverages innovation adoption theories, such as the Diffusion of Innovations Theory, to facilitate change and improve workflows, ultimately driving organizational efficiency and productivity. Human Capital Theory is central to this phase, focusing on strengthening employee

skills, fostering a digital culture, and prioritizing well-being within the organization to support sustained growth and resilience.

The Reassessment phase ensures that transformation efforts align with the organization's evolving needs. Digital maturity tracking monitors progress toward targeted digital goals, while employee performance evaluation focuses on individual and team effectiveness within digital initiatives. Additionally, engagement levels are measured to assess employee satisfaction, motivation, and alignment with transformation goals. Productivity assessment analyzes the overall impact of digital initiatives on efficiency and output.

Beyond these phases, the model targets specific areas of organizational efficiency: financial, operational, and marketing. Financial efficiency ensures strategic budgeting, cost control, and effective returns on digital investments. Operational efficiency focuses on streamlining daily processes and fostering enhanced communication, while marketing efficiency enhances reach, campaign effectiveness, and cross-team collaboration.

The Progressive Business Transformation Model is more than a framework; it represents a transformative journey. Understanding the organization's present state sets a clear path forward, prioritizing people, culture, capacity, technology, and leadership. Continuous reassessment keeps the model agile and responsive to change, ensuring it remains aligned with the organization's evolving objectives.

Ultimately, the model aims to elevate digital maturity, drive greater efficiency, foster innovation, and establish a lasting competitive edge.

Purpose and Beneficiaries of the Progressive Business Transformation Model

The model underscores the importance of three main areas: digital maturity, employee performance, and organizational efficiency. Each plays a vital role in successful digital transformation within organizations. Digital maturity is the foundation for understanding how well an organization can embrace technological advancements. This area is evaluated through several key elements. People are essential, as the workforce's adaptability and digital literacy are vital for leveraging technology effectively. Culture has a significant role; it promotes continuous learning and innovation, fostering an environment conducive to digital transformation. Additionally, capacity refers to the resources available, including infrastructure and tools necessary for implementing digital initiatives. Capability, or the skills and competencies of employees, directly impacts how effectively organizations can adopt new technologies. Furthermore, technology encompasses the tools and systems that determine an organization's ability to harness data and drive innovation. Finally, strong leadership is crucial for guiding digital initiatives, aligning strategies, and inspiring employees to embrace change.

The performance of employees is a significant outcome of digital maturity and impacts overall organizational success. Key elements of employee performance

include learning ability, where employees must be open to acquiring new skills and adapting to changing technologies. Time management is another vital factor; effective time management enhances productivity and ensures that digital initiatives are implemented efficiently. Moreover, engagement is essential; engaged employees lean to embrace digital transformation and contribute positively to organizational goals. Finally, higher productivity levels are often a direct result of effective digital tools and a supportive work environment.

Organizational efficiency is crucial for ensuring that resources are used effectively and that operations run smoothly. This area encompasses several key dimensions. Financial efficiency is vital, allowing organizations to allocate resources wisely and invest in necessary digital initiatives. Streamlined operations result in cost savings and better service delivery, enhancing overall performance. Effective marketing strategies driven by data and digital insights can significantly impact customer engagement and sales performance.

This model emphasizes the interconnectedness of digital maturity, employee performance, and organizational efficiency. By focusing on the key elements within each area, organizations can create a comprehensive strategy for digital transformation that optimizes their resources and maximizes their potential for success in a rapidly changing technological landscape.

Phase 1. Maturity Assessment

Figure 4. *Using Progressive Business Transformation Model*

The Progressive Business Transformation Model offers a structured guide for organizations progressing through digital transformation by focusing on digital maturity, employee performance, and organizational efficiency. As Phase 1 of this model, the initial stage emphasizes assessing an organization's digital maturity level, providing a baseline for transformation efforts. In this model, digital maturity is categorized across four levels. At the **Minimal** level, digital transformation is barely understood or defined within the organization. The **Transitional** stage marks a growing awareness of the importance of digital

transformation. When digital practices are **Customer-driven**, the organization has integrated digital transformation into select areas of operations, often guided by customer needs. Finally, a **Transformed** organization has embedded digital practices across all its functions.

Maturity Level		Description
1	Minimal	Digital transformation is not understood or barely defined.
2	Transitional	The importance of digital transformation is starting to be acknowledged by the organization.
3	Customer-driven	Digital transformation is integrated into some parts of business operations.
4	Transformed	Digital transformation is embedded across organizations.

Employee performance is assessed on a four-point scale from **Novice** to **Expert**. At the **Novice** level, employees show limited engagement and low productivity, while at the **Expert** level, employees demonstrate exceptional skill, high engagement, and outstanding productivity.

Employee Performance		Description
4	Expert	Exceptional mastery with deep engagement and outstanding productivity.
3	Advanced	High proficiency with strong engagement and above-average productivity.
2	Intermediate	Competent performance with moderate engagement and consistent productivity.
1	Novice	Basic performance with limited engagement and low productivity.

Organizational efficiency is similarly measured from **Basic** to **Exemplary**. Basic efficiency involves foundational practices in finance, operations, and marketing, while **Exemplary** efficiency signifies exceptional performance, optimized processes, and significant innovation.

Organization's Efficiency		Description
4	Exemplary	Outstanding efficiency marked by exceptional performance and innovation.
3	Advanced	Enhanced efficiency with optimized processes and personalized approaches.
2	Intermediate	Improved efficiency with effective management across all areas.
1	Basic or Unsure	Foundational efficiency with basic practices in finance, operations, and marketing.

Together, these dimensions create a comprehensive narrative roadmap, guiding organizations from the initial stages of digital awareness to full transformation. By continuously improving employee capabilities and operational efficiency, the model offers leaders with helpful insights into the current state of their organization and clear steps for advancing efficiency, engagement, and innovation.

Phase 2. Implementation

The Implementation phase of the Progressive Business Transformation Model consists of three key steps aimed at driving digital maturity across all facets of the organization. These steps establish a structured foundation for assessing

current digital capabilities, developing human capital, and implementing a feedback mechanism that aligns with maturity goals.

Implementation 1. Establish an Effective Assessment of Digital Maturity level on People, Culture, Capacity, Capability, Technology, and Leadership

Activities	Persons/ Departments Responsible	Key Performance Indicators (KPIs)	Key Result Areas (KRAs)
Organize an ad hoc committee for digital maturity level assessment and review	Lead: Human Resources Support: Department Heads Approver: Human Resource (HR) Manager	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Creation of a memo of the ad hoc committee that the HR Manager should approve ✓ Dissemination of the memo 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Organize the ad hoc committee whenever possible
Assess maturity level and gap analysis in terms of People, Culture, Capacity, Capability, Technology, and Leadership	Lead: Human Resources Support: Department Heads Approver: HR Manager	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ A report of assessment results ✓ Ad hoc committee meeting to discuss findings 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ The report with the findings should be submitted to the HR Manager for review, feedback, and signatory for final confirmation
Restructuring current HR programs and set activities	Lead: Human Resources	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ HR to provide information to stakeholders ✓ HR to ask for proposed 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ HRM presents the restructured plan for the approval of C-level top management

with clear success criteria	Support: Department Heads Approver: HR Manager	changes from each department head for the improvements	
Implementation of new and updated programs toward meeting defined success criteria	Lead: Human Resources Support: Dept. Heads Figurehead: HR Manager	✓ Official rollout of new and updated programs	✓ All employees understand the reasons and benefits of the implemented change
Monitoring and reassessment	Lead: Human Resources Support: Department Heads	✓ HR to identify checkpoints ✓ HR to reassess the current level and share results with all concerned stakeholders	✓ The HR Manager approves reports for dissemination, and stakeholders should receive the reports ✓ HR Manager to drive the next schedule for reassessment

The first implementation area addresses conclusions and recommendations from Statement of the Problem (SOP) items 2, 3, 5, 6, 7, and 8, informed by both qualitative and quantitative findings. Organizations are advised to re-assess, restructure, and re-implement strategies to elevate digital maturity across essential domains: people, culture, capacity, capability, technology, and leadership.

Specifically, to thrive in the evolving technology sector, organizations should focus on a progressive business transformation that builds customer trust, diversifies services, and enhances efficiency through streamlined operations and optimized resource allocation. Continued investment in Research and Development, particularly in AI and machine learning, will strengthen resilience and foster innovation.

To support these goals, an ad hoc committee comprising representatives from all departments, not solely human resources, should be formed to assess and review the organizational maturity level. This approach ensures that insights are gathered from all areas, enabling a thorough understanding of the organization's digital strong points and growth opportunities. Leveraging employees' awareness of digital opportunities, organizations should foster innovation, engagement, and collaboration while optimizing resources and investing in training. Strengthened feedback mechanisms can help leadership address employee needs and build a more agile workforce, reinforcing commitment to transformation.

In addition to this foundational program, a diversification and innovation strategy is proposed to enable organizations to expand their service offerings and continuously innovate to meet evolving customer needs. This strategy includes organizing service expansion workshops with cross-functional teams to identify underrepresented service areas, brainstorm new offerings, and leverage existing strengths to address market gaps. A dedicated budget for research and development

will support integrating emerging technologies such as AI and machine learning, encouraging employees to contribute ideas for innovative solutions that enhance customer satisfaction. Digital literacy campaigns will also be launched, equipping all employees, particularly older workers, to use new technologies effectively and foster a more adaptable workforce.

The expected outcomes of the Diversification and Innovation Strategy include increased service diversification, enhanced credibility, improved customer satisfaction, and a culture of innovation within the organization. The proposed implementations are ad hoc, with decisions tailored to current and future business needs. Full authority is granted to business technology companies and their human resource departments to adapt and enhance these programs for optimal organizational maturity. This comprehensive approach aligns organizational capabilities with strategic goals, positioning the organization for sustained growth and adaptability in a rapidly evolving market.

Implementation 2. Advancing Human Capital and Fostering Continuous Learning

Activities	Persons/ Departments Responsible	Key Performance Indicators (KPIs)	Key Result Areas (KRAs)
Organize an ad hoc committee for Competency-based Human Capital Management	Lead: Human Resources Support: Department Heads	✓ Creation of a memo of the ad hoc committee that the HR Manager should approve	✓ Organize the ad hoc committee whenever possible

	Approver: Human Resource (HR) Manager	✓ Dissemination of the memo	
Perform small group meetings. Covered topics may include: a. Factor and analyze productivity b. Factor and analyze performance c. Digitalization d. Recognize top performers, e. Govern critical success tasks f. Set target milestones and conduct success factors g. Validate and reward	Lead: Human Resources Participants: Department Heads Validator: Human Resource (HR) Manager	✓ A clear program plans ✓ Ad hoc committee meeting to discuss criteria and craft a proposal	✓ The report with the findings should be submitted to the HR Manager for review, feedback, and signatory for final confirmation
Risk assessment and pilot test	Lead: Human Resources Support: Department Heads Figurehead: HR Manager	✓ Risk assessment has been performed supported by a risk register ✓ Dissemination of reports about the pilot tests and rollout plan	✓ Validation and approval of HR Manager

Rollout implementation of a Competency-based Human Capital Management Program	Lead: Human Resources Support: Department Heads Figurehead: HR Manager	✓ Information dissemination includes e-mails, videos, and short meetings.	✓ All employees understand the reasons and benefits of the program
Monitoring and reassessment	Lead: Human Resources Support: Department Heads	✓ HR to identify checkpoints ✓ HR to reassess current maturity level and share results with all concerned stakeholders	✓ HR Manager approves reports for dissemination ✓ All stakeholders should receive the reports ✓ HR Manager to drive the next schedule for reassessment

The second implementation area addresses conclusions and recommendations from Statement of the Problem (SOP) items 1, 3, 4, 6, 7, and 8, informed by both qualitative and quantitative findings. Organizations should prioritize human capital advancement through strategic investment in education, training, and development programs across different generations within the workforce. This goal can be achieved through a Competency-Based Human Capital

Management Transformation Program, which will benefit individual employees and positively impact the organization.

To support progression in digital maturity, the human resources department should emphasize competency-based improvements aligned with the company's business models. This approach encourages development, career progression, and transformation among employees, ensuring they meet the evolving demands of the organization. Recognizing that employees are the foundation of any successful business, the implementation highlights the necessity of investing in their competencies to maximize productivity and performance.

In alignment with this focus, a Continuous Learning and Mentorship Initiative is proposed to foster a culture of ongoing development and enhance collaboration between younger and more experienced employees. The initiative aims to create an environment where continuous learning is valued and knowledge sharing is encouraged. Key components of this initiative include developing ongoing training programs that focus on emerging technologies, digital tools, and essential soft skills like emotional intelligence and time management. Such targeted training sessions will cater to the various needs of employees at different job levels and tenures.

Additionally, the initiative will implement a mentorship pairing system, connecting younger employees with seasoned staff members to facilitate knowledge transfer and bridge generational divides. This mentorship program will

enable younger workers to gain valuable insights from their mentors' experiences while providing older employees opportunities to adapt to new technologies. Regular engagement surveys will also be conducted to assess employee satisfaction and the effectiveness of learning initiatives, allowing for ongoing refinement of training content and program structure. Another critical component of this implementation is the Digital Maturity Enhancement Program, aimed at improving organizational efficiency by elevating digital maturity across all workforce levels. This program includes tailored training initiatives designed to be job-level specific, ensuring that employees receive relevant training that enhances their performance in their respective roles. For example, advanced training will be delivered for Officers, while foundational training will be provided for Entry-Level Professionals. Additionally, annual maturity assessments will be conducted to evaluate the organization's digital maturity levels, providing insights into areas needing improvement and helping to prioritize development efforts.

The expected outcomes of this comprehensive approach include enhanced digital skills across the workforce, improved employee performance and engagement, and increased organizational efficiency in financial, operational, and marketing areas. By integrating competency-based management with continuous learning, mentorship, and a focus on digital maturity, this implementation supports employees in reaching their full potential while aligning their growth with the organization's strategic goals. Ultimately, this strategy contributes to a Progressive

Business Transformation Model that enhances the organization's overall maturity and capability.

Implementation 3: Creation of an effective 360-degree feedback mechanism on Human Resource Management operations and programs relevant to maturity level and digital transformation

Activities	Persons/ Departments Responsible	Key Performance Indicators (KPIs)	Key Result Areas (KRAs)
Assessment of evaluation tools used for Human Resource programs	Lead: Human Resources Support: Department Heads Approver: Human Resource (HR) Manager	✓ Report on findings ✓ Ad hoc committee checkpoint review of status and next actions	✓ The report with the findings should be submitted to the HR Manager for review, feedback, and signatory for final confirmation
Developing a new, updated version of the evaluation and 360-degree feedback tool	Lead: Human Resources Support: Department Heads Approver: Human Resource (HR) Manager	✓ Revisions should be coordinated, reviewed, and approved.	✓ HR Manager approves new 360-degree feedback tool.
Risk assessment and pilot test	Lead: Human Resources Support: Department Heads	✓ Risk assessment has been performed supported by a risk register	✓ Validation and approval of HR Manager

	Figurehead: HR Manager	✓ Dissemination of reports about the pilot tests and rollout plan	
Rollout implementation of new 360-degree feedback mechanism	Lead: Human Resources Support: Department Heads Figurehead: HR Manager	✓ Information dissemination includes e-mails, videos, and short meetings.	✓ All employees understand the reasons and benefits of the program
Monitoring and reassessment	Lead: Human Resources Support: Department Heads	✓ HR to identify checkpoints ✓ HR to reassess current maturity level and share results with all concerned stakeholders	✓ HR Manager approves reports for dissemination ✓ All stakeholders should receive the reports ✓ HR Manager to drive the next schedule for reassessment

The third proposed program area focuses on implementing an effective 360-degree feedback mechanism among business technology employees and the human resources department towards achieving a more systematic way of capturing feedback and actions. This implementation is a response to the conclusion and recommendation for Statement of the Problem number 3, wherein business

technology companies and human resources departments should perform continuous assessments of maturity level on a yearly interval to provide the management the perspective and ability to evaluate, measure, and improve productivity and performance through relevant and systemized information for decision making and improvements in areas and operations of the business. The researcher believes that for a business technology company to achieve progression and advancement of maturity level, it should be guided by employees' captured views and feedback when setting direction for any future business transformation.

Phase 3. Reassessment

The Reassessment phase ensures that digital transformation efforts remain aligned with the organization's evolving goals and responsive to shifting market conditions, technological advancements, and employee needs. Designed to review progress, refine strategies, and sustain momentum, this phase provides feedback loops that help the organization remain on a path of continuous improvement.

Digital maturity tracking is a key component, systematically measuring progress against the organization's maturity targets. This involves revisiting the core dimensions from the initial assessment, people, culture, capacity, technology, and leadership, to understand areas of growth, emerging challenges, and new priorities. By comparing the initial maturity state to the current one, organizations can refine their focus and adapt their strategies accordingly.

Employee performance evaluation also plays a central role, assessing both individual and team effectiveness within digital transformation initiatives. This evaluation looks at technical proficiency and adaptability to new tools and processes. By gathering performance metrics and employee feedback, organizations can identify skill gaps, training needs, and areas where further support or resources may be necessary. Recognizing top performers and motivating ongoing engagement with transformation goals fosters a strong sense of participation and achievement.

Equally important is measuring engagement levels, which includes assessing employee satisfaction, motivation, and alignment with transformation objectives. High engagement reflects a healthy, adaptive culture essential for sustaining momentum in digital transformation. Lower engagement levels may indicate where employees feel disconnected from the transformation journey, highlighting the need for strengthened communication and involvement strategies.

The productivity and efficiency assessment examines the overall impact of transformation on operational efficiency. Organizations gain insight into whether digital initiatives are delivering the desired outcomes by analyzing metrics like time savings, process completion rates, and resource utilization. This understanding of efficiency and productivity improvements provides a clearer picture of the tangible benefits of transformation efforts.

Organizations can refine their transformation strategy as needed based on findings from digital maturity tracking, employee evaluations, engagement, and productivity assessments. Adjustments may involve re-prioritizing initiatives, updating technologies, enhancing training, or recalibrating leadership approaches.

The Reassessment phase emphasizes a **continuous improvement cycle, bringing the organization back to Phase 1 of the Assessment** with a refreshed understanding of its current and future needs. This cyclical process ensures that transformation remains adaptive, effective, and in sync with the organization's strategic objectives, reinforcing its capacity to drive long-term digital growth and resilience.

Final Insights: A Holistic Approach to Navigating Digital Transformation through the Progressive Business Transformation Model

The proposed Progressive Business Transformation Model emerges from a comprehensive analysis of the challenges faced by organizations in adapting to the rapid pace of digital transformation. In an era where technological advancements dictate market dynamics, organizations must evolve to maintain their competitive edge. This model synthesizes findings from both qualitative and quantitative analyses, highlighting the critical need for a structured approach to enhance digital maturity across key areas, such as people, culture, capacity, capability, technology, and leadership. By addressing these interconnected

dimensions, the model offers a holistic framework that guides organizations through their transformation journey, ensuring that they are responsive to change and proactive in shaping their futures.

The benefits of this model extend to various stakeholders, including businesses, industries, and operational teams. For businesses, the model provides a roadmap for continuous improvement, allowing them to align their strategies with the evolving needs of their customers and market conditions. By fostering a culture of innovation and resilience, organizations can diversify their service offerings, enhance customer satisfaction, and drive revenue growth. The structured implementation of training programs, mentorship initiatives, and digital literacy campaigns equips employees with the necessary skills and knowledge to thrive in a digital-first environment, thereby boosting overall performance and engagement.

In a broader context, the Progressive Business Transformation Model is a valuable industry resource. As organizations across various sectors adopt this framework, they contribute to a collective advancement in operational efficiency and innovation. This model prepares companies to navigate the complexities of digital transformation and fosters a culture of collaboration and knowledge sharing among employees at all levels. By investing in their workforce and embracing continuous learning, organizations can build a more agile, adaptive,

and competitive landscape that benefits the entire industry, paving the way for sustainable growth and success in the future.

APPENDIX B

TURNITIN SIMILARITY REPORT

The acceptable Turnitin similarity is below 25%, with this study recording a 9% similarity index.

The screenshot displays a Turnitin Originality Report for the document 'Major Chapters (Manoy).docx' submitted by 'fsfse sswwe'. The report shows a similarity index of 9%. A 'Digital Receipt' overlay is present, providing submission details and a preview of the document's first page. The receipt includes the following information:

- Submission author: fsfse sswwe
- Assignment title: Submit
- Submission title: Major Chapters (Manoy).docx
- File name: Major_Chapters_Manoy_.docx
- File size: 7.82M
- Page count: 304
- Word count: 44,502
- Character count: 285,748
- Submission date: 12-Jan-2025 12:18AM (UTC-0600)
- Submission ID: 2562710346

The receipt also includes a preview of the document's first page, which contains the following text:

UNIVERSITY COURSE
UNIVERSITY COURSE

Chapter 1
Introduction

This section has the essential groundwork for the research by including...
...to identify the research problem, to understand the background to provide context...
...to identify the research problem, to understand the background to provide context...
...to identify the research problem, to understand the background to provide context...

Background of the Study

An essential part of a research proposal is the background information...
...to identify the research problem, to understand the background to provide context...
...to identify the research problem, to understand the background to provide context...

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APPENDIX C

GRAMMARLY QUALITY OF WRITING REPORT

Chapters 1 & 2

Performance

Text score: 97 out of 100. This score represents the quality of writing in this document. You can increase it by addressing Grammarly's suggestions. 97

Word count

Characters	80,690	Reading time	44 min 12 sec
Words	11,052	Speaking time	1 hr 25 min
Sentences	888		

Readability

Metrics compared to other Grammarly users

Word length	6	<div style="width: 100%; border: 1px solid gray; position: relative;"><div style="width: 100%; height: 100%; background-color: #ccc;"></div><div style="width: 100%; height: 100%; background-color: #008000; position: absolute; top: 0; left: 0;"></div></div>	Above average
Sentence length	12.4	<div style="width: 100%; border: 1px solid gray; position: relative;"><div style="width: 100%; height: 100%; background-color: #ccc;"></div><div style="width: 100%; height: 100%; background-color: #008000; position: absolute; top: 0; left: 0;"></div></div>	Above average
Readability score	17 ⊙		

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Chapter 3 (Set 1)

Performance

Text score: 97 out of 100. This score represents the quality of writing in this document. You can increase it by addressing Grammarly's suggestions. 97

Word count

Characters	85,028	Reading time	47 min 1 sec
Words	11,757	Speaking time	1 hr 30 min
Sentences	1,136		

Readability

Metrics compared to other Grammarly users

Word length	5.9	<div style="width: 100%; border: 1px solid gray; position: relative;"><div style="width: 100%; height: 100%; background-color: #ccc;"></div><div style="width: 100%; height: 100%; background-color: #008000; position: absolute; top: 0; left: 0;"></div></div>	Above average
Sentence length	10.3	<div style="width: 100%; border: 1px solid gray; position: relative;"><div style="width: 100%; height: 100%; background-color: #ccc;"></div><div style="width: 100%; height: 100%; background-color: #008000; position: absolute; top: 0; left: 0;"></div></div>	Above average
Readability score	24 ⊙		

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Chapter 3 (Set 2)

Performance

Text score: 96 out of 100. This score represents the quality of writing in this document. You can increase it by addressing Grammarly's suggestions. 96

Word count

Characters	84,315	Reading time	46 min 38 sec
Words	11,660	Speaking time	1 hr 29 min
Sentences	1,325		

Readability

Metrics compared to other Grammarly users

Word length	5.8	<div style="width: 100%; border: 1px solid gray; position: relative;"><div style="width: 100%; height: 100%; background-color: #ccc;"></div><div style="width: 100%; height: 100%; background-color: #008000; position: absolute; top: 0; left: 0;"></div></div>	Above average
Sentence length	8.8	<div style="width: 100%; border: 1px solid gray; position: relative;"><div style="width: 100%; height: 100%; background-color: #ccc;"></div><div style="width: 100%; height: 100%; background-color: #008000; position: absolute; top: 0; left: 0;"></div></div>	Above average
Readability score	23 ⊙		

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Chapter 4

Performance

Text score: 96 out of 100. This score represents the quality of writing in this document. You can increase it by addressing Grammarly's suggestions. 96

Word count

Characters	24,378	Reading time	12 min 51 sec
Words	3,213	Speaking time	24 min 42 sec
Sentences	161		

Readability

Metrics compared to other Grammarly users

Word length	6.4	<div style="width: 80%; height: 10px; background: linear-gradient(to right, #ccc, #2e8b57);"></div>	Above average
Sentence length	20	<div style="width: 80%; height: 10px; background: linear-gradient(to right, #ccc, #2e8b57);"></div>	Above average
Readability score	3		

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Appendix A – Output of the Study

Performance

Text score: 96 out of 100. This score represents the quality of writing in this document. You can increase it by addressing Grammarly's suggestions. 96

Word count

Characters	30,169	Reading time	15 min 37 sec
Words	3,905	Speaking time	30 min 2 sec
Sentences	327		

Readability

Metrics compared to other Grammarly users

Word length	6.5	<div style="width: 80%; height: 10px; background: linear-gradient(to right, #ccc, #2e8b57);"></div>	Above average
Sentence length	11.9	<div style="width: 80%; height: 10px; background: linear-gradient(to right, #ccc, #2e8b57);"></div>	Above average
Readability score	7		

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grammarly

Your Grammarly Documents

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CREATED	TITLE	TEXT PREVIEW
2025-01-12 07:10 UTC	Major Chapters (Manoy) Grammarly -	1 APPENDIX A PROPOSED PROGRESSIVE BUSINESS TRANSFORMATION MODEL (THE OUTPUT OF THE STUDY) The Progressive Business Transformati...
2025-01-12 07:06 UTC	Major Chapters (Manoy) Grammarly -	1 Chapter 4 SUMMARY OF FINDINGS, CONCLUSIONS, AND RECOMMENDATIONS This chapter outlines the summary of findings, conclusion...
2025-01-12 07:02 UTC	Major Chapters (Manoy) Grammarly -	1 Table 42. Level of Organizations' Efficiency Based on Operations Indicators Weighted Mean Verbal Interpretation Daily Operations: The organization manages...
2025-01-12 06:55 UTC	Major Chapters (Manoy) Grammarly -	1 Chapter 3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS This chapter provides the analyzed data along with a detailed examination and interpretation of the problems outlined ...
2025-01-12 06:40 UTC	Major Chapters (Manoy) Grammarly -	1 Chapter 1 INTRODUCTION This section lays the essential groundwork for the research by including several critical components. It encompasses the backgroun...

APPENDIX D

CERTIFICATE OF PAPER PRESENTATION

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for presenting a research paper at the **2nd Asia Multidisciplinary Research Conference 2024 [AMRC2024]** with the theme **“Building Bridges: Integrating Diverse Disciplines for Asia's Progress,”** held virtually on December 8, 2024.

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APPENDIX E

CERTIFICATE OF PARTICIPATION

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Abstract ID: AMRC2024-OFD-004

Paper Title: Triangulating Digital Maturity, Organizational Efficiency, and Employees' Performance: Pioneering a Progressive Business Transformation Model

for winning the Best Presenter Competition at the **2nd Asia Multidisciplinary Research Conference 2024 [AMRC2024]** with the theme **“Building Bridges: Integrating Diverse Disciplines for Asia's Progress,”** held virtually on December 8, 2024.

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